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The art of measuring art:
Methodical development and validation of RizbA,
a transdisciplinary rating instrument for
two-dimensional pictorial works

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Art should comfort the disturbed and disturb the comfortable.

Cesar A. Cruz

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Abstract

Although psychological research on art has some tradition, measuring artworks and their formal content has received surprisingly little attention in quantitative research. One reason for this neglect may be the humanistic or qualitative orientation of art sciences; another may be the lack of reliable, valid, and objective instruments for measuring pictorial expression. By bridging art theory and psychometrics, the Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA) addresses this gap.

The scale was developed and validated in four validation studies on a total of 899 pictorial works by contemporary artists and nonprofessionals, being rated by a total of 1,577 art experts. A 26-item version was developed in the first study. The second study validated the scale on pictorial works by nonprofessionals, the third on pictures by contemporary artists. Statistical quality criteria such as item difficulty, capacity of differentiation between images, test-retest reliability, inter-rater reliability, Principal Component Analysis and Tucker's coefficients of congruence were computed. The fourth study specified three path models and conducted a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). Three further methodical studies developed a machine learning approach, validated a version usable for non-art experts, and provided an item pool for three-dimensional works. Three application studies used the scale on image samples by persons with chronic pain, depression, delirium, and by children.

The results suggest high capacity of differentiation (η_p^2 [.28, .90]), high test-retest reliability (r [.86, .92]), and modest to excellent inter-rater reliability (ICC [.53, .92]). Regarding the CFA, only one model partially suggests an acceptable fit.

The findings imply reliability and generalizability while the question of the factor structure persists and speaks to a methodological gap between empirical evidence and theory. Since art is ambiguous, with various approaches to its analysis, postdisciplinary approaches are needed to do justice to it.

Zusammenfassung

In Anbetracht der Geschichte von Kunstpsychologie ist überraschend, wie wenig Aufmerksamkeit der Messung von Werk und formalem Inhalt bislang zuteilwurde. Ein Grund hierfür mag die geisteswissenschaftliche bzw. qualitative Ausrichtung der Kunstwissenschaften sein, ein anderer der Mangel an reliablen, validen und objektiven Messinstrumenten für bildlichen Ausdruck. Das Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (RizbA) schließt die Lücke und verbindet Kunst mit Psychometrie.

Die Skala wurde in vier Validierungsstudien entwickelt. 899 zeitgenössische Bilder nicht- und professioneller Künstler*innen wurden von insgesamt 1.577 Kunstexpert*innen bewertet. Die erste Studie ergab eine 26-Item Version, die zweite validierte diese an nicht-professioneller und die dritte an professioneller Kunst. Gütekriterien wie Itemschwierigkeit, Diskriminanzfähigkeit zwischen Bildern, Test-Retest- und Inter-Rater*innen-Reliabilität, Hauptkomponentenanalysen sowie Tucker-Kongruenzkoeffizienten wurden berechnet. Die vierte Studie spezifizierte drei Pfadmodelle und prüfte diese mit konfirmatorischen Faktorenanalysen (KFA). Drei weitere methodische Studien entwickelten einen Machine Learning Ansatz, eine Version für Nicht-Kunstexpert*innen und einen Itempool für dreidimensionale Werke. In drei Anwendungsstudien wurde die Skala an Bildstichproben von Menschen mit chronischen Schmerzen, Depression, Delirium sowie von Kindern erprobt.

Die Skala verfügt über eine hohe Diskriminanzfähigkeit (η_p^2 [.28, .90]), hohe Retest-Reliabilität (r [.86, .92]) und ausreichende bis ausgezeichnete Inter-Rater*innen-Reliabilität (ICC [.53, .92]). Die KFA ergibt nur für ein Modell teilweise akzeptablen Fit.

Die Ergebnisse sprechen für Reliabilität und Generalisierbarkeit. Die Frage der Faktorenstruktur bleibt bestehen und deutet auf eine methodische Lücke zwischen Empirie und Theorie hin. Da Kunst mehrdeutig ist und eine Vielzahl an Analysemöglichkeiten mit sich bringt, benötigt es mehr postdisziplinärer Ansätze um ihr gerecht werden können.

Ethics approval

This research received a positive vote of the Ethics Committee for Creative Arts Therapies at the Nürtingen-Geislingen University, Germany.

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Open Science

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Abbreviations

AAA	Assessment of Art Attributes
AART-ASSESS-P	Anthroposophic Art Therapy Assessment Paint
API	Application Programming Interface
ART	Artificial intelligence raters
CFA	Confirmatory Factor Analysis
CO	Color
COM	Composition
DAP	Draw a Person
DAPA	Descriptive Assessment of Psychiatric Art
DoKuPro	Dokumentation Kunsttherapeutischer Prozesse [Documentation of art therapeutic processes]
dTDT	digital Tree Drawing Test
EX	Expression
EFA	Exploratory Factor Analysis
FEATS	Formal Elements Art Therapy Scale
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
MO	Motion
NBS	Nürtinger Beurteilungsskala [Nürtingen rating scale]
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
RE	Representation
RidbA	Ratinginstrument für dreidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten [Rating instrument for three-dimensional pictorial works]
RizbA	Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten [Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works]
SH	Shaping
SP	Spatiality
TAT	Thematic Apperception Test

Indices

CFI	Comparative fit index
CI	Confidence interval
df	Degrees of freedom
ICC	Intraclass correlation coefficient
M	Mean
MLR	Robust maximum likelihood estimator
MSE	Mean squared error
N	Sample size
η^2	Partial eta-squared effect size estimator
p	p-value
p_i	Item difficulty
RMSEA	Root-mean-square error of approximation
s_i^2	Item variance
SD	Standard deviation
SRMR	Standardized root-mean-square residual
T1	1st time of measurement (test)
T2	2nd time of measurement (retest)
TLI	Tucker-Lewis index
χ^2	Chi-square

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1 Theory

1.1 Why measure art?

It has been more than half a century since Walter Benjamin (1969) argued for a deliberate handling of traditional concepts like creatorship and ingenuity, eternal value and mystery. Visual art, including such concepts as creativity and aesthetics, has been subject to psychological research for some time (Allesch, 2006, p. 33 ff.; Commare et al., 2018). Starting with Gustav Theodor Fechner (1876), founder of empirical aesthetics, art psychological research by now includes a variety of concepts, e.g., perception, experience, emotion, aesthetic appreciation, personality, creativity (Schuster, 2002, p. 12), and fields of research, such as empirical and experimental aesthetics. Despite more than a century of empirical research on art, researchers still regard art as a mysterious aspect of human experience (Leder et al., 2012).

One of the reasons might be that art and psychology stem from different scientific disciplines (cf. Utitz, 1929). There are many approaches to the analysis of artworks. Most of them come from the humanities or qualitative empirical studies, which are often argued to do more justice to the complexity of art. However, for a complex understanding of aesthetics and creative processes it is crucial to use both idiographic and nomothetic data (Machotka, 2012). While the first offers specification and richness of data, group data clarifies underlying structures and allows generalizability of phenomena. To measure art in nuanced profiles, we need transdisciplinary approaches to the subject. Arts and humanities offer manifold approaches to image analysis, while psychometrics offers the methods to quantitatively measure constructs. If we bridge the gap between those academic cultures (Leder et al., 2018), an art theory-based and reliable measurement tool for artworks can arise. This might even solve some of the mystery of the ways art affects us.

Surprisingly, quantitative research has paid little attention to art-making and the artwork itself. Most studies in art psychology, creativity research, and empirical aesthetics focus on the psychological correlates of art (e.g., Martindale, 2007; North & Hargreaves, 1996; Specht, 2007; Tröndle & Tschacher, 2012), but do not take into account the artwork itself and its formal content. When they do, art is often operationalized as categorical, independent variables. For example, in experiments,

visual art is often measured in terms of broad or even dichotomous categories, such as art vs. non-art (e.g., Hager et al., 2012), genre (e.g., Commare et al., 2018), epoch of art (e.g., Leder et al., 2012), representational vs. abstract classifications (e.g., Gridley, 2006, 2013; Leder et al., 2012; Mastandrea & Crano, 2019; Meskin et al., 2013), degree of abstraction (e.g., Specht, 2007), symmetry vs. asymmetry (e.g., Leder et al., 2018) or beauty vs. ugliness (e.g., Ishizu & Zeki, 2011). But treating artworks categorically yields only a limited range of information (Maclagan, 1999). Also, it is contrary to the use of dimensional scales currently considered state-of-the-art in psychology. Only few studies go into further detail; for example, by identifying different forms of complexity in artworks (Nadal et al., 2010) or by examining the relationship between perception of image complexity and content-related processes in paintings (Commare et al., 2018). Another surprising aspect is that most studies use a small range of noncontemporary images from art history as stimuli, but hardly any contemporary art. Developing a universal tool to quantitatively measure artworks enriches art psychological methods and might give us a better understanding of correlations between artworks and psychological variables.

1.2 Previous research

I begin with an overview of approaches and instruments in the transdisciplinary field between art and psychology. Since this is not a systematic review, no claim for exhaustivity is made. To categorize the concepts, they are classified in projective, qualitative, and quantitative methodology; note that that some do cross-relate in terms of mixed methodology. The instruments are briefly discussed in terms of convergency and divergency in view of the objective of this research: a quantitative measurement of pictorial expression that fulfills scientific criteria, i.e., objectivity, validity, and reliability.

1.2.1 Projective instruments

When people think of testing in connection with art, what most often comes to mind is the projective drawing test. Although widely used in clinical settings (Lilienfeld et al., 2000) the validity of such tests is controversial. To name but a few examples, the *Bird's Nest Drawing* (Kaiser, 1996; Kaiser & Deaver, 2009; Yoon et al., 2020) seeks to assess attachment security. Kaiser (1996) inter alia associates the inclusion of birds in a drawing with high attachment security and depictions of a bottomless nest with

low attachment security. However, validation studies are based on small nonrepresentative sample sizes (Kaiser & Deaver, 2009). The *Draw a Person* test (DAP; Naglieri et al., 1988) is suggested for evaluating children's intelligence. In a representative validation study Troncone et al. (2020) found only poor validity and concluded that it fails as a psychometrically sound assessment of intellectual functioning. A meta-analysis by Lilienfeld et al. (2000) of the *Rorschach Inkblot Test*, the *Thematic Apperception Test* (TAT), and *human figure drawings* comes to the conclusion that empirical support for validity is only given for a small number of indices. Moosbrugger and Kelava (2007; S. 32) state that projective tests usually do not meet the required scientific quality standards of objectivity, reliability, and validity and can at best serve as exploratory aids. They might be a viable complementary path for diagnostic anamnesis interviews or serve in a therapeutic intervention. For example, the *My Family as Animals* technique (Rio, 2001) can be used for including younger children in family therapy processes.

Beyond that, new methods based on projective tests emerged. For example, the original *tree-drawing test* (Koch, 1957; Stanzani Maserati et al., 2015) associates motif-related aspects like roots, trunk or crown with personality, intelligence, or psychotrauma – all associations of questionable validity. The *digital Tree Drawing Test* (dTDT; Robens et al., 2019) also asks individuals to paint a tree of their choice on a digitizer but refers to cognitive mechanisms like visuospatial processes, visual memory, motor execution, and planning abilities. It includes criteria such as a trunk-to-crown ratio but mainly focuses on the work process, e.g., the total duration it takes to paint, including a ratio between painting and not-painting time or the pen's pressure on the screen. In an exploratory study, Robens et al. (2019) compared individuals with mild cognitive impairment, early dementia of the Alzheimer type, and healthy controls. Participants with a cognitive impairment used fewer colors and line widths and changed less often between both, line widths and colors, than the control group. Also, their images showed fewer contrasts and heterogeneity.

Without going too deep into the debate on the use and usefulness of projective tests, this work does not aim for projective measurement of a latent variable that might lie beyond a picture. For now, it aims solely to capture a picture without jumping to conclusions about the creator's psyche.

1.2.2 Qualitative instruments

The second category is qualitative instruments. They do not allow quantifiability but provide theoretical frameworks for scale development. Since this is a quantitative approach, only two qualitative instruments are presented, whereby the second provides particularly important theoretical categories that will be reflected in the test construction.

The first is the qualitative content analysis for systematizing pictorial works (Thyme et al., 2013), which relates to *qualitative content analysis* (Graneheim & Lundman, 2004) as a widely used method in qualitative research. Combined with the creator's clarifying remarks before and after creating, colors and pictorial elements are coded and categorized. This results in sub- and overarching themes. It is used as a method for analyzing pictures and verbal testimonies from psychodynamic art psychotherapy sessions and claims to keep manifest messages and latent meanings in images intact (Thyme et al., 2013). Compared to most projective tests, this method does not just rely on the picture to draw conclusions about the psyche but takes into account the creator's inherent perspective.

The second instrument is a systematic assessment of images based on a phenomenological perspective on art therapy and artistic expression (Betensky, 1991): the *phenomenological picture analysis*. The theoretical starting point is the aesthetic state in its dual function as both a method of cognition and a therapeutic agent in art therapy. In a processual dialogue between creator and therapist, various picture elements are viewed and discussed: subjective spontaneous impression, material in terms of choice and technique, predominant features, color, shaping, motion, spatiality, a description of its content, expression, and composition (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003).

1.2.3 Quantitative instruments

Table 1 provides an overview of existing quantitative instruments in alphabetical order. Since it is not a systematic review, there is no claim to completeness, especially regarding instruments in languages other than English or German. Most of these instruments originate from art therapy, which is specifically interested in correlations between artworks and inner representations of its creator (e.g., emotion, cognition, behavior, diagnosis). This discipline and its hypothesized mechanisms are based on

this assumption. However, most of the existing tools either do not fulfill the objective of being a universal tool for all types of images, or they do not sufficiently meet methodical standards of reliability, validity, and objectivity. Several of them do not follow a psychological paradigm of test construction, which becomes apparent in this overview: firstly, the terminology and methodology differs between instruments. Few theoretically define the construct that is to be measured. Many publications do not use terms like scale or factors. These inadequacies can both be attributed to the fact that scales do not originate in a psychometric methodology based on test theory. Secondly, the literature is short on information, including the scales themselves. Only one study provides materials under the premises of Open Methodology.

A new instrument for measuring pictorial expression is the *Anthroposophic Art Therapy Assessment Paint* (AART-ASSESS-P; Mehl et al., 2020) for assessing anthroposophic art therapy. It has been validated on a small clinical sample as pre-/posttest on art therapy sessions. However, the reported inter-rater reliability is weak; a common problem among existing art therapeutic instruments (Eitel et al., 2008). The *Descriptive Assessment of Psychiatric Art* (DAPA; Elbing & Hacking, 2001; Hacking & Foreman, 2000; Hacking et al., 1996; Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2004) is a coding system that separates the image into 20 fields equal in size, rates each of them separately, and then calculates means across fields. The instrument requires a prior rater training and is applicable only to art in a psychiatric context. The *Documentation of art therapeutic processes* (Dokumentation Kunsttherapeutischer Prozesse (DoKuPro); Elbing & Hölzer, 2007; Elbing et al., 2009) serves as a systematic documentation tool for the client's behavior during art therapy sessions and includes various levels within the triangular therapeutic relationship among client, art therapist, and art medium (Bat Or & Zilcha-Mano, 2018). Regarding the artistic product, only one module including 11 items is relevant, i.e., the expression and representation of the object. The *Diagnostic Drawing Series* (Cohen & Mills, 2016; Mills, 2003) is a standardized art interview based on three picture drawing tasks using a specific choice of material. The participant is asked to first “make a picture using these materials”, second, “draw a picture of a tree”, and third, “make a picture of how you're feeling, using lines, shapes, and colors”. These images are rated based on 24 categories. With high inter-rater reliabilities being reported, it is designed to contribute to diagnostics and is applicable to research and practical (clinical) use. However, it does not use Likert scales and due to specific tasks and material is not

applicable to all types of images. The *Formal Elements Art Therapy Scale* (FEATS; Gantt, 2016; Gantt & Anderson, 2009) was developed for rating a specific drawing task, the *Person Picking an Apple From a Tree* assessment (Betts, 2006). Only some scales can be applied to non-directed art. Also, the construct to be measured goes beyond pictorial expression and inherently refers to the creator's psyche with scales such as logic and problem-solving. The *Nürtingen rating scale* (Nürtinger Beurteilungsskala (NBS); Eber et al., 1998; Elbing & Hacking, 2001) can be used regardless of material, format, or motif, but has not been empirically tested in terms of scientific quality criteria. The *Systematic picture analysis* (Gruber et al., 2002) is an observational tool describing formal-aesthetic criteria, but does not offer throughout interval level scaled data and is designated to art therapeutic evaluation. Finally, the closest approach to this work in method and content stems from a neuropsychological perspective. The *Assessment of Art Attributes* (AAA; Chatterjee et al., 2010; Penn Center for Neuroaesthetics, 2019) which aims to quantify artworks by connecting art and psychometrics. The AAA consists of 12 single-item scales on formal-perceptual and conceptual-representational attributes as well as two additional scales on aesthetic appreciation. The results suggest medium to high inter-rater agreement after having conducted rater training and using non-parametric correlation measures. A capacity to differentiate between pictures or subgroups of pictures as well as factor analyses are not reported. It has been tested on 24 prominent paintings from what Chatterjee et al. (2010) call "Western canon", and by two individuals with Alzheimer's disease (van Buren et al., 2013). As far as known, it was not further validated on other samples.

1.2.4 Digital approaches

Further approaches use digital technology to objectify image analysis. For example, Mattson (2009, 2010, 2011) combines measures such as the FEATS with public domain image analysis software for a computerized assessment of art-based instruments instead of manual rating. Kim et al. (2007) use a computer-based system for color-related aspects including five basic elements (*number of colors, color list, number of clusters for each color, area for each color, length of edges*) and nine applied elements (*main, secondary and background colors, placement, space, emotional tone, blending, detail, line, multiplicity of colors, complexity*). Besides some new elements, most of them are based on DAPA, FEATS, and DDS.

Table 1

Quantitative Instruments

Instrument	Description	Construct	Subscales		Response format	Validation samples		Application	References
			No.	Description		Images*	Raters*		
<i>Anthroposophic Art Therapy Assessment Paint (AART-ASSESS-P)</i>	assessment tool for anthroposophic art therapy	pictorial expression	5	<i>shape development</i> <i>shape arrangement</i> <i>order & symmetry</i> <i>color application</i> <i>color quality</i>	7-point Likert scale (1 = <i>not distinct</i> , 7 = <i>very distinct</i>) dichotomous (<i>yes vs. no</i>)	<i>N</i> = 136 spontaneously drawn watercolor aquarelles by 68 patients with breast carcinoma	<i>N</i> = 5 2 raters per painting	anthroposophic painting therapy, diagnostic tool to hypothetically associate pictorial elements with anthroposophic anthropology	Mehl et al. (2020)
<i>Assessment of Art Attributes (AAA)</i>	quantitative assessment of art attributes	formal-perceptual and conceptual-representational art attributes + aesthetic appreciation	12 + 2	formal-perceptual: <i>balance</i> <i>color saturation</i> <i>color temperature</i> <i>depth</i> <i>complexity</i> <i>stroke</i> conceptual-representational: <i>abstraction</i> <i>animacy</i> <i>emotion</i> <i>realism</i> <i>objectivity</i> <i>accuracy</i> aesthetic appreciation: <i>preference</i> <i>interest</i>	5-point Likert scale (e.g., 1 = <i>abstract</i> , 5 = <i>representational</i>)	<i>N</i> = 24 paintings from the “Western canon” from different time periods (e.g., by Jackson Pollock, Frida Kahlo, Paul Cezanne) <i>N</i> = 30 paintings by 2 individuals with Alzheimer’s disease (5 self-portraits and 25 watercolor paintings)	<i>N</i> = 90 artistically naïve (<i>n</i> = 60) and experienced (<i>n</i> = 30) students <i>N</i> = 81 artistically naïve (<i>n</i> = 12) and knowledgeable (<i>n</i> = 69) students	any piece of art, neuropsychological studies	Chatterjee et al. (2010); Penn Center for Neuroaesthetics (2019)

Instrument	Description	Construct	Subscales		Response format	Validation samples		Application	References
			No.	Description		Images*	Raters*		
Descriptive Assessment of Psychiatric Art (DAPA)	coding system for analysis of art created by patients with psychiatric diseases	formal elements	5	<i>color</i> <i>color intensity</i> <i>quality of line</i> <i>space covered</i> <i>subjectively judged</i> <i>emotional tone</i>	multiple choice (e.g., colors: <i>red, yellow, purple, green, blue, brown, white, black</i> ; color intensity: <i>high vs. neutral vs. low</i>)	paintings by <i>N</i> = 33 individuals with psychiatric diseases n.a. 86 individuals with psychiatric diseases and 23 controls	<i>N</i> = 6 5 students and the author <i>N</i> = 6 not specified	art in psychiatric contexts, diagnostics	Elbing and Hacking (2001); Hacking and Foreman (2000); Hacking et al. (1996); Stuhler-Bauer and Elbing (2004)
Diagnostic Drawing Series (DDS)	standardized art interview based on 3 pictures drawing task (free picture, tree picture, feeling picture) using specific material	manifestation of defenses psycho-pathological indicators mood	24	<i>color</i> <i>idiosyncratic color</i> <i>blending</i> <i>elements</i> <i>line length</i> <i>integration</i> <i>tree</i> <i>depiction</i> <i>edges</i> <i>image</i> <i>enclosure</i> <i>pressure</i> <i>movement</i> <i>space usage</i> <i>tilt</i> <i>unusual placement</i> <i>groundline</i> <i>people</i> <i>animals</i>	multiple choice (e.g., color: <i>mono vs. 2-3 vs. 4+ vs. blank</i>) dichotomous (<i>yes vs. no</i>).	n.a. <i>N</i> = 4,000 drawings by adults and adolescents included in archive	n.a.	pictures from a specific drawing task, art therapy assessment, contributes to diagnostics, research, (clinical) use	Cohen and Mills (2016); (Mills, 2003)

Instrument	Description	Construct	Subscales		Response format	Validation samples		Application	References
			No.	Description		Images*	Raters*		
DDS (see previous)				<i>objects</i> <i>symbols</i> <i>writing</i> <i>landscape</i>					
Documentation of art therapeutic processes (DoKuPro; <i>Dokumentation kunsttherapeutischer Prozesse</i>)	observational tool for a systematic documentation of the client's behavior during art therapy sessions	art therapy process	7	<i>material</i> <i>method of working</i> <i>attitude towards work</i> <i>expression and representation of the object</i> <i>reflection and viewing</i> <i>client within the group</i> <i>client's relationship towards the object</i>	6-point Likert scale (1 = <i>do not agree at all</i> , 6 = <i>fully agree</i>) free text entry	<i>N</i> = 1031 observations of art therapy processes	n.a.	art therapeutic processes, documentation, research	Elbing (2007); Elbing et al. (2009); Elbing et al. (2010)
Formal Elements Art Therapy Scale (FEATS)	rating system to measure global variables in drawing resulting from	global variables in art	14	<i>prominence of color</i> <i>color fit</i> <i>implied energy</i> <i>space</i> <i>integration</i> <i>logic</i> <i>realism</i> <i>problem-solving</i>	5-point Likert scale	n.a.	n.a.	images from the <i>Person Picking an Apple From a Tree</i> assessment (Betts, 2006), some scales applicable to other assessments or non-directive art	Gantt (2016); Gantt and Anderson (2009)

Instrument	Description	Construct	Subscales		Response format	Validation samples		Application	References
			No.	Description		Images*	Raters*		
FEATS (see previous)	the <i>Person Picking an Apple From a Tree</i> assessment (Betts, 2006)			<i>developmental level</i> <i>details of objects and environment</i> <i>line quality</i> <i>person rotation</i> <i>perseveration</i>				(drawings and paintings), art therapy	
Nürtingen rating scale (NBS; <i>Nürtinger Beurteilungsskala</i>)	assessment of images by patients in the art therapy process	image properties	4	<i>color</i> <i>shape</i> <i>line</i> <i>motion</i>	5-point Likert scale (1 = <i>fully agree</i> , 5 = <i>do not agree at all</i>)	n.a.	n.a.	art therapy	Eber et al. (1998); Elbing and Hacking (2001)
Systematic picture analysis	observational tool describing formal-aesthetic criteria for an art therapeutic evaluation	formal-aesthetic criteria	7	<i>materiality</i> <i>material</i> <i>processing</i> <i>line</i> <i>shape</i> <i>color</i> <i>composition</i> <i>topic</i>	7- and 9-point Likert scale dichotomous multiple choice free text entry	<i>N</i> = 162 pictures by patients with breast carcinoma (<i>n</i> = 33), gastrointestinal carcinoma (<i>n</i> = 29), and rheumatism (<i>n</i> = 28)	<i>N</i> = 4 experts	art therapeutic evaluation	Gruber et al. (2002)

Note. *as far as known from according publications without claiming completeness; n.a. = information not available

Hayn-Leichsenring et al. (2020) use computational network science and empirical methods for assessing global image properties and their subjective preferences through the viewer. The properties are operationalized as *self-similarity* (if an object as a whole is similar to its parts), *complexity*, *heterogeneity of luminance gradients*, *color measures* (hue, saturation, value), and *aspect ratio*. Digital methods are also used for the controversial *Tree Drawing* test: Pinteá et al. (2014) automatically measure the ratio between crown and trunk diameters. Gu et al. (2020) use image scanning and computer image recognition technology to quantitatively collect pictorial data. Finally, Chan et al. (2021) demonstrate that the digital drawing test can be a diagnostic tool for screening of mild cognitive impairment and dementia.

1.2.5 Summary of existing instruments

In summary, attempts to quantify images exist. However, many of them are not designed for art in general, but for therapeutic or clinical use. Other instruments can be used for assessment beyond clinical applications but concentrate on specific drawing tasks and are not suitable for non-directive art. Many do not meet scientific criteria and are not validated on representative samples. Most of them do not provide Likert scaled data and therefore do not allow inference statistics and hypothesis testing.

1.3. Goal of this work

This work aims for a combination of a methodically and theoretically sound test construction based on test theory and art theoretical content. Since the construct pictorial expression has mainly been considered theoretically and qualitatively until now, a transdisciplinary approach between different methodological perspectives is needed.

This work aims to

1. meet scientific standards, i.e., objectivity, validity, and reliability,
2. measure a theoretically defined construct, i.e., pictorial expression in terms of a formal picture analysis,
3. in a methodically sound way based on test theory, that provides interval level data and allows inference statistics

4. provide a universal tool for all types of two-dimensional pictorial works in terms of material (e.g., drawings, paintings, collages) and creation (e.g., non-/directive art, non-/clinical art), and
5. offer a variety of application possibilities in art-related research and practice across disciplines (e.g., psychology, psychiatry, art therapy, art pedagogy, art history).

1.4 Construct and nomological network

1.4.1 Pictorial expression

Defining the nomological network, the instrument aims to assess the construct pictorial expression, which is defined as artistic creation in the form of a picture. While phenomenology describes the attitude towards analyzing art, the subject of analysis refers to a formal picture analysis. Pictorial expression does not directly refer to the creator's expression, which is complex, ambivalent, and cannot be exhaustively captured by just analyzing one image. Instead, the construct refers only to the artwork.

Phenomenological picture analysis

Modern phenomenology goes back to Edmund Husserl and is interested in phenomena (things, objects) and how they present themselves as perceived experiences (Betensky, 1991). Husserl postulates that an artwork possesses an invisible space that belongs to the picture and cannot be grasped by experience (Uzelac, 1998). Roman Ingarden – phenomenologist and founder of immanentism, a hermeneutic approach that aims to understand artworks under their own preconditions with the elimination of all external factors – states that the aesthetic object comprises a potential of possibilities that can be actualized by the perceiver but mostly are not fully captured by them (Schneider, 2017, p. 194 ff.). From these perspectives it can already be seen that art is not an autonomous structure that can be measured without the perceiver's influence. Therefore, this work is rooted in the tradition of *phenomenological picture analysis* (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003, 2004), a qualitative art therapeutic tool. The phenomenological method consists in the attempt to view and describe what is perceived as precisely as possible (Betensky, 1991). The viewer seeks to overcome accidental judgment, preconception, and

association (Streb, 1984) while at the same time being aware that there is no such thing as absolute objectivity and while reflecting on one's own perceptions.

Formal picture analysis

Formal picture analysis (Bauer, 1996) captures formal pictorial attributes that can be found across literature about art (e.g., Arnheim, 2000; Bauer, 1996; Kandinsky, 1955; Meyer, 2011; Vollmar, 2008): *representation, color, shaping, spatiality, motion, composition, and expression*. Bauer (1996, p. 161) states that form is the appearance of a message with the critical proviso that the form cannot be isolated from the historical context. However, following a quantitative approach, this work needs to isolate form from content and historical context – not to ignore it completely, but to disassemble art to enable its operationalization in the first place. To disassemble, measure, and reassemble art, this work decided to start by measuring formal elements, since these are most likely to be analyzed objectively. Coming from *formal picture analysis*, the item development (see Study 1) was theory-led based on the following seven theoretical content areas (see Table 2), which were *a priori* defined and served as a framework for systematically creating an exhaustive item pool to be then empirically tested (see Appendix A).

1.4.2 Distinct concepts

This work does not aim for an evaluative assessment or judgment of art in terms of the creator's talent, achievement, or mastery. The focus lies on the visual presentation (Wiesing, 2005) and leaves out the “colonializing view” of unintentional identification of objects (Marotzki & Stoetzer, 2006). It omits the picture reference, e.g., knowledge, association, or emotion (Huber, 2005). Being limited to a detailed but classical conception of images, it does not take into account the creation process (Uzelac, 1998). The construct is distinct from aesthetic appreciation (Hager et al., 2012; Leder et al., 2012), since it is not asking for the viewer's liking. Of course, *formal picture analysis* is not the only way to examine art. There are many distinct art theoretical methods (e.g., *stylistic analysis, structural analysis, iconographic-iconological approach, reception aesthetics*) some of which will be addressed in the discussion. In summary, it is neither evaluative nor interpretative nor projective but aims for a value-free description solely of formal elements.

Table 2*Formal picture analysis: Theoretical content areas*

No.	Content area	Definition
1	<i>Representation</i> <i>RE</i>	Representation refers to a basic classification. This includes a positioning of the work in the continuum between painting and drawing as well as its level of abstraction (Arnheim, 2000, p. 139 ff.).
2	<i>Color</i> <i>CO</i>	Stuhler-Bauer and Elbing (2003) consider color, its selection, use, distribution, and interaction as the central component of an image. It includes both quality and quantity, as well as luminosity. This, inter alia, refers to Johann Wolfgang von Goethe's color theory (e.g., tertiary colors; Vollmar, 2008, p. 71) and Johannes Itten (e.g., primary color; Meyer, 2011; Vollmar, 2008, p. 58).
3	<i>Shaping</i> <i>SH</i>	Along with color, shaping is a core component, although shaping differs from color, since it can exist independently in contrast to color which always requires shape (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003). It includes shaping of components (e.g., organic) and surface (e.g., appearing two-dimensional). Since shapes mostly emerge from lines (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003), lines are also a component.
4	<i>Spatiality</i> <i>SP</i>	Spatiality refers to an arrangement of pictorial space. Since it is by definition a three-dimensional construct, using this concept on two-dimensional works seems paradox. Thus, it refers to a mode of representation through which a spatial effect is created (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003), the presence or absence of perspective, spatial depth, and the handling of image space (Arnheim, 2000, p. 215 ff.; Meyer, 2011).
5	<i>Motion</i> <i>MO</i>	Motion in a non-kinetic picture seems equally paradoxical. It also refers to an illusory movement, e.g., lines that are perceived as traces of movement or direct the gaze of the viewer. Also an oblique image object can suggest a deviation from a resting position (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003). Motion refers to the quality of movement: a perception of motion, its intensity and directionality (Arnheim, 2000, p. 371 ff.).
6	<i>Composition</i> <i>COM</i>	Composition refers to an overall view on all formal aspects a picture is composed of. It describes the image structure, the relationship of its elements to each other, and literally to the big picture (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003). Central elements are the orientation of the overall composition, symmetry, and relationship between picture elements.
7	<i>Expression</i> <i>EX</i>	Expression describes the character of an image. Stuhler-Bauer and Elbing (2003) introduce a concept of qualities of a perceived impression of an image. They also emphasize that these are difficult to quantify, since they are usually composed of different sensory qualities. Interpretations and associations are not subsumed here. However, this is theorized to be the least objective content area.

1.4.3 Construct map

At the beginning of this research, there were barely any quantitative studies on pictorial expression that could have been referred to, which led to an exploratory approach: the items were hypothesized to represent components of the construct and not to necessarily correlate with each other. Similar to formative models, they were expected to combine results in the overall construct and create a profile of characteristics. A total sum value across the whole scale was not considered meaningful, since it can only be interpreted at item or component level. Concretely, this means that the degree of abstraction can be high or low, but pictorial expression in total cannot. Consequently, an *a priori* construct map was neither useful nor possible to create.

1.5 Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA)

RizbA is a questionnaire for *formal picture analysis* of two-dimensional pictorial works. The final version includes 26 items (see Table 3) in German and uses a six-point Likert scale, which is discretely scaled and verbally anchored in shades of agreement (0 = *strongly disagree*, 5 = *strongly agree*). Raters using the questionnaire receive a brief instruction to rate the image presented. They are asked to focus on the predominant overall expression of a picture and no single details, while affirming that there is no right or wrong, but only their valuation. Neither a rater training nor sample images are provided to avoid manipulation of judgment.

RizbA is not a diagnostic tool and in this respect differs from drawing technique assessments. Of course, correlations between pictorial expression and psychological variables are hypothesized and pilot studies on this issue will be presented below. But art is a complex construct that until now hasn't been researched quantitatively in depth. Currently, it would be tempting and probably erroneous to jump to evaluative conclusions about latent psychological variables exclusively based on pictorial expression. However, based on more research and in combination with other scales, RizbA might in the future provide additional diagnostic information.

Table 3*Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA): Items and translated items*

No.	Item	Translated item
1	Das Bild enthält zeichnerische Elemente	The picture includes graphic elements
2	Das Bild enthält malerische Elemente	The picture includes pictorial elements
3	Die Darstellungsweise ist gegenständlich	The manner of representation is concrete
4	Die Darstellungsweise ist abstrakt	The manner of representation is abstract
5	Der Farbauftrag ist pastos	The color application is pastose
6	Die vorherrschende Farbgebung ist leuchtend	The predominant coloring is vibrant
7	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend reine Farben	In the picture primary colors are prevalent
8	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend Mischfarben (Sekundärfarben)	In the picture mixed colors (secondary colors) are prevalent
9	Im Bild sind Komplementärkontraste vorhanden	In the picture there are complementary contrasts
10	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend organisch	In the picture organic shapes are prevalent
11	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend geometrisch	In the picture geometric shapes are prevalent
12	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend gebogen	The layout of the line is predominantly curved
13	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend eckig	The layout of the line is predominantly angled
14	Das Bild enthält unbearbeitete Flächen	The picture includes unworked areas
15	Das Bild wirkt tief	The picture appears to be deep
16	Das Bild ist perspektivisch	The picture is perspectival
17	Das Bild ist frei von Perspektive (aperspektivisch)	The picture is without perspective (aperspectival)
18	Das Bild ist unruhig	The picture is restless
19	Das Bild ist wild	The picture is wild
20	Die Gesamtkomposition ist senkrecht angelegt	The global composition is laid out vertically
21	Die Gesamtkomposition ist waagrecht angelegt	The global composition is laid out horizontally
22	Die Gesamtkomposition ist diagonal angelegt	The global composition is laid out diagonally
23	Die Gesamtkomposition ist flächendeckend ohne Hauptmotiv (All-Over-Structure)	The global composition is laid out area-wide without a main subject (All-Over-Structure)
24	Das Bild wirkt diffus	The picture appears to be diffuse
25	Das Bild wirkt präzise, exakt	The picture appears to be precise, accurate
26	Das Bild wirkt harmonisch	The picture appears to be harmonic

2 Empirical studies: Methods and results

2.1 Validation studies

For constructing and validating the scale, several empirical studies have been conducted: the core of this work is four validation studies (see Table 4), which validated RizbA on a total of 899 artworks by contemporary artists and nonprofessionals, being rated by a total of 1,577 art experts.

Table 4

Validation studies: Image and rater samples

		Study 1 (Schoch et al., 2017)	Study 2 (Schoch & Ostermann, 2022)	Study 3 (Schoch & Ostermann, 2020)	Study 4 (Schoch & Ostermann, 2021, July 13)
Images	Type	Pictorial works by nonprofessionals	Contemporary artworks by professional artists	Pictorial works by nonprofessionals and contemporary artworks by professional artists	
		$N = 12$	$N = 294$	$N = 318$	$N = 275$
	Data collection	Attendance study	Attendance study	Digital database <i>prometheus</i> (prometheus, 2021; Simon & Verstegen, 2004)	Online call and digital data base WikiArt (2021) using the <i>WikiArt</i> Application Programming Interface (API; Davis, 2018; WikiArt, 2020)
Raters	Type	Art therapists	Various art experts (e.g., art therapists, art pedagogues, artists, art historians, designers, restorers)		
	Sample size	$N_{T1} = 12$ $N_{T2} = 8$	$N_{T1} = 880$ $N_{T2} = 475$	$N_{T1} = 506$ $N_{T2} = 238$	$N = 179$
	Data collection	Online studies			

Note. N = sample size, T1 = test, T2 = retest

2.1.1 Study 1: Test construction

Schoch, K., Gruber, H., & Ostermann, T. (2017). Measuring art: Methodical development of a quantitative rating instrument measuring pictorial expression (RizbA). *The Arts in Psychotherapy, 55*, 73-79.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aip.2017.04.014>

In an initial study, RizbA was constructed based on a theoretical framework of content areas (see 1.4.1 and Table 2) and empirically tested on a small heterogeneous sample of pictorial works by nonprofessionals. A pool of 113 items (see Appendix A) was gathered based on art literature, compendia (e.g., Arnheim, 2000; Kandinsky, 1955; Meyer, 2011; Vollmar, 2008), and existing instruments (NBS, DAPA, DoKuPro). Two online studies were conducted, in which art therapists ($N_{T1} = 12$, $N_{T2} = 8$) rated a sample of nine pictures. Based on statistical quality criteria like capacity of differentiation between pictorial works, inter-rater reliability, and test-retest reliability, items not meeting the criteria were excluded. As an exploratory approach, Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was used. The study resulted in a 26-items version. Its capacity of differentiation between pictorial works ranges between .90 (T1) and .77 (T2), its inter-rater reliability between .53 (T1) and .92 (T2). Test-retest reliability is .92. PCAs suggest a four-factor solution but is exploratory and based on a small sample.

2.1.2 Study 2: Validation on nonprofessional pictorial works

Schoch, K., & Ostermann, T. (2022). Psychometrics of art: Validation of RizbA, a quantitative rating instrument for pictorial expression. *Creativity Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2021.1987734> *SocArXiv*.
<https://doi:10.31235/osf.io/uc9e2>

The second study validated the 26-item version on 294 images created by 147 non-artists or nonprofessional artists. In a randomized test-retest study the image material was rated by 880 (T1) and 475 (T2) experts. Statistical quality criteria, such as item difficulty, capacity of differentiation, inter-rater reliability, and test-retest reliability were calculated. PCA and indices of factor similarity were computed. The scale's capacity of differentiation yields a partial eta-squared of .28 (T1) and .33 (T2). Test-

retest reliability is .93. PCA reveals an eight-factor solution. Tucker's coefficients of congruence range between |0.82| and |1.00|. Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (*ICC*) are .81 (T1) and .84 (T2). In summary, the results indicate generalizability to nonprofessional works.

2.1.3 Study 3: Validation on contemporary artworks

Schoch, K., & Ostermann, T. (2020). Giving the art greater weight in art psychology: RizbA, a quantitative questionnaire for formal picture analysis. *Creativity. Theories – Research – Application* 7(2), 373-410. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ctra-2020-0019>

The third study was implemented analogously to the second but used a sample of 318 works by professional artists dated to the 21st century. In a randomized test-retest design, the pictures were rated by 506 (T1) and 238 (T2) art experts. Statistical quality criteria, such as item difficulty, capacity of differentiation, inter-rater reliability, test-retest reliability, PCA, and indices of factor similarity were computed. The overall test's capacity of differentiation yields a partial eta-squared of .31 (T1) and .40 (T2). Test-retest reliability is .86. PCA reveals an eight-factor solution, which is largely consistent across both measurement points. Tucker's coefficient of congruence ranges between |.71| and |1.00|. *ICC* are .86 (T1) and .73 (T2). The results indicate generalizability also to contemporary professional art.

2.1.4 Summary of studies 1–3

All 26 items yield approximately medium-sized difficulty indices and thus provide an excellent mechanism for differentiating between images and their particular characteristics. Other criteria that indicate capacity of differentiation between pictures are moderate to large item variances. Comparing results to common effect sizes (Coster, 2012), large effects can be assumed. However, capacity of differentiation decreases for larger image samples. This is probably because the larger a sample is, the more likely it contains similar images, e.g., representational pencil drawings. In alignment with effect size conventions (Cohen, 1992), the test-retest reliabilities suggest large effects and imply stability across time. In accordance with conventions (Koo & Li, 2016) the scale yields moderate to excellent inter-rater reliabilities. The results of the overall test (see Table 5) suggest that RizbA is a reliable measure across images, raters, and time that is applicable to pictorial works

by professionals and nonprofessionals. The next, obligatory step is an exploration of a potential factor structure.

Table 5

Statistical Quality Criteria: Overall Test

Criteria	Index	Time of measurement	Study 1	Study 2	Study 3
Capacity of differentiation	η_p^2	T1	.90	.28	.31
		T2	.77	.33	.40
Test-retest reliability	r		.92	.93	.86
Number of factors	PCA		4	8	8
Inter-rater reliability	ICC	T1	.53	.81	.86
		T2	.92	.84	.73

Note. T1 = test, T2 = retest, η_p^2 = partial eta-squared effect size estimator, r = correlation, PCA = Principal Component Analysis, ICC = intraclass correlation coefficient

2.1.5 Study 4: Factor structure

Schoch, K., & Ostermann, T. (2021, July 13). Empirics vs. art theory: Exploring a factor structure of pictorial expression based on contemporary artworks. [Manuscript submitted for publication]. *SocArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/xyrf5>

The fourth study explored the factor structure of pictorial expression using a sample of 275 contemporary pictorial works by artists and nonprofessionals that were rated by 179 experts in a randomized study. Three path models were specified, and Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFA) were carried out. Models A and B were based on the empirical results of the second and third study, while model C referred to the theoretical framework of content areas (see 1.4.1) used in the first study (see 2.1.1). Model C was additionally tested on a combined dataset of the second study (see 2.1.2), third study (see 2.1.3), and the data of this study. While models A and B do not converge, model C is associated with fit indices as follows: $\chi^2 = 1299.752$, $df = 278$, $p = .000$, RMSEA = .122, 90% CI [.116, .129], CFI = .712, TLI = .679, SRMR

= .135 and for the combined dataset: $\chi^2 = 6860.824$, $df = 278$, $p = .000$, RMSEA = .086, 90% CI [.084, .088], CFI = .740, TLI = .696, SRMR = .084. Only model C partly suggests an acceptable fit for the combined data and suggests there might not be a globally stable factor structure across artworks. Also, the results speak to a methodological gap between empirics and theory.

2.2 Further studies

Another three studies were conducted to evolve particular methodical aspects, i.e., a machine learning approach, a brief manual making the scale applicable to persons without art expertise, and the theoretical groundwork for an analogous instrument for three-dimensional art.

2.2.1 ARTificial intelligence

Gengenbach, T., & Schoch, K. (2022). ARTificial intelligence raters: Neural networks for rating pictorial expression. *Journal of Science and Technology of the Arts* 14(1), 49–71. <https://doi.org/10.34632/jsta.2022.10196>

Previous studies on classification of fine art (e.g., Cetinic et al., 2018; Tan et al., 2016) show that features of paintings can be captured and categorized by machine learning approaches. This progress can also benefit art psychology by facilitating data collection on artworks without the need to acquire experts as raters. In this study a machine learning approach is used to predict RizbA ratings. Based on a pre-trained model the algorithm was fine-tuned via transfer learning (Razavian et al., 2014; Sarkar, 2018; Sarkar et al., 2018) on 886 pictorial works from the second (see 2.1.2), third (see 2.1.3), and fourth study (see 2.1.4). As a quality criterion, ARTificial intelligence raters (ART) were compared with generic raters created from the real human expert raters using error rate and mean squared error. ART ratings have been found in the same error range as randomly chosen human ratings and can be seen equivalent to real human expert raters for almost all items. Further training with more data will close the gap to the human raters on all items.

2.2.2 RizbA for non-art disciplines

Jerusalem, J. L. L. (2020). Rizba für alle: Überprüfung der Einsatzmöglichkeiten eines Ratinginstruments für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (RizbA) und des neu dazu erstellten Manuals [RizbA for everyone: Review of the possible uses of a rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA) and the newly created manual]. Thesis (B.Sc.). Witten/Herdecke University. *Open Science Framework*. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/FVJZM>

Though RizbA seems to be a practical tool, it was hitherto only usable to art experts familiar with art terminology. To make the scale applicable to other disciplines, a brief manual was developed, that consists of explanatory notes to the items based on art literature (see 1.4.1). To examine the quality of this extended version in a 2x2 design, two groups (art experts vs. non-experts) were compared between two conditions (with vs. without manual). The data of art experts with the manual stemmed from the second study (see 2.1.2). The other three conditions were collected within a randomized quasi-experimental online study with a total of 383 expert and non-expert raters. As statistical quality criteria, descriptive statistics, item difficulty, capacity of differentiation, and inter-rater reliability were calculated and compared between conditions. The results suggest a beneficial effect of the manual, in particular for non-experts. For most indices expert ratings are more reliable, but non-experts are still sufficiently reliable when using the manual. In summary, RizbA can be reliably used by non-art experts, e.g., psychologists, psychiatrists, educators.

2.2.3 A third dimension (RidbA)

Müller, S. (2020). Dreidimensionaler Blick auf Kunst: Theoretische Grundlage einer Testentwicklung zur Erfassung dreidimensionaler Arbeiten [A three-dimensional view on art: Theoretical groundwork for developing a test to capture three-dimensional works]. Thesis (B.A.). HKS – University of Applied Sciences and Arts Ottersberg.

A third pre-empirical work laid the theoretical groundwork for developing an analogous scale for three-dimensional pictorial works. Within a systematic search of the literature, a pool of 227 items was gathered and systematized in nine theory-based

content areas: *representation, overall composition, shaping, shape composition, surface structuring, coloring, material, motion, and mass-space relation*. This item pool is to be empirically tested and might result in RidbA (Ratinginstrument für dreidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten), a rating instrument for three-dimensional pictorial works.

2.3 Application studies

Four collaborative application studies used the scale to investigate correlations between pictorial expression and psychological or clinical variables (e.g., chronic pain, recurrent depression, developmental stages of child drawings, and delirium).

2.3.1 Chronic pain

Janßen, B. (2018). Erprobung des Ratinginstruments für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (RizbA): Ansatz zu einer möglichen Untersuchung des bildnerischen Ausdrucks von Schmerz in gemalten Bildern von Menschen mit chronischer Schmerzsymptomatik [Testing the rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA): Pilot study for investigating pictorial expression in pictures painted by people with chronic pain symptoms]. Thesis (B.A.). HKS – University of Applied Sciences and Arts Ottersberg. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3407808>

A pilot study explored whether individuals diagnosed with chronic pain symptoms express their experience in their pictorial works. Pictures by individuals experiencing chronic pain ($N = 4$) were compared with a healthy control group ($N = 4$). All images were rated by art experts ($N = 33$) in a blind study. Results suggest a significant difference in 16 of 26 items but are not representative due to the small image sample.

2.3.2 Recurrent depression

Epstein, C. (2019). Bildlicher Ausdruck von Depression: Erprobung des Ratinginstruments RizbA an Bildstichproben aus dem klinischen Kunsttherapiesetting [Pictorial expression of depression: Testing the rating instrument RizbA on image samples from a clinical art therapy setting]. Thesis (B.Sc.). Witten/Herdecke University. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3365921>

Another pilot study explored whether individuals diagnosed with a recurrent depression express this diagnosis in their pictorial works. Images by individuals experiencing recurring episodes of depression ($N = 17$) were compared with a matched healthy control group ($N = 17$). The results suggest a significant difference in four items: pictures from the experimental group were less brilliant in terms of brightness, showed less contrast, and were more likely to have an all-over-structure and a depth of perspective. The results suggest images by persons with and without depression might differ in pictorial expression.

2.3.3 Developmental stages of child drawings

Ladegast, S. (2020). Untersuchung von Kinderzeichnungen: Erprobung des Ratinginstrument RizbA zur Untersuchung von Entwicklungsstufen der Kinderzeichnung [Examination of children's drawings: Testing of the rating instrument RizbA for the analysis of developmental stages of child drawings]. (B.A.). HKS – University of Applied Sciences and Arts Ottersberg, *Open Science Framework*. <https://osf.io/gn3mt>

Another study examined whether RizbA makes it possible to measure the developmental stages of child drawings (i.e., scribbling stage, work maturity, and schematic stages I+II) based on Hans-Günther Richter (1997). Drawings ($N = 90$) by children within the age groups corresponding to the phases (1–4, 5–7, and 8–12 years) were collected and rated by art experts in a blind study. The analysis focused on six items, which all showed significant differences between stages and could clearly differentiate between them.

2.3.4 Geriatric delirium

Masuch, J., Antwerpen, L., Schoch, K., Steiger, S. J., Brons-Daymond, S., Gosch, M., & Singler, K. (2021). Zeigt sich ein Delir auf der Bildebene? Eine systematische Bildanalyse von geriatrischen Delir-Risiko-Patient*innen mittels RizbA [Does a delirium show on a pictorial level? A systematic image analysis of geriatric patients at risk of delirium using RizbA; Manuscript submitted for publication].

Another study examined whether indications specific to geriatric delirium can be pictorially expressed. In a randomized test-retest design images ($N = 635$) by 71

individuals in acute geriatrics were rated by art therapists ($N = 660$). Images were compared within subjects (*delirium vs. no delirium*). The results indicate differences, i.e., images by creators in delirium being more abstract, restless, wild, and diffuse. In the future, this might be used as diagnostic warning signals for an emerging delirium within acute geriatric individuals.

3 Discussion

The instrument was successfully validated and is reliably applicable to contemporary two-dimensional pictorial works by professional artists and nonprofessionals. As a novelty, RizbA enables a quantitative capture of artworks that meets scientific criteria. Although the factor structure remains open, one thing is certain: it is possible to measure pictorial expression in terms of a *formal picture analysis* objectively, validly, and reliably. By providing a measure for pictorial expression, the scale opens new perspectives in a transdisciplinary field of art and psychology for both research and practice.

3.1 Limitations

Detailed limitations of each study are to be found in the relevant publications. The following is a brief summary of the overarching limitations of the entire research conducted.

3.1.1 Diversity of samples

Regarding the image samples, the works by nonprofessionals in the first and second study were collected in attendance studies in Germany and are not globally representative. In the fourth study, data was collected via a digital call in German and English. This resulted in an international sample. Still, the chosen languages were an exclusion criterion for participants speaking other languages. The contemporary art was collected via digital databases, *prometheus* (Simon & Verstegen, 2004) and *WikiArt* (2021). *prometheus* includes works by African, American, and Asian artists. But being a shared archive of German institutions, it is biased in favor of European art. *WikiArt* (2021) is a shared knowledge database without GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) institutions serving as gatekeepers. Theoretically speaking, this diversifies the database. Practically speaking, both databases lack

metadata of the artists' geographical region of origin, self-identified gender and other diversity indicators (Pacher-Nishikawa et al., 2021) to make sure the samples are heterogeneous.

As for the raters, sample data on self-identified gender was collected. Most raters are female, some are male, and some are non-binary, which might reflect the gender proportion in arts and humanities. All experts were required to speak German, which resulted in individuals mostly stemming from Germany, Austria, or Switzerland. In consequence, this sample is also afflicted with a Eurocentric bias.

3.1.2 Exploratory approach

In view of the lack of quantitative research on pictorial expression, an exploratory approach of test construction was chosen. Content areas were theoretically defined to systematically create an item pool. However, it was not predictable whether they would be reflected in the empirical data. Consequently, it was not possible to create *a priori* a construct map and the scarcity of data made it difficult to formulate hypotheses on effect sizes, factor structure etc.

3.1.3 Factors

In the first study the items 18, 19, 24, 25, and 26 are subsumed under the content areas *expression* and *movement*. In the second and third study they are assigned the factor label *picture effect* based on an iterative discussion process of expert opinions. Based on theoretical reasoning, *picture effect* is not particularly a part of pictorial expression, if we strictly define it in terms of a *formal picture analysis*. They rather capture the atmosphere in an image. In the further development of the scale, this factor could be excluded or used as an additional optional scale.

Regarding the factor structure, the fourth study indicated that none of the hypothesized models – whether empirical or theory-based – provides a thoroughly good or acceptable fit. As an exploratory approach an *a posteriori* card sorting test was conducted with art experts to generate further theory-based models. When conducting a CFA they converged – in comparison to the empirically based models A and B – but still did not provide a good model fit. It can be assumed that theory-based models are more likely to fit than the empirically based models based on PCA. There are several possible reasons: first, the sample might not be large enough to map a factor structure since CFA is a large sample procedure. According to Shi et al.

(2019) a sample of 200 observations only provides a reasonable estimate for CFI and TLI when the number of observed variables is less than 30. Second, the factor structure in PCA and CFA computations might differ because of the difference in procedures (Suhr, 2005, 2006). Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) results can differ depending on the chosen statistical procedure and other criteria (Auerswald & Moshagen, 2019), e.g., in some instances, PCA loadings are closer approximations of the factor loadings (De Winter & Dodou, 2016). Third, one should consider the possibility that there might be no stable global solution across all art. Fourth, there is likely to be a methodical gap between empirics and theory when it comes to *formal picture analysis*. Pictorial expression might be a more complex construct than anticipated. Fifth, as Husserl postulates, there might be a latent part of pictorial expression that cannot be captured, an invisible space that belongs to the picture and cannot be grasped by experience (Uzelac, 1998). This might be a missing piece in the search for a factor structure. Sixth, it is possible that there is no underlying factor structure analogous to psychological constructs like personality or intelligence.

3.2 Implications

3.2.1 Artworks and psychological correlates

Referring to Freeman's model (Freeman, 1995, 2008), the theory of pictures is based on an intentional network of four factors: picture, artist, world, and viewer. Images can refer to the real world and how it is perceived by the artist, but also to imaginative, inner worlds. One of these interrelationships – the one between artist and picture – focuses on the creator's intention and other features as well as how they affect the artistic product (Vivaldi et al., 2020). Art psychology mostly focuses on picture-viewer relations. RizbA allows for a more detailed scientific examination of correlates between psychological constructs for artworks and both the viewer's and the creator's psyche. For example, correlations have been found between art preferences and personality traits. Individuals who enjoy novelty, ambiguity, and dissonance and who are open-minded and sensation-seeking, prefer abstract over representational art. Abstract, random, and field-independent thinkers prefer abstraction as well (Gridley, 2006, 2013). RizbA goes beyond categories like abstract vs. representational and allows a deeper examination. It can be used for research to shed light on the formal criteria that make individuals prefer specific art.

3.2.2 Art-making

Although creativity, aesthetics, and art-making correlate (Zaidel et al., 2013), research usually focuses on these topics separately (Tinio, 2013) and ignores artistic creation itself. One way to combine them is the *Mirror Model of Art* that connects art-making and art-viewing and proposes that aesthetic experiences mirror the art-making process (Tinio, 2013). Other research investigates not only the affective, evaluative, and neurophysiological correlates of perceiving art, but also the interaction with art (Pelowski et al., 2017). RizbA could contribute to these more holistic views by investigating interrelationships between viewing, interacting, and making art. Further research could ask participants not only to look at art but also to create art. If abstract thinkers prefer viewing abstract art (Gridley, 2013), they might also be more likely to create abstract art.

3.2.3 Creativity

The concept of art has changed considerably since the early 20th century, yet can hardly be imagined without the concept of creativity. Leaving aside other heterogeneous and complex perspectives on creativity (e.g., Glăveanu, 2013; Rhodes, 1961; Said-Metwaly et al., 2017), it is hereby referred to a contemporary conception: a democratic view, in which anyone is considered able to create from anything (Kampylis & Valtanen, 2010). Considering creativity a relevant factor for artistic creation, concepts like creative expression and creative judgment (Amendt-Lyon, 2001) are likely to in artworks. Although assessment of creativity is a controversial and unsettled issue (Said-Metwaly et al., 2017), there are methods to assess artistic products (Said-Metwaly et al., 2017), e.g., the *Consensual Assessment Technique* (Amabile, 1982) or the *Creative Solution Diagnosis Scale* (Cropley & Kaufman, 2012). However, their main construct of interest is creativity of a product or a person, not the product itself. Combining them with RizbA could provide more information on how a product is perceived to be creative.

3.2.4 Art therapy

Firstly, RizbA is usable for fundamental research. One elementary subject of the art therapeutic triangle (artwork – client – therapist) is client–art relations (Bat Or & Zilcha-Mano, 2018), concomitant with the fundamental assumption that an artwork

is related to its creator and a multitude of their psychological constructs, e.g., emotions, cognition, behavior, personality, and mental health (Freeman, 1995, 2008; Penzes et al., 2018; Vivaldi et al., 2020). Much theoretical and qualitative work has been done on this issue, but experimental studies are still needed (Vivaldi et al., 2020). As the application studies (see 2.3) demonstrate, RizbA can be used to investigate this hypothesis quantitatively in randomized controlled studies. Finding empirical support for a linkage between cognitive, emotional, and social processes to artworks could acknowledge art therapy as a powerful method of working with inner representations. Secondly, the scale can supplement applied research. The majority of mechanistic and efficacy studies consist of pre-/posttest designs that investigate changes in cognitive, emotional, social, clinical, or other psychological outcomes (e.g., Abbing et al., 2018; Kim, 2013; Maujean et al., 2014; Schouten et al., 2015; Slayton et al., 2010). By using RizbA, these studies could additionally incorporate the artistic medium as an important aspect – not only descriptively but also through the use of inference statistics. Thirdly, RizbA can be used as efficient and useful documentation tool in the art therapy process. Changes in pictorial expression can be documented in parallel to mental health variables. Working in the same way as psychometric instruments, it can be connected to clinical institutional reporting systems for other experts, e.g., psychologists, psychiatrists, or therapists. In this way, health improvement or effectiveness of therapy can be evaluated in detail – in individual cases and mechanist research. Furthermore, the tool can support art therapists’ routine of self-reflecting on one’s own perceptions in inter- and supervision.

3.3 Future research

3.3.1 Divergent and convergent validity

Further validation should examine convergent and divergent validity by using related but distinct scales such as AAA, DDS or FEATS. A methodical challenge might be to adequately compare RizbA with instruments using other than Likert scales.

3.3.2 Software application

A further development of the machine learning approach will be programming an app that allows researchers and practitioners to automatically and efficiently document and automatically rate their image material. In accordance with data protection and agreement of the users, the image and rating data could be fed into the calibration sample as a data donation under the terms of Open Science – an approach that was for example chosen for HEXACO Personality Inventory – Revised (HEXACO-PI-R; Lee & Ashton, 2009). Moreover, the app could involve further documentation features (e.g., photo and video archive, other scales, documentation forms) similar to the *MARA app* (Movement Assessment and Reporting App, Dunphy & Hens, 2018) for dance and movement therapy.

3.3.3 Factor structure

Future studies should further investigate the factor structure. If there is one that is stable across all art, a much larger calibration sample might solve the issue. Otherwise, it might be proof for a potential gap between art theory and empirics, that could only be closed by postdisciplinary approaches.

3.3.4 Analyzing art

Although this work is based on art theory, this is an empirical study. As such it did not consider all theories in width and depth. Instead, it disassembled art and chose one measurable construct to later reassemble more pieces and get an overall picture of art. Therefore, various methods of analyzing art need to be considered as well. While it is important to acknowledge that this is only a glimpse of the entire field, some other approaches are briefly addressed hereafter.

Stylistic analysis

The *stylistic analysis* does not interpret the artwork based on its particular appearance but focuses on characteristics of a certain cluster of artworks, e.g., a historical epoch. Its main interest lies in classification, which is taken strictly as a non-artistic criterion. The artwork is not seen as an autonomous “world” for itself, but rather as just a medium in which something is expressed (Bauer, 1996; p. 167 ff.). *Stylistic analysis* will be relevant when validating RizbA on art historical images.

Structural analysis

Sedlmeyer’s art historical paradigm, *structural analysis* (Bauer, 1996; p. 194 ff.), became a counter-model to *stylistic analysis*. It is concerned with a linkage between form and content and aims to overcome their dichotomy. However, Bauer (1996) criticizes that it can create an illusory wholeness of artworks but isolates them from their historical context, a relevant aspect if aiming for a holistic view. This is a parallel to RizbA, which excludes not only stylistic criteria, but also content. It shows how important it is not just to disassemble art to make it measurable, but to aim further for a postdisciplinary holistic analysis.

Iconographic-iconological approach

The *iconographic-iconological method* (Eberlein, 2008) is a tool that Panofsky (1978, 2006) abstracted to a theoretical model and that is comprised of three stages: first, the *pre-iconographic description* determines the primary or natural subject and identifies the objects presented in an image and requires a rudimentary knowledge of the history of style as a corrective principle for understanding the image elements as artistic motifs. Second, the *iconographic analysis* uses historical sources and the history of types to unveil underlying themes and ideas. Third, the *iconological interpretation* examines the actual meaning and content, instrumentalizing the time difference between artwork and interpreter. The *iconographic-iconological method* decrypts images based on historical contextualization, implying that an artwork can never be detached from its historical context. RizbA resembles the first stage of *pre-iconographic description* and excludes *iconographic analysis* and *iconological interpretation*. This level of analysis alone cannot be sufficient if we aim for a comprehensive understanding on art.

Reception aesthetics

Reception aesthetics (Kemp, 1988) suggests that every artwork provides a receptive function. The way it encounters the viewer depends on the way the viewer approaches art, thus responding to and acknowledging the viewer's effort. This approach is oriented towards the artwork and goes in search of an implicit viewer, i.e., a viewer function in the artwork. Each image is addressed to someone, framing its recipient, and discloses two sorts of information: the image speaks about its place and impact in society and about itself. Consequently, *reception aesthetics* has (at least) three tasks: first, it must recognize the means by which the artwork gets in touch with us. Second, it must read those means with regard to their social-historical context. Third, it must consider their actual aesthetic statement. In summary, recipient and artwork are not clinically pure and isolated entities. Although RizbA does not explicitly address internal psychological processes, the items summarized as *picture effect* refer to those. If these items are to be maintained, more theoretical considerations need to be made regarding the underlying construct.

Postdisciplinarity

Bauer (1996) states, the pure form or color of an artwork is not the artwork or its message itself. Separating the constituent aspects of an image – form, content, subject – or isolating one aspect he considered to be absurd. A pure formal analysis is not possible since it is impossible not to address the message of an artwork. Addressing this reasoning that isolating an artwork from its content and subject makes it essential to create much more complex measurement models to do justice to art. However, on an epistemological level, quantitative research uses model simplifications to test specified hypotheses, while humanities offer larger-scaled theoretical models to explain complex systems. To make art quantitatively measurable, we must disassemble it. To do justice to art with all its complexity we have to reassemble it. This is something of a methodical dilemma between disciplines that calls for mixed methods and postdisciplinary approaches.

3.3.5 Diversity and colonial continuities

Due to colonial continuities European and Northern American art science still lacks diverse and universal perspectives. Cultural forms, such as thinking, art, science, and anthropology, once were the product and an alibi of an imperial and colonial power.

Due to this, they became one and the same with thinking, art, science, and anthropology in general. Largely they are still understood as culture itself. In consequence, the *white* gaze claims universality for something that is not universal (Grant & Price, 2020).

Concretely this means that not only are the samples biased towards a *white* Eurocentrist and Northern American perspective; but so is the art theory behind it. In its way of thinking, RizbA refers to prominent European theorists, such as Husserl or Fechner. This leads to one of the major limitations of this work: a *white* – historically mostly cis, male and heterosexual – gaze on art, which consequently is limited and not representative for the whole subject. Taken strictly, without further validation and inclusion of postcolonial perspectives, RizbA is only applicable to European and Northern American art. If we want to find globally representative perspectives on art, we need to rethink the "historical domination of Western-centric and heteropatriarchal approaches to knowledge" (Pownall et al., 2020, October 13)

By now the questionnaire has been validated on a total of 899 contemporary images by professional artists and nonprofessionals. In further applications studies it has been used on a total of 767 images originating from specific samples. Future studies should expand the calibration sample. This refers to both more globally representative international material and specific groups, e.g., from historical epochs, self-taught artists, children and adolescents, or individuals who do not like to work artistically at all. Those studies must also investigate validity by taking into account geographical region, gender and other relevant diversity variables of both of images and raters with a critical view to Eurocentrism (Mosquera, 1992).

3.4 Conclusion

The instrument was successfully validated and is reliably applicable to contemporary two-dimensional pictorial works by professional artists and nonprofessionals. As a novelty, RizbA enables a quantitative capture of artworks that meets scientific criteria. Although the factor structure remains open, one thing is certain: it is possible to measure pictorial expression in terms of a *formal picture analysis* objectively, validly, and reliably. RizbA provides a high capacity of differentiation between pictorial works, high test-retest reliability, and modest to excellent inter-rater reliability. Three further methodical studies develop a machine learning approach,

create a test version that is usable to experts from all disciplines, and gather an item pool for three-dimensional works. Four further application studies test the scale on clinical image samples by persons with chronic pain, depression, delirium and child drawings. By providing a measure for pictorial expression, the scale opens new perspectives in a transdisciplinary field of art and psychology for both research and practice. However, this is an empirical work with results speaking to a methodological gap between empirics and theory. This dilemma might be only solved by more postdisciplinary approaches in the future.

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Giving the Art Greater Weight in Art Psychology: RizbA, a Quantitative Questionnaire for Formal Picture Analysis

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ABSTRACT

In empirical art psychology and creativity research most studies focus on the psychological correlates of art. Only few go beyond treating artworks as categorical data (e.g. abstract vs. representational) and consider artworks in detail. In part this is due to the lack of reliable quantitative measurements. The rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (*RizbA*) makes a difference to current research designs. The current study validates the questionnaire on a representative sample of contemporary visual art, consisting of 318 images depicting works by artists from different cultural areas dated to the 21st century. In a randomized test-retest design, the pictorial material was rated by 506 (T1) and 238 (T2) art experts using *RizbA*. Statistical quality criteria, such as item difficulty, capacity of differentiation, test-retest reliability, and intraclass correlation were calculated. Principal component analysis (PCA) and indices of factor similarity were computed. The overall test's capacity for differentiation yields partial eta-squared of .31 (T1) and .40 (T2). Test-retest reliability is .86. PCA reveals an eight-factor solution, which is largely consistent across both measurement points. Tucker's coefficient of congruence ranges between |.71| and |1.00|. Intraclass correlation coefficients are .86 (T1) and .73 (T2). This study indicates generalizability of the questionnaire to contemporary artworks. Although a conclusion on the factors' structure cannot be drawn yet, results are very promising. As the first reliable quantitative tool for formal picture analysis, *RizbA* allows more detailed examination of visual art and its psychological correlates. This broadens research methodology by giving art greater weight in art psychology and creativity research.

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INTRODUCTION

Although psychological research on art has some tradition, artworks themselves, including their formal content, have received surprisingly little attention in quantitative research. Although Hayn-Leichsenring, Kenett, Schulz, and Chatterjee (2020) state that it is not useful to treat abstract paintings as a single category, art is usually operationalized in terms of a categorical independent variable. In fact, most studies in art psychology, creativity research, and empirical aesthetics focus on art in general and its psychological correlates, while only few consider artworks in detail or at all. For example, in experiments, visual art is often operationalized in terms of broad, sometimes even dichotomous categories, such as art vs. non-art (e.g., Hager, Hagemann, Danner, & Schankin, 2012), genre (Commare, Rosenberg, & Leder, 2018), epoch of art (e.g., Leder, Gerger, Dressler, & Schabmann, 2012), representational vs. abstract (e.g., Gridley, 2013), degree of abstraction (e.g., Specht, 2007), symmetry vs. asymmetry (e.g., Leder et al., 2018) or beauty vs. ugliness (e.g., Ishizu & Zeki, 2011). Only a few studies go into further detail; for example, by identifying different forms of complexity in artworks (Nadal, Munar, Marty, & Cela-Conde, 2010) or by examining the relationship between perception of image complexity and content-related processes in paintings (Commare et al., 2018). Beyond that, hardly any study uses contemporary artworks as pictorial stimuli. Still, these approaches only partially consider art with all its various layers and the sense-making processes that might be related to it: embodied, felt, emotional, intellectual, and intersubjective (Sullivan & McCarthy, 2009). Treating artworks categorically yields only a limited range of information (Maclagan, 1999) of the content contained in pictures.

As discussed by Schoch, Gruber, and Ostermann (2017) and Schoch and Ostermann (under review) there is a severe lack of instruments for a detailed analysis of artworks, that are also quantitative, standardized, and reliable, allow inference statistics, and are validated on and meant to be applicable to all sorts of two-dimensional pictorial works. Only one tool stemming from a neuropsychological perspective shares a similar approach with this work: *The Assessment of Art Attributes* (Chatterjee, Widick, Sternschein, Smith, & Bromberger, 2010; Penn Center for Neuroaesthetics, 2019). By connecting art and science, it aims to quantify artworks including to both formal-perceptual and content-representational attributes. The scale consists of 14 items assessing broad categories. The results suggest medium to high agreement between raters, while using non-parametric measures of correlation and having previously conducted a rater training with training slides regarding the attributes. Unfortunately, other statistical quality criteria, such as the test's capacity to differentiate between pictures or subgroups of pictures or factors analysis, are not reported. Moreover, it has been tested on a small sample of prominent

paintings from the western canon, but as far as we can tell, not on other pictorial material, and it was not further validated.

Consequently, more detailed validated approaches are needed to measure artworks in nuanced profiles to fill this gap. If genuine aspects of artworks are left out of research methodology, this is due in part to a lack of reliable quantitative measures available for this purpose. This is where the rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (*RizbA*) contributes to the current lines of research. In a first pilot study (Schoch et al., 2017), the questionnaire was developed and empirically tested on a small heterogeneous sample of pictorial works created by non-professionals. This resulted in a preliminary test version and encouraging statistical results regarding reliability. In a second study (Schoch & Ostermann, under review) *RizbA* was validated on a large representative sample of amateur pictorial works and a large sample of experts rating those, yielding moderate to high reliabilities and allowing generalizability to non-professional art.

METHOD

Since the two previous studies successfully validated *RizbA* on amateur pictorial works, the current study aims to extend the area of application to professional visual art. It validates the instrument in terms of its generalizability to contemporary artworks. A large representative sample of pictorial works is used, created by artists from different cultural areas and dated to the 21st century.

The Rating Instrument for Two-Dimensional Pictorial Works (*RizbA*)

RizbA is a 26-item questionnaire referring to formal picture analysis (Streb, 1984; Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003), originating from the humanities and the arts and focusing on maximization of objectivity. It focuses on structuring art experts' ratings and includes formal aspects such as representation, color, shape, motion, composition, and expression. The test was developed in a previous pilot study (Schoch et al., 2017) and successfully validated in a second study with a large representative sample (Schoch & Ostermann, under review), both using pictorial works created by amateurs. The questionnaire uses a bipolar, six-point Likert-scale, which is discretely scaled and verbally anchored in shades of agreement (0 = *strongly disagree*, 5 = *strongly agree*). Using the questionnaire, raters receive a brief instruction to rate the image presented using the *RizbA* questionnaire. They are asked to focus on pre-dominant overall expression of a picture rather than any single details, while endorsing that there is no right or wrong, but only their valuation.

Pictorial Material.

The image material consists of artworks by contemporary artists from different cultural areas, including Europe, Asia, Africa, Northern and Southern America. We chose contemporary art for two reasons. Firstly, although art has evolved in the last centuries, it is

surprising that empirical research with contemporaries still uses only a small range of hundred-year-old, predominantly western images, such as impressionist or expressionist paintings when it comes to artistic stimulus material. One practical reason for this might be legal aspects of image rights. Fortunately, with digitization and Open GLAM initiatives (GLAM Wiki, 2020) availability of art has currently considerably changed. We thus took this chance to use contemporary artworks for a contemporary study. The second reason for using contemporary works is comparability, since all previous validation studies (Schoch et al., 2017; Schoch & Ostermann, under review) and pilot studies (Epstein, 2019; Janßen, 2018) on *RizbA* used amateur works from the 21st century.

Data was gathered using *prometheus*, which is a distributed digital image archive connecting databases from various institutes, research facilities, and museums (<https://www.prometheus-bildarchiv.de>; Simon & Verstegen, 2004). Databases not relevant to the subject were excluded from the search engine (e.g., architecture, archeology, early and prehistory, Egyptology, churches and castles, graphic prints, video). The archive was searched using the advanced search option starting with image material dated 2018 and going backwards chronologically. Hits were further selected based on additional criteria the first of which being that the year of their making had to be in the 21st century.

Second, only drawings, paintings, collages, and mixed-techniques in between were used, since the test has not yet been validated for other than handmade two-dimensional works. Thus, machined works (e.g., photography), three-dimensional work (e.g., sculpture) and printing techniques (e.g., etching) were excluded. Since they make use of more elaborated tools, such as a photo camera or a printing press, those techniques entail different creation processes than using a pencil or brush, where the ductus of the creator is directly recognizable. It is highly likely that *RizbA* also works for non-handmade techniques, but it needs further testing and validation to have empirical evidence considering that.

Third, the image had to comprise a whole view. Images showing only a detail of an artwork or a whole exhibition space displaying the artwork were excluded. Fourth, images had to offer a sufficiently good picture quality (e.g., resolution, sharpness, picture section). The resulting sample was reduced to one image per artist, choosing the most recent piece.

The required sample size of images was calculated based on existing guidelines on principal component analysis (PCA), We oriented towards Guadagnoli and Velicer (1988) as well as Osborne and Costello (2009), in which a subject to item ratio of at least 10:1 is proposed. As a consequence, a minimum sample size of at least 260 images was calculated to be sufficient for the study.

The systematic search resulted in a final sample of 318 images of artworks by professional artists differing in gender, ethnicity, and origin dated from 2005 to 2018 (see Table 1). Since *prometheus* is a distributed archive with data stemming from different institutions, the digital image size varied between 18 kilobytes and 7.4 megabytes. Meeting the requirements of the online survey provider, larger images were reduced to a maximum of 640 kilobytes by using Apple Photos software.

Table 1
Pictorial material: Dating of artworks

Dating (year)	Number of artworks selected
2018	0
2017	0
2016	3
2015	19
2014	35
2013	20
2012	22
2011	14
2010	21
2009	25
2008	22
2007	37
2006	30
2005	70
In total	318

The Study

Study Design

An online study design was chosen using *SoSci Survey* (Leiner, 2018) with additional use of PHP elements. The study consisted of a test (T1) and a retest (T2) at intervals of a minimum of 14 days (see Figure 1), in which experts were asked to rate the image sample using *RizbA*. Each rater was presented the same six images at both times of measurement. Raters with a professional training in visual art were recruited via email, websites, and social media. For this purpose, 122 universities, 48 associations, 23 art museums and 742 individuals in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland were contacted inviting all their professional staff, students, and associates to participate and disseminate the call for raters among others. No rater training was conducted. As an incentive, vouchers were raffled among participants.

Figure 1. Study design: Test-retest design

Raters

As a criterion for inclusion to ensure raters know the art terms used, only professionals who have an academic degree related to visual art or are students who have been studying an art-related subject for at least one year were requested to participate. Only relevant disciplines were allowed. These included art history, art pedagogy, visual art, art therapy, design, graphic design, art sciences, image sciences, restoration and others.

There are only a few empirically based guidelines regarding the statistically required sample size of raters. Some literature recommends two or three observations per subject, given $\alpha = .05$ and a required reliability of at least .40 (Walter, Eliasziw, & Donner, 1998). Since this is not an application study, but the constitutive calibration of a new questionnaire, either way we opted for a larger number of raters. Addressing sample size and ICCs, for an exploratory approach, an *a priori* set cut-off point and a pilot study are recommended (LeBreton & Senter, 2008). The first pilot study (Schoch et al., 2017) yielded moderate to very strong rater agreement with eight to twelve raters per image. Since both preceding studies (Schoch et al., 2017; Schoch & Ostermann, under review) resulted in sufficiently high inter-rater agreement and test-retest reliability, the current investigation concentrates on artistic stimulus material rather than on the raters' judgement. This is why the current one aims for only ten raters per picture at T1, in comparison to the previous study aiming for the double number.

Procedure

In the online survey, participants were introduced to using the *RizbA* scale and asked to rate each picture consecutively presented to them using all 26 items. For each rater, six images were randomly, successively drawn without returning them. When all images of the entire picture sample had been drawn from the hat and rated once, the process started again. The order in which items were presented was randomized between subjects.

Fourteen days after completing the first survey (T1), raters were electronically invited to the retest, at which they were shown the same selection of pictures as in the first

part and again rated them using the *RizbA* scale. Raters could not skip items, but had to answer all questions to proceed. At the end of both tests, raters were asked whether they had completed the questionnaire seriously, outlining that the participation is anonymous and there will be no consequences if they didn't. In T1, only datasets of raters who finished rating all six images were used in the analysis. Raters who stated not to have completed the questionnaire seriously were not invited to the retest (T2). For each rater, a code was automatically generated at the end of T1, maintaining anonymity and enabling later assignment from T1 and T2 responses. A database was automatically established, in which information was stored.

Statistical Analysis

Only complete datasets were used, in which all six presented images were fully processed. Data from prematurely terminated surveys was excluded. For reasons of comparability, statistical analyses were conducted analogically to the recent validation study on amateur works.

Analysis of the questionnaire's quality criteria focused on two units. For calculation of item means, item standard deviation, item difficulty, capacity of differentiation, test-retest reliability, factor analysis, and index of factor similarity pictorial works were the unit of analysis. For inter-rater reliability, raters served as the relevant unit. The data included three levels (items, pictures, raters), of which the relevant one was chosen for each analysis, while the other two were averaged. Because each rater assessed only six images from the entire pictorial material, on a rater level the dataset inherently included a large amount of empty cells. For analyses regarding raters' agreement, subjects were therefore merged to new generic combined raters. Due to this restructuring of the data and different numbers of ratings per image, missing values occurred, which were not imputed. For analysis, only those generic raters with less than 20 % missing values were used, so as not to lose too much data through listwise deletion. This cut-off point was defined *a posteriori*, based on the descriptive statistics. For structuring the datasets, Excel including Visual Basic for Applications was used. All statistical analyses were analogically conducted for both times of measurements, test (T1) and retest (T2). The data was analyzed using SPSS Statistics 24.

Descriptive Statistics: Raters Descriptive statistics were calculated for the sample of raters in terms of demographic variables, such as gender, age and art-related qualification.

Descriptive Statistics: Items Descriptive statistics were calculated for each item.

Item Difficulty Item difficulty reflects the difficulty to answer an item. As a measure for item difficulty Dahl's difficulty index for interval-levelled data was computed. It is the arithmetic mean of item responses and is defined within the range of 0 to 1. The higher its

value, the easier it is for raters to answer symptomatically, meaning to give a positive response. Vice versa, the lower the value, the less likely agreement is. While items with extreme indices can barely differentiate, since extreme characteristics are rarely given, those with a medium difficulty are the most informative (Moosbrugger & Kelava, 2007, p. 74).

Capacity of Differentiation Another criterion is that items should be able to distinguish between different types of images. For example, the difference between a tender pencil drawing and a pasty oil-painting should be reflected in the data. Capacity of differentiation between images was examined for each item, as well as the overall test by criteria like item variance and item effect size. Item variance is understood as an item's differentiation ability with regard to the sample, in this case the image sample (Moosbrugger & Kelava, 2007, p. 71). Item variance was calculated along with the descriptive statistics. Item effect size is a further measure for indicating the amount of variance explained by an item or the overall test. It was calculated using a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA), in which the items served as dependent variables and the images as fixed factors. The resulting partial eta-squared computed (Levine & Hullett, 2002) was interpreted as an effect size estimator for the variance explained by each item and the overall test.

Test-Retest Reliability One and the same picture should be rated similarly at any given time. As an indicator for stability and ratings not being arbitrary, test-retest reliability between both times of measurement was determined by calculating Pearson product-moment correlations.

Principal Component Analysis Factor analysis serves as a tool to examine whether items correlate highly with the factors they are supposed to measure, such as constructs, dimensions, or attributes. An exploratory procedure was chosen, since there is no previous empirical data available on a possible factors' structure. PCA was chosen as a method of extraction, because it aims at explaining as much variance of the observed variable as possible (Moosbrugger & Kelava, 2007, p. 308). A PCA followed by varimax rotation was conducted. This was based on recommendations by Brown (2009) and Suhr (2005) as an exploratory data reduction procedure (Osborne & Costello, 2004; Suhr, 2006). Kaiser criterion and scree plot were applied and results were compared to Horn's parallel analysis, using O'Connor's syntax (O'Connor, 2000, 2018). Factors with larger eigenvalues than parallel components were extracted in another PCA followed by varimax rotation.

Tucker's Coefficient of Congruence Tucker's coefficient of congruence (Lorenzo-Seva & Ten Berge, 2006; Tucker & Lewis, 1973) was computed, functioning as a further index on accepting or rejecting the given factor's solution. The coefficient represents the cosine of the angle between two vectors and a standardized measure of proportionality of

elements (Lorenzo-Seva & Ten Berge, 2006). It is an additional reliability coefficient indicating whether an otherwise acceptable factor model, such as the exploratory one above retrieved by a PCA, does indeed represent the interrelations among the attributes for a population (Tucker & Lewis, 1973).

The procedure was followed and the coefficient was calculated as outlined by Wünsch (2016) as well as Fetz, Vogt, Ostermann, Schmitz, and Schulz-Quach (2018). The dataset was split into two random samples, a PCA followed by varimax rotation was calculated, and the suggested eight factors were extracted. The resulting component loading matrices were both compared with each other. Two-tailed Pearson correlations ($\alpha = .05$) were calculated. Based on significant correlations between factors from both samples, factors were accordingly paired and Tucker's coefficient of congruency was calculated. The values of this statistical parameter per definition range between +1 and -1 and can be interpreted similarly to the Pearson's product-moment correlation (Chan, Ho, Leung, Chan, & Yung, 1999). Since it depicts the degree of deviation between two factors, negative coefficients can be interpreted similarly to positive values. Results were interpreted as recommended by Chan et al. (1999) and Lorenzo-Seva and Ten Berge (2006), where a critical congruence level, rather than unity for indication of identical factors is suggested. Values between .85 - .94 indicate fair similarity, whereas values higher than .95 suggest two factors or components being equal.

Inter-Rater Reliability Inter-rater agreement serves as a measure for objectivity. It was calculated for each item and the overall test as a measure for relative consistency between the expert ratings (LeBreton & Senter, 2008). On the basis of not all images being rated by each subject, and values being averaged, intraclass correlation coefficients (*ICCs*) one-way random average measures with absolute agreement were calculated. Due to the restructuring of the dataset by averaging beyond raters for the analysis of *ICCs*, missing values occurred that fulfill the assumptions of missing at random (MAR; Rubin, 1996; Schafer & Olsen, 1998). A frequency analysis of missing values per case was conducted. In consequence, three different models of datasets were compiled and the *ICCs* calculated separately with these were compared to each other. For reference, model A was created by excluding all cases with more than 20% missing values from the dataset. No missing values were imputed resulting in SPSS's basic procedure in treating missing values, listwise deletion. Since this diminished sample size resulted in a decrease of power of the analysis, two further models were compiled both using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm (Baltes-Götz, 2013; Pigott, 2001) for imputation. In model B, all cases with more than 20% missing values were excluded as well, and the remaining missing values were imputed. In model C, all cases were included and all

missing values were imputed. Multivariate normal data is assumed. EM algorithm was applied, because of its advantages in comparison to other simpler ways of treating missing values (e.g., listwise deletion or mean imputation), and for preserving the relationship with other variables (Pigott, 2001). Since there are no significant differences between Monte Carlo Markov chain (MCMC) method and EM algorithm in accuracy of imputation (Lin, 2010), we went for the latter, as the plainer procedure resulting in only one imputed dataset. Finally in addition Cronbach's alpha was calculated as a measure for internal consistency, which in this case is functionally equivalent to the formulation of ICCs (McGraw & Wong, 1996; Shrout & Fleiss, 1979).

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics: Raters

In total, 1,160 participants started the online survey at T1. 643 of those processed only three of the six images. However, we only used the data of raters who completed T1 and processed all six images they were presented with. T1 was completed by a total of 521 raters. T2 was completed by 239 of those. At T1, data of eleven raters were excluded from the analysis for admitting to not having filled out the survey seriously. Data of four more raters was excluded, because they did not meet the inclusion criteria of expertise. The final sample of valid raters at T1 consists of 506 experts (432 female, 66 male, 8 diverse) between 19 and 77 years ($M = 32.92$, $SD = 11.68$). All of them have an academic degree in an art-related subject (63.6 %) or are in at least in their second year of study (36.4 %). The raters' disciplines include art therapy (24.9%), art history (19.2 %), visual art (14.6 %), art pedagogy (12.8 %), graphic design (4.7 %), design (4.7 %), art sciences (3.4%), restoration (2.4 %), image sciences (.4 %), and various others (12.8 %). Each picture is rated by one to 19 raters ($M = 9.54$, $SD = 2.50$) at T1 and by zero to ten raters ($M = 4.49$, $SD = 1.89$) at T2.

Descriptive Statistics: Items

The calculated item means range from 1.81 to 3.29 ($M = 2.35$, $SD = .40$) at T1 and from 1.75 to 3.25 ($M = 2.34$, $SD = .38$) at T2. Item standard deviations lie between 1.20 and 1.75 ($M = 1.49$, $SD = .11$) at T1 and between 1.14 and 1.69 ($M = 1.44$, $SD = .12$) at T2 (see Table 2).

Item Difficulty

Item difficulty p_i ranges from .36 to .66 ($M = .47$, $SD = .08$) at T1 and from .35 to .65 ($M = .46$, $SD = .08$) at T2 (see Table 2).

Capacity of Differentiation

Capacity of differentiation in the form of items' variance s_i^2 ranges from 1.48 to 3.05 ($M = 2.24$, $SD = .33$) at T1 and from 1.31 to 2.84 ($M = 2.09$, $SD = .34$) at T2 (see Table 2). Par-

tial eta-squared ranges from .23 to .58 ($M = .45$, $SD = .09$) at T1 and from .35 to .71 ($M = .54$, $SD = .08$) at T2 (see Table 2). The overall test yields a partial eta-squared of .31 (Pillai's trace: $F(8243, 70642) = 3.80$, $p = .000$) at T1 and .40 (Pillai's trace: $F(8164, 28938) = 2.38$, $p = .000$) at T2.

Table 2

RizbA: Translated* items and item values (T1+T2), unit of analysis pictures

No. Item*		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	s_i^2	p_i	η_p^2	
1	The picture includes graphic elements	<i>T1</i>	2.91	1.53	2.33	.36	.38
		<i>T2</i>	2.87	1.48	2.20	.35	.50
2	The picture includes pictorial elements	<i>T1</i>	3.29	1.48	2.19	.36	.50
		<i>T2</i>	3.25	1.46	2.12	.36	.56
3	The manner of representation is concrete	<i>T1</i>	2.87	1.63	2.65	.36	.58
		<i>T2</i>	2.81	1.57	2.45	.36	.71
4	The manner of representation is abstract	<i>T1</i>	2.37	1.61	2.60	.37	.57
		<i>T2</i>	2.41	1.57	2.47	.37	.66
5	The color application is pastose	<i>T1</i>	1.82	1.43	2.04	.38	.38
		<i>T2</i>	1.98	1.44	2.06	.38	.47
6	The predominant coloring is vibrant	<i>T1</i>	2.24	1.52	2.31	.38	.53
		<i>T2</i>	2.29	1.46	2.14	.38	.63
7	In the picture primary colors are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	1.91	1.36	1.86	.39	.29
		<i>T2</i>	1.92	1.30	1.68	.38	.35
8	In the picture mixed colors (secondary colors) are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	2.69	1.49	2.22	.41	.46
		<i>T2</i>	2.70	1.45	2.11	.39	.54
9	In the picture there are complementary contrasts	<i>T1</i>	2.42	1.60	2.55	.41	.41
		<i>T2</i>	2.43	1.59	2.53	.42	.50
10	In the picture organic shapes are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	2.70	1.42	2.03	.44	.49
		<i>T2</i>	2.72	1.38	1.91	.43	.58
11	In the picture geometric shapes are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	2.05	1.48	2.20	.45	.56
		<i>T2</i>	1.95	1.40	1.97	.43	.64
12	The layout of the line is predominantly curved	<i>T1</i>	2.47	1.44	2.08	.45	.50
		<i>T2</i>	2.57	1.37	1.89	.45	.60
13	The layout of the line is predominantly angled	<i>T1</i>	1.83	1.45	2.11	.47	.54
		<i>T2</i>	1.81	1.38	1.91	.45	.63
14	The picture includes unworked areas	<i>T1</i>	1.92	1.75	3.05	.47	.53
		<i>T2</i>	1.93	1.69	2.84	.46	.59
15	The picture appears to be deep	<i>T1</i>	2.37	1.39	1.92	.48	.37
		<i>T2</i>	2.28	1.35	1.83	.48	.49
16	The picture is perspectival	<i>T1</i>	2.52	1.50	2.23	.50	.48
		<i>T2</i>	2.43	1.46	2.12	.48	.58
17	The picture is without perspective (aperspectival)	<i>T1</i>	2.08	1.60	2.56	.50	.44
		<i>T2</i>	2.19	1.55	2.41	.48	.58

No. Item*		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	s_i^2	p_i	η_p^2
18 The picture is restless	<i>T1</i>	2.54	1.43	2.04	.51	.42
	<i>T2</i>	2.47	1.36	1.84	.50	.52
19 The picture is wild	<i>T1</i>	2.23	1.46	2.13	.51	.49
	<i>T2</i>	2.24	1.38	1.91	.51	.55
20 The global composition is laid out vertically	<i>T1</i>	2.49	1.57	2.45	.54	.48
	<i>T2</i>	2.40	1.53	2.35	.53	.57
21 The global composition is laid out horizontally	<i>T1</i>	1.96	1.52	2.32	.54	.45
	<i>T2</i>	1.92	1.47	2.16	.54	.56
22 The global composition is laid out diagonally	<i>T1</i>	1.82	1.48	2.20	.55	.40
	<i>T2</i>	1.75	1.42	2.03	.55	.49
23 The global composition is laid out area-wide without a main subject (All-Over-Structure)	<i>T1</i>	1.81	1.68	2.81	.56	.47
	<i>T2</i>	1.87	1.64	2.69	.55	.56
24 The picture appears to be diffuse	<i>T1</i>	2.20	1.41	2.00	.58	.31
	<i>T2</i>	2.20	1.34	1.80	.57	.43
25 The picture appears to be precise, accurate	<i>T1</i>	2.74	1.38	1.90	.58	.41
	<i>T2</i>	2.74	1.32	1.74	.57	.51
26 The picture appears to be harmonic	<i>T1</i>	2.78	1.22	1.48	.66	.23
	<i>T2</i>	2.69	1.14	1.31	.65	.36
<i>M</i>	<i>T1</i>	2.35	1.49	2.24	.47	.45
	<i>T2</i>	2.34	1.44	2.09	.46	.54
<i>SD</i>	<i>T1</i>	.40	.11	.33	.08	.09
	<i>T2</i>	1.75	1.14	1.31	.35	.35
<i>Min</i>	<i>T1</i>	1.81	1.22	1.48	.36	.23
	<i>T2</i>	1.75	1.14	1.31	.35	.35
<i>Max</i>	<i>T1</i>	3.29	1.75	3.05	.66	.58
	<i>T2</i>	3.25	1.69	2.84	.65	.71

* = original German version see additional material, T1 = test, T2 = retest, M = mean (0 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree), SD = item standard deviation, Min = minimum, Max = maximum, s_i^2 = item variance, p_i = item difficulty, η_p^2 = partial eta-squared effect size estimator

Test-Retest Reliability

Overall test-retest reliability yields a Pearson product-moment correlation of .86 ($r(3510) = .86, p = .000$).

Principal Component Analysis

A PCA followed by varimax rotation for both T1 and T2 results in eight factors with eigenvalues above one referring to Kaiser criterion. Both scree plots suggest six factors. Compared to Horn's parallel analysis, eight factors have larger eigenvalues than parallel components at both times of measurement. In another PCA followed by varimax rotation, eight factors are extracted accounting for 63.65 % (T1) and 65.99 % (T2) of the common variance (see Table 3 and 4).

Table 3 Rizba: Rotated component matrix, factor loadings (T1)

Preliminary labels	No.	Item	Components															
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8								
<i>shaping</i>	13	The layout of the line is predominantly angled	-.800															
	11	In the picture geometric shapes are prevalent	-.782															
	10	In the picture organic shapes are prevalent	.748															
	12	The layout of the line is predominantly curved	.725															
<i>picture effect</i>	18	The picture is restless		.834														
	19	The picture is wild		.784														
	26	The picture appears to be harmonic		-.695														
<i>spatiality</i>	24	The picture appears to be diffuse		.689														
	25	The picture appears to be precise, accurate		-.544														
	16	The picture is perspectival			.840													
<i>representation</i>	15	The picture appears to be deep			.830													
	17	The picture is without perspective (aperspectival)			-.743	.400												
	4	The manner of representation is abstract				.697												
<i>color intensity</i>	3	The manner of representation is concrete				-.672												
	23	The global composition is laid out area-wide without a main subject (All-Over-Structure)				.640												
	6	The predominant coloring is vibrant					.789											
<i>pictorial elements (painting)</i>	9	In the picture there are complementary contrasts					.702											
	8	In the picture mixed colors (secondary colors) are prevalent						.823										
	7	In the picture primary colors are prevalent						.526	-.663									
<i>composition</i>	2	The picture includes pictorial elements	.410															
	5	The color application is pastose							.418									
	20	The global composition is laid out vertically								.875								
<i>pictorial elements (drawing)</i>	21	The global composition is laid out horizontally								-.705								
	1	The picture includes graphic elements									.688							
	14	The picture includes unworked areas										.615						
	22	The global composition is laid out diagonally																.530

Method of extraction: PCA; Method of rotation: Varimax, Kaiser normalization; Values < .40 suppressed

Table 4 RizbA: Rotated component matrix, factor loadings (T2)

Preliminary labels	No.	Item	Components											
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
<i>picture effect</i>	18	The picture is restless	.856											
	19	The picture is wild	.794											
	24	The picture appears to be diffuse	.762											
	26	The picture appears to be harmonic	-.694											
	25	The picture appears to be precise, accurate	-.569											
<i>shaping</i>	13	The layout of the line is predominantly angled		-.815										
	12	The layout of the line is predominantly curved		.8										
<i>representation</i>	10	In the picture organic shapes are prevalent		.785										
	11	In the picture geometric shapes are prevalent		-.769										
	4	The manner of representation is abstract			.741									
	3	The manner of representation is concrete			-.740									
	23	The global composition is laid out area-wide without a main subject (All-Over-Structure)			.713									
<i>pictorial elements (painting)</i>	8	In the picture mixed colors (secondary colors) are prevalent				.726								
	2	The picture includes pictorial elements				.651								
<i>pictorial elements (drawing)</i>	5	The color application is pastose				.585								
	14	The picture includes unworked areas				-.577								
	1	The picture includes graphic elements				-.491		.456						
<i>spatiality</i>	15	The picture appears to be deep				.786								
	16	The picture is perspectival			-.467			.747						
<i>color intensity</i>	17	The picture is without perspective (aperspectival)			.536			-.634						
	6	The predominant coloring is vibrant						.760						
<i>composition</i>	7	In the picture primary colors are prevalent					-.422							
	9	In the picture there are complementary contrasts						.634						
	21	The global composition is laid out horizontally											-.820	
	20	The global composition is laid out vertically											.790	
	22	The global composition is laid out diagonally											.913	

Method of extraction: PCA; Method of rotation: Varimax, Kaiser normalization; Values < .40 suppressed

Tucker's Coefficient of Congruence

Tucker's coefficient of congruence ranges between $|.97|$ and $|1.00|$ at T1 and between $|.71|$ and $|.99|$ at T2 (see Table 5).

Table 5
Tucker's coefficient of congruence (T1 and T2)

Time of measurement	Factor	Tucker's coefficient of congruence
T1	factor ₁₁	.99
	factor ₂₂	1.00
	factor ₃₄	.99
	factor ₄₃	.98
	factor ₅₅	.99
	factor ₆₆	.97
	factor ₇₇	.99
	factor ₈₈	.98
T2	factor ₁₂	-.92
	factor ₂₃	.99
	factor ₃₁	.98
	factor ₄₄	.96
	factor ₅₆	.83
	factor ₆₇	.97
	factor ₇₈	.94
	factor ₈₅	.71

Inter-Rater Reliability

For model A items' ICCs range from .55 to .91 ($M = .82$, $SD = .08$) at T1 and from .32 to .82 ($M = .66$, $SD = .11$) at T2. Overall ICCs are .86 ($F(6681, 46774) = 7.14$, $p = .000$, 95% CI [.85, .87]) at T1 and .71 ($F(7045, 14092) = 3.50$, $p = .000$, 95% CI [.70, .73]) at T2. For model B items' ICCs range from .57 to .90 ($M = .83$, $SD = .07$) at T1 and from .36 to .82 ($M = .68$, $SD = .10$) at T2. Overall ICCs are .86 ($F(8267, 57876) = 7.38$, $p = .000$, 95% CI [.86, .87]) at T1 and .73 ($F(8267, 16536) = 3.67$, $p = .000$, 95% CI [.72, .74]) at T2. For model C items' ICCs range from .87 to .97 ($M = .94$, $SD = .02$) at T1 and from .73 to .92 ($M = .87$, $SD = .04$) at T2. Overall ICCs are .96 ($F(8267, 148824) = 22.94$, $p = .000$, 95% CI [.96, .96]) at T1 and .90 ($F(8267, 82680) = 9.49$, $p = .000$, 95% CI [.89, .89]) at T2 (see Table 6; Figure 2 and 3).

Table 6
RizbA: Translated* items and item values (T1+T2), unit of analysis raters

No.	Item*		<i>model A</i>	<i>model B</i>	<i>model C</i>
1	The picture includes graphic elements	<i>T1</i>	.77	.78	.93
		<i>T2</i>	.65	.67	.84
2	The picture includes pictorial elements	<i>T1</i>	.86	.87	.96
		<i>T2</i>	.70	.72	.84
3	The manner of representation is concrete	<i>T1</i>	.91	.90	.97
		<i>T2</i>	.82	.82	.91
4	The manner of representation is abstract	<i>T1</i>	.90	.89	.97
		<i>T2</i>	.76	.77	.92
5	The color application is pastose	<i>T1</i>	.79	.80	.93
		<i>T2</i>	.57	.62	.87
6	The predominant coloring is vibrant	<i>T1</i>	.88	.88	.96
		<i>T2</i>	.76	.77	.91
7	In the picture primary colors are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	.69	.72	.90
		<i>T2</i>	.32	.36	.80
8	In the picture mixed colors (secondary colors) are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	.84	.84	.95
		<i>T2</i>	.67	.67	.86
9	In the picture there are complementary contrasts	<i>T1</i>	.80	.82	.94
		<i>T2</i>	.60	.62	.88
10	In the picture organic shapes are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	.86	.86	.96
		<i>T2</i>	.73	.73	.86
11	In the picture geometric shapes are prevalent	<i>T1</i>	.90	.90	.97
		<i>T2</i>	.77	.77	.92
12	The layout of the line is predominantly curved	<i>T1</i>	.87	.87	.96
		<i>T2</i>	.73	.73	.88
13	The layout of the line is predominantly angled	<i>T1</i>	.89	.89	.96
		<i>T2</i>	.75	.76	.92
14	The picture includes unworked areas	<i>T1</i>	.89	.89	.96
		<i>T2</i>	.73	.75	.92
15	The picture appears to be deep	<i>T1</i>	.77	.78	.93
		<i>T2</i>	.60	.63	.86
16	The picture is perspectival	<i>T1</i>	.85	.85	.95
		<i>T2</i>	.69	.71	.89
17	The picture is without perspective (aperspectival)	<i>T1</i>	.83	.84	.95
		<i>T2</i>	.66	.69	.90
18	The picture is restless	<i>T1</i>	.81	.82	.94
		<i>T2</i>	.66	.68	.86
19	The picture is wild	<i>T1</i>	.85	.86	.96
		<i>T2</i>	.71	.72	.88

No.	Item*		model A	model B	model C
20	The global composition is laid out vertically	T1	.86	.86	.96
		T2	.71	.73	.89
21	The global composition is laid out horizontally	T1	.82	.85	.95
		T2	.67	.69	.91
22	The global composition is laid out diagonally	T1	.82	.81	.94
		T2	.60	.63	.89
23	The global composition is laid out area-wide without a main subject (All-Over-Structure)	T1	.85	.85	.95
		T2	.69	.69	.91
24	The picture appears to be diffuse	T1	.70	.72	.91
		T2	.62	.61	.84
25	The picture appears to be precise, accurate	T1	.81	.81	.94
		T2	.64	.68	.84
26	The picture appears to be harmonic	T1	.55	.57	.87
		T2	.42	.47	.73
<i>M</i>		T1	.82	.83	.94
		T2	.66	.68	.87
<i>SD</i>		T1	.08	.07	.02
		T2	.11	.10	.04
<i>Min</i>		T1	.55	.57	.87
		T2	.32	.36	.73
<i>Max</i>		T1	.91	.90	.97
		T2	.82	.82	.92

* = original German version see additional material, T1 = test, T2 = retest, *M* = mean (0 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree), *SD* = item standard deviation, *Min* = minimum, *Max* = maximum, *ICC* = intraclass correlation coefficient average measure

Figure 2. Items' ICCs (T1): Model A, B, and C with 95% confidence interval

Figure 3. Items' ICCs (T2): Model A, B, and C with 95% confidence interval

DISCUSSION

In empirical art psychology and creativity research most studies focus on the psychological correlates of art. Only a few go beyond treating artworks as categorical data (e.g. abstract vs. representational) and consider artworks in detail. The rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works *RizbA* makes a difference to current research approaches. This article outlines the validity of the novel *RizbA* by means of a statistical approach. Thus, the results presented here need to be discussed by both statistical quality criteria, as well as their limitations and implications given for further research.

Statistical Quality Criteria

Item Difficulty The items yield medium-sized difficulty indices, providing excellent information on and differentiation between pictorial characteristics.

Capacity of Differentiation Item variances as an additional criterion for capacity of differentiation are moderate to large. Comparing partial eta-squared to common effect sizes (Coster, 2012), large effects can be assumed here as well, meaning the instrument is capable of differentiating between different types of images.

Test-Retest Reliability Relating to common effect size conventions (Cohen, 1992), the overall test-reliability suggests a large effect and implies *RizbA* as being a stable measure across time. This ensures ratings are not arbitrary, but one and the same picture is rated similar at any given time.

Principal Component Analysis

The results empirically support the existence of an interpretable factor structure. PCA suggests eight interpretable components, measured by the scale, that account for a large part of common variance. Prospective factor labels were *a posteriori* designated based on the empirical data and theoretical reasoning. This involved an iterative discussion process of expert opinions referring to art theory, which included experts of the HKS – University of Applied Sciences and Arts in Ottersberg and the German Creative Arts Therapies Research Association (FVKT).

Resulting factor labels (in corresponding order to Table 5) might be *shaping*, *picture effect*, *spatiality*, *representation*, *color intensity*, *pictorial elements (painting)*, *composition*, and *pictorial elements (drawing)*. The number of extracted factors is different from the first pilot study, which indicated only four factors preliminarily interpreted as *picture effect*, *representation*, *shaping* and *perspective* (Schoch et al., 2017). However, they resemble the factors structure in the second study that used amateur pictorial works (Schoch & Ostermann, under review), with *shaping* and *picture effect* factors being the most stable components across studies. The *picture effect* factor is stable across times of measurement

and studies and contains high factor loadings. However, in terms of content validity, it does not clearly measure the defined concept of formal picture elements. Thought must be given to exclude this factor in the final test version. Moreover, especially two items should be further reviewed: Item 7 (*In the picture primary colors are prevalent*) on both times of measurements has diametrically opposed cross loadings on two factors, namely *color intensity* and *pictorial elements (painting)*. A theoretical reason to explain this cross-load might be that color is a relevant item for both factors. Item 22 (*The global composition is laid out diagonally*) has a medium loading on *pictorial elements (drawing)* at T1, but turns into a highly loading single item factor at T2.

The most intriguing conclusion of the expert group process is that the empirical factor solution does not properly reflect existing art theories as described in professional literature (e.g., Belting, Dilly, Kemp, Sauerländer, & Warnke, 1996). This becomes particularly clear when comparing the factor labels of this study with the theoretical content areas used to compile the initial pool of 113 items in early test construction phase: *representation, color, shape, space, movement, composition* and *expression* (Schoch, 2014). Those might sound similar to current labels, but contain very different items than a priori theoretically hypothesized. One explanation for this disparity might be that *RizbA* does not measure formal elements in terms of a theoretical classification model of picture analysis, like art history, or image science contextualizes them. Rather, *RizbA* appears to capture sort of a temper or atmosphere of the image itself. However, it is not a subjective impression of how an image is perceived. It is intersubjectively measurable as the inter-rater reliabilities indicate. This might suggest a gap between art theory and its empirical findings that should be further addressed.

Tucker's Coefficients of Congruence Tucker's coefficients of congruence at T1 all indicate high similarity and thus all respective two components being equal. At T2, two factors yield high, four yield fair, and two suggest only moderate similarity. Still, the results obtained are rather conservative (Wünsch, 2016). Analogically to the previous study, we went for the conservative approach in contrast to the usual procedure, stipulating a Procrustean factor rotation with orthogonal rotation to maximum similarity (Chan et al., 1999; Cliff, 1966; McCrae, Zonderman, Costa Jr, Bond, & Paunonen, 1996; Raykov & Little, 1999; Schönemann, 1966; Zumbo, Sireci, & Hambleton, 2003).

Inter-Rater Reliability Comparing ICCs resulting from the three datasets, model C yields the highest inter-rater reliability. Still, due the amount of values imputed, the dataset includes zero variance items and is likely to overestimate the effect. Reliabilities in model A and B are comparable with one another, but generally lower than in model C. Model A

suffers from the disadvantages of listwise deletion, such as biased estimations and loss of precision (Baltes-Götz, 2013). However, to avoid these and prevent a decrease in power we decided to go for model B, which entails a moderate loss of data due to excluding cases, but provides a realistic dataset with sufficient power. Based on statistical guidelines (Koo & Li, 2016; LeBreton & Senter, 2008), *ICC* of the overall test at T1 can be interpreted as strong agreement among raters (LeBreton & Senter, 2008) and thus good inter-rater reliability (Koo & Li, 2016). On the item level, the results reach from moderate to very strong agreement and hence moderate to good reliability. At T2, the entire test yields strong agreement and moderate reliability. On the item level, results are more diverse reaching from weak to strong agreement, which suggests poor to good reliability.

When compared, the test quality at T1 is mostly higher and more reliable than at T2, which may be because of the differences in the sample size of raters. This is reflected in good to excellent results at T1 compared to considerably weak to moderate quality criteria at T2 regarding *ICCs*, Tucker's coefficients of congruence and PCA in particular (Suhr, 2005). Considering the partly small amount of ratings for some stimuli at T2, it is debatable to what extent results of the retest are conclusive for other quality criteria than test-retest reliability.

Comparing the present results to those of the previous validation study by Schoch and Ostermann (under review) on amateur art, item means, item standard deviations, item variance, and partial eta-squared reach similar values. Factorial structures resemble one another and Tucker's coefficient of congruence are comparably high. *ICCs* for the overall test are similar in both studies, with T1 of the current study yielding a slightly higher reliability compared to T1 of the previous study. Then again, T2 of the current study has slightly less reliability than at T2 in the previous study. The only clear difference lies within test-retest reliability, which was .93 higher in the preceding study compared to the current one, attaining only .86.

Limitations

Technical Aspects There are two technical drawbacks as result of the online data collection. Image sizes were rather small to meet the *SoSci Survey's* (Leiner, 2018) maximum upload capacity and to make sure images load fast with any internet connection. Based on the large sample size needed, this was discarded. Also, the raters viewed the images on their own devices, which might result in a different display of color and resolution. Using a better quality of image solution, a different rating experience may be expected, especially when original works instead of digital copies are used.

As already mentioned, for some images at the retest, the number of ratings is insufficiently small. In the survey, images were drawn without putting back, which should normally lead to a reasonably equal number of ratings per picture. However, if raters did not terminate the survey, the images presented to them were already drawn, but are not represented in the data, because only complete sets were included in the analysis. Future studies should use an even more detailed PHP code, putting pictures back if subjects prematurely abort the survey. However, the general sample size at T2 was not sufficiently large to calculate all statistics appropriately with sufficient power. Results at T2 are to be interpreted with caution.

Data Structure

As described, datasets regarding raters' agreement were merged, which resulted in missing values. For not losing too much data through listwise deletion, in model B only those generic raters with less than 20 % missing values were used and the remaining missing values were imputed. Since the presentation of artworks was randomized and the assumption of missing at random is fulfilled, the results are probably not biased by this *a posteriori* defined cut-off point. Still, the criterion was not defined *a priori* and there is a non-negligible loss of information. Also, there are several disadvantages of imputation compared to originally obtained data, for example underestimating the standard error (Baltes-Götz, 2013).

Factor Analysis

PCA suggests an interpretable factor structure with eight components. Still, not having conducted a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), final conclusions cannot be drawn. On the basis of the exploratory state of research in this field, other statistical criteria usually used for test validation were not yet applied. This includes internal consistency measures, such as split-half reliability, which require test scales measuring one construct, to date an uncertain condition.

Samples

The metadata about the images provided by *prometheus* varies slightly in terms of completeness, precision, and systematics, due to stemming from different institutions, which contribute to the archive. Although these sources are institutes, research facilities and museums, it cannot be guaranteed that all information and dating is unflawed. Due to an error, two artists' images were included in the sample, opposed to the initial regulation specifying one image each.

Although the amount of information included in the metadata differs, it reveals several biases regarding ethnicity and gender in image databases. In principle, the pictorial material includes a relatively heterogeneous sample created by artists of different origins.

The *prometheus* database includes works by international artists from European, African, American, and Asian countries. Still, being based in Germany, there is a bias towards a western cultural area. Considering the rater sample, they also come from a probably Eurocentric cultural context. Since art and several psychological variables differ across cultures (Cattaneo, 1994), it can be assumed that there are cultural differences in art-making and art perception as well. Speaking about the artists' gender, 73.4 % of its creators are male, only 18.4 % female and 0.3 % diverse. For the remaining 7.9 % the gender is not assignable based on the metadata. Unfortunately, this bias in gender and diversity reflect the current art world (Fraiberger, Sinatra, Resch, Riedl, & Barabási, 2018), where cis white males are still disproportionately more featured. Network effects play a crucial role in an artist's reputation and valuation, while being from a country with better access to the art network means having higher chances of starting and ending one's career at the top. (Fraiberger et al., 2018). Considering the rater sample, experts stem from German speaking countries (Germany, Austria, Switzerland). Here, 85.38 % are female, 13.04 % male and 1.58 % diverse.

Thus, the image and the rater sample are both biased in terms of gender and tend towards a western, in particular Eurocentric, and probably objectivistic cultural context. Since art as well as several psychological variables differ across cultures (Cattaneo, 1994), it is highly likely to find differences in art-making and rating art as well. This probably also refers to gender and other contexts relevant to both pictures and raters. Future studies should investigate the instrument's validity by taking into account gender, ethnicity, and other relevant variables of both pictures and raters with a critical view on Eurocentrism (Mosquera, 1992) and paternalistic structures. In particular, scientific databases and research should strive for more diversity to accurately represent the spectrum of the population. Although at the time of this study *WikiArt* (<https://www.wikiart.org>) is not comprehensive enough when it comes to contemporary art, open projects like this with specific categories such as "female artists" might become a promising tool in conducting art-related research (e.g., Marengo, Fazekas, & Tombros, 2017; Mohammad & Kiritchenko, 2018).

Artworks

In the current study, only two-dimensional artworks were used as image material. It is apparent that contemporary visual art entails a multitude of art forms, such as plastics, installations, environments, happenings, digital art, street art, and more. Addressing this issue there has currently been an item pool compiled for three-dimensional works (e.g., sculptures, plastics, reliefs). It is waiting to be empirically tested. However, more specific instruments are needed to measure walk-in artworks in terms of a formal analysis analogously to *RizbA*.

Implications

RizbA was successfully validated on a sample of contemporary art. Taking the study's results into consideration, it is highly likely that they can be generalized to the entirety of pictorial contemporary art. This makes *RizbA* a valid and reliable instrument for all sorts of handmade two-dimensional pictorial works – whether created by artists or amateurs.

Enhancing Methodology in Research on Art

Independently from the focus of research on art, it would be highly desirable not only to capture psychological and physiological variables, but also the artwork itself. Until now, there has been a lack of instruments that are capable of reliably describing these. According to our results, *RizbA* might make a difference. With *RizbA*, it may be possible to reliably examine both the artwork and its psychological correlates. As the first quantitative and reliable tool for formal picture analysis, *RizbA* allows a detailed analysis of the formal content and a wide range of applicability. In art psychology, objects of research could be further assessed, giving art-making and artworks significantly more weight. Adding such a measurement of artworks to existing methodology in the field, it might become highly instructive for a wide range of research topics, such as aesthetics, creativity, and personality.

Empirical Aesthetics

Psychological aesthetics has a long empirical tradition (Leder, Belke, Oeberst, & Augustin, 2004; Martindale, 2007) going back to experimental psychologists like Wundt (1874) and Fechner (1876). Still, the focus of empirical aesthetics is art perception with all its constructs, such as aesthetic experience, aesthetic appreciation, or aesthetic emotions. There are complex theoretical models like the *Information-processing Stage Model of Aesthetic Processing* (Leder et al., 2004), stating aesthetic experience to be a reciprocal cognitive and affective process, or the *Vienna Integrated Model of Art Perception* (Pelowski, Markey, Forster, Gerger, & Leder, 2017) – a model of processing visual artworks.

Outcomes provoked by an art object, such as aesthetic emotions (Menninghaus et al., 2018), aesthetic appreciation, and aesthetic judgement, have already been empirically examined. For example, people differ in art preference, their emotions towards it, and in what they regard to be art (Leder et al., 2012). Another example are field studies; for example, in museum contexts, where Tröndle and Tschacher (2012) found artworks being correlated with physical reactions of viewers, their spatial behavior, and their aesthetic ratings. Innovative field research like this could also be enriched by rating the art and including this data.

Existing theories and research of this sort could be supplemented with an additional view on the artworks' formal content. For example, an area for investigation could focus

on the part of a painting that makes people appreciate it – this might be the intensity of color or the dynamics – and not just which category – abstract or representational. One way to operationalize this could be by combining the *Art Reception Survey* (Hager et al., 2012) and *RizbA*, and assessing intercorrelations between them. For example, cognitive stimulation might be linked to an artwork's composition. Furthermore, in field studies one could additionally research whether there are specific contents of artworks that make people move differently in a gallery space.

For example, an artwork by Kara Walker with a lot of figures in movement and thus more dynamics might invite perceivers to behave differently than the quiet-color field painting by Helen Frankenthaler. This could be operationalized in a correlation study, in which both are rated, the artworks using *RizbA* and the viewers' movement profiles in the gallery space. And then again, a color field by Helen Frankenthaler might provoke a different response than a conceptual work by Tracy Emin. Hence, further instruments should be developed, each specifically capturing different types of art.

Aesthetics and Creativity

Still, research usually focuses on creativity and aesthetics separately, which limits the view on art inherently comprising both perspectives – the artist's and the art viewer's. On a theoretical level, Tinio (2013) developed the *Mirror Model of Art* to overcome this divide. The model connects art-making and art-viewing and proposes that aesthetic experiences mirror the art-making process. It proposes three levels in the art-making process (initialization / expansion and adaption / finalizing) reversely mirroring three stages in the process of art-experiencing (early automatic processing / intermediate memory-based processing / meaning-making, aesthetic judgements, aesthetic emotions).

In their research, Pelowski et al. (2017) investigate affective, evaluative, and neuro-physiological correlates of perceiving and interacting with art. One could drive this idea that viewing and making art are connected and include sense-making processes (Sullivan & McCarthy, 2009), forwarded by designing a study that involves both creation and perception. Psychological measures and *RizbA* ratings could be used for investigating how inner processes and their pictorial expression in form of artworks are linked. Using *RizbA*, studies on those issues could go beyond measuring solely psychological variables and additionally capture the artworks themselves while they are being created and perceived.

Art and Personality

Although aesthetics, creativity, and art-making have to be differentiated, they correlate and overlap to a large extent (Zaidel, Nadal, Flexas, & Munar, 2013). For example, there is evidence for correlations between art preferences, thinking styles, and personality

(Gridley, 2006, 2013). Personality also predicts aesthetic chills, well before intelligence or demographic background (Silvia & Nusbaum, 2011).

Besides that, creativity is closely related with openness to experience. Creative people tend to have an affinity or ability for changing within their personality traits. Complexity might even be a trait inherent to creative personalities (Haller & Courvoisier, 2010). These findings relate to the paradoxes of creativity, one of which is that the combination of personality features do not necessarily or logically belong together; for example, divergent and convergent thinking (Cropley, 1997). This also relates to previous studies (Gridley, 2006, 2013), in which evidence was found for correlations between personality and art preference, for example when it comes to openness to experience.

Taking into account that aesthetics and creativity are linked and both are related to personality, it is likely that there are correlations between artworks as an outcome of these and personality as well. If openness to experience correlates positively with a liking for abstract art (Gridley, 2013), people with high scores might not only be more likely to appreciate, but also more likely to create abstract artworks. This could be assessed by methodologically combining *RizbA* with personality measures, such as HEXACO-PI-R (Lee & Ashton, 2009; Moshagen, Hilbig, & Zettler, 2014).

Analogies With Other Arts

Another direction of research would be to find similarities and differences between the arts, for example visual arts, performing arts, literature, and music. Research already conducted on music (Colver & El-Alayli, 2016), film (e.g., Hanich, Wagner, Shah, Jacobsen, & Menninghaus, 2014; Wassiliwizky, Wagner, Jacobsen, & Menninghaus, 2015), or poetry (e.g., Menninghaus, Bohrn, Altmann, Lubrich, & Jacobs, 2014) could be expanded to visual arts. For example, analogical to Wassiliwizky et al. (2015) investigating art-elicited chills with regard to films, one could examine which formal elements in an image move you and make you shiver – the corporeality in Louise Bourgeois' or rather the veiled colors in Esther Teichmann's works.

Future Research

The next obligatory step is to conduct CFA to verify the factor structure of the scale (Suhr, 2006). In terms of further investigating the previously mentioned gap between art theory and its empirical findings, the CFA should test two models against each other. The first model suggests a factor structure based on the empirical data collected. The other compounds items to factors, as art theory would predict dimensions. Finding substantial differences between theory and empirics would fuel the discourse between arts, humanities, and science described by Mersch (2019) and other theorists. Therefore, we are currently

conducting another study, using new image material and computing the CFA based on an evolved theoretical model of the construct pictorial expression.

Another consecutive step is translating and validating the questionnaire into English and making it accessible to a broader audience. Future research will also include other populations of raters, such as art experts from other cultural areas or raters from other professions than the arts. Addressing the latter issue, a study has currently been conducted, testing the questionnaire on expert vs. non-expert raters in art (Jerusalem, 2020). The resulting test manual explains art-related terminology and ensures that the questionnaire is also applicable by researchers and practitioners from other domains without art training (e.g., psychology, pedagogy, psychiatry). In terms of test validation, there will be further studies examining convergent and divergent validity by multitrait-multimethod matrix analyses (Campbell & Fiske, 1959) using related but distinct scales, such as the *Assessment of Art Attributes* (Chatterjee et al., 2010), the *Diagnostic Drawing Series* (B. M. Cohen & Mills, 2015; Mills, 2003) or the *Formal Elements Art Therapy Scale* (Gantt, 2016).

In order to achieve a maximum of comparability, statistical analyses were conducted analogically to the previous study, including averaging data to the relevant level of analysis. Future approaches might put more emphasis on the different units of analysis by using other statistical approaches, for example multilevel modelling (Silvia, 2007). Future research will concentrate on further validation regarding other sorts of two-dimensional pictorial works, such as non-handmade techniques, images created by children and adolescents and by people from non-western cultural contexts. The validation should also reach out to other populations of raters, for example art experts from other cultural areas or raters from professions other than the arts. Addressing the latter issue, a study is currently being conducted testing the questionnaire on expert vs. non-expert raters and developing a test manual explaining the terminology. This will make the questionnaire applicable to researchers and practitioners from all domains.

Due to the Open Data provided by RizbA validation studies, images and associated RizbA ratings can be further used for secondary data analyses. So far, there are similarities with a data set. However, RizbA is primarily a questionnaire, not a database. Firstly, because the image samples of contemporary art and amateur works collected so far are not necessarily representative for all types of artworks and not appropriate for all research questions. Secondly, RizbA's aim is to be a universal and open methodological tool that can be used on any sample of two-dimensional pictorial works on any research question it is appropriate for. Based on good to high values in inter-rater reliability in all previous validation studies, RizbA ratings can be considered stable and generalizable

among different rater samples. A further validation study using additional explanations of technical terms showed that even within raters without art expertise, good inter-rater agreement is given (Jerusalem, 2020). In practical terms, if we conducted two identical studies on the same image material with different rater samples, taken aside natural variation in data, the ratings would be alike, accurate and stable. Finally, *RizbA*'s focus does not rely on the raters' opinions, which are rather a method of gaining data. Images and their formal analysis by raters are the general unit of analysis here.

CONCLUSION

Although a final conclusion to the factors structure cannot be drawn yet, results are very promising. The questionnaire yields fair to high test quality regarding reliability and validity. After successfully validating *RizbA* on amateur and artist handmade two-dimensional pictorial works, its use can be recommended for both non-professional and professional contemporary art. Being a universal tool for quantitative formal picture analysis, it complements current research methodology in art and science. Future studies in art psychology, creativity research, and empirical aesthetics can go beyond focusing solely on psychological correlates. By the inclusion of a reliable measurement of picture analysis, art is given greater weight in art psychology. Future research will focus on a validation on other more diverse samples regarding image material and raters. A further goal is getting insight in the factors structure, perhaps revealing a Big Eight of visual art.

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APPENDIX

Ethics approval

The authors received a positive vote of the Ethics Committee for Creative Arts Therapies at the Nürtingen-Geislingen University, Germany (Reference number 19C27J101W).

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Abbreviations

CFA Confirmatory factor analysis

PCA Principal component analysis

PhP Hypertext Preprocessor

RizbA Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works)

Additional Material

RizbA Original version

Table 7
RizbA: Original German version

No.	Item
1	Das Bild enthält zeichnerische Elemente
2	Das Bild enthält malerische Elemente
3	Die Darstellungsweise ist gegenständlich
4	Die Darstellungsweise ist abstrakt
5	Der Farbauftrag ist pastos
6	Die vorherrschende Farbgebung ist leuchtend
7	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend reine Farben
8	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend Mischfarben (Sekundärfarben)
9	Im Bild sind Komplementärkontraste vorhanden
10	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend organisch
11	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend geometrisch
12	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend gebogen
13	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend eckig
14	Das Bild enthält unbearbeitete Flächen
15	Das Bild wirkt tief
16	Das Bild ist perspektivisch
17	Das Bild ist frei von Perspektive (aperspektivisch)
18	Das Bild ist unruhig
19	Das Bild ist wild
20	Die Gesamtkomposition ist senkrecht angelegt
21	Die Gesamtkomposition ist waagrecht angelegt
22	Die Gesamtkomposition ist diagonal angelegt
23	Die Gesamtkomposition ist flächendeckend ohne Hauptmotiv (All-Over-Structure)
24	Das Bild wirkt diffus
25	Das Bild wirkt präzise, exakt
26	Das Bild wirkt harmonisch

Open Data and Methodology

The list of artworks including metadata, the *SoSci Survey* structure (project structure, PHP code for randomization and drawing, values, variables), as well as the syntax for data structuring (Excel VBA macros) and statistical analysis (SPSS syntax) are available under a CC-BY 4.0 license at Open Science Framework via https://osf.io/p84xw/?view_only=8caa81c8ac954bb9ac7f56c4e5d2fe50.

A paper-pencil-version of the current original German version of *RizbA* questionnaire is available under a CC-BY 4.0 license at Zenodo:

Schoch, K. (2020, April 24). Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (RizbA): Fragebogen mit Erläuterungen in deutscher Sprache [Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA): Questionnaire with explanatory notes in German language]. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530859>

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**Empirics vs. art theory:
Exploring a factor structure of pictorial expression
based on contemporary artworks**

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Abstract

The RizbA scale combines psychometrics and art theory and enables a measurement of pictorial expression. This study explores its factor structure and a potential gap between theory and empirics. A sample of 275 pictorial works by artists and nonprofessionals was rated by 179 art experts. Three CFA path models were specified: models A and B based on the empirical results of previous studies, C on the theory of the initial study. Model C was additionally tested on a combined dataset. A and B did not converge, C was associated with fit indices as follows: RSMEA = .122, CFI = .712, TLI = .679, SRMR = .135, for the combined dataset: RSMEA = .086, CFI = .740, TLI = .696, SRMR = .084. Only model C partly suggests an acceptable fit. The results speak to a methodological gap between empirics and theory, that might be solved by a postdisciplinary measurement model.

Keywords: art theory, confirmatory factor analysis, formal picture analysis, pictorial expression, visual art

Introduction

Psychological research on visual art has a long tradition. Surprisingly, however, until now formal elements of artworks have received little attention in quantitative research. Another peculiarity is that most studies deal with historical art, but seldom with contemporary works. This is even more striking since arts and humanities provide a range of methods to analyze artworks including contemporary art (e.g., Bockemühl, 1989; Huber, 2005; Kemp, 1988; Panofsky, 2006). In order to do justice to the arts, approaches from empirical sciences and humanities will need to move towards becoming more transdisciplinarily connected and share their discourses, and this study contributes to that process.

As already discussed in detail (Schoch et al., 2017; Schoch & Ostermann, 2020, 2021, May 4), RizbA (Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works) fills the severe lack of a quantitative, reliable and validated instrument for conducting a detailed formal analysis of artworks, that allows inferential statistics and is applicable to all sorts of two-dimensional pictorial works.

The rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA)

RizbA is an Open Methodology tool. The 26-item questionnaire (see Table 1) refers to a formal picture analysis and focuses on a maximization of objectivity. The instrument uses a six-point Likert-scale, which is discretely scaled and verbally anchored in shades of agreement (0 = *strongly disagree* to 5 = *strongly agree*). Raters receive a brief instruction to process the presented image: They are asked to focus on the pre-dominant overall expression and no single details, while being reminded that there is no right or wrong, but only their evaluation. Explanatory notes explaining art terminology ensure that the questionnaire remains applicable and reliable (Jerusalem, 2020, February 20) not only to art experts, but also to experts from other domains.

Table 1*Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA)*

No.	Item*
1	The picture includes graphic elements
2	The picture includes pictorial elements
3	The manner of representation is concrete
4	The manner of representation is abstract
5	The color application is pastose
6	The predominant coloring is vibrant
7	In the picture primary colors are prevalent
8	In the picture mixed colors (secondary colors) are prevalent
9	In the picture there are complementary contrasts
10	In the picture organic shapes are prevalent
11	In the picture geometric shapes are prevalent
12	The layout of the line is predominantly curved
13	The layout of the line is predominantly angled
14	The picture includes unworked areas
15	The picture appears to be deep
16	The picture is perspectival
17	The picture is without perspective (aperspectival)
18	The picture is restless
19	The picture is wild
20	The global composition is laid out vertically
21	The global composition is laid out horizontally
22	The global composition is laid out diagonally
23	The global composition is laid out area-wide without a main subject (All-Over-Structure)
24	The picture appears to be diffuse
25	The picture appears to be precise, accurate
26	The picture appears to be harmonic

* = original German version see additional material

Pictorial expression

Defining the nomological network, RizbA assesses the construct of pictorial expression, which is defined as artistic creations in the form of a picture. It focuses on the concept of a formal picture analysis (Streb, 1984; Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003) originating from the humanities and the arts. It analyzes formal aspects, such as representation, color, spatiality, shaping, pictorial elements and composition, which can be found across art literature (e.g. Arnheim, 2013; Bauer, 1996; Kandinsky, 1955; Meyer, 2011; Vollmar, 2008). This approach is rooted in the tradition of phenomenological picture analysis (Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003, 2004). In art therapy, the phenomenological method consists of attempting attentive viewing and describing as precisely as possible, what is seen (Betensky, 1991). The viewer seeks to overcome accidental judgement, preconception and association (Streb, 1984). The relevant systemic level is the pictorial representation consciously omitting the picture reference, e.g. knowledge,

associations, emotions (Huber, 2005). It focuses on visual presentation (Wiesing, 2005) leaving out the colonializing view of unintentional identification of objects (Marotzki & Stoetzer, 2006). It is limited to a detailed but classical conception of images, not taking into account the creation process (Uzelac, 1998). The test does not judge the creator's achievement or mastery and is distinct from aesthetic appreciation. It is neither evaluative nor interpretative nor projective but aims for a value-free description of formal elements. A rater training or sample images for certain characteristics are deliberately dispensed with to avoid a manipulation of judgement.

Previous research

So far three main validation studies have been conducted using randomized online surveys, in which image samples were rated by experts from visual art disciplines. Focusing on statistical quality criteria, these studies successfully validated the questionnaire in terms of item difficulty, capacity for differentiation, test-retest and inter-rater reliability. Results indicate good to high reliabilities and allow a generalizability to professional and nonprofessional contemporary art. Still, the question of the factor structure remained partly unsolved.

In an initial study (Schoch et al., 2017), RizbA was constructed based on a theoretical framework of content areas and empirically tested on a small heterogeneous sample of pictorial works by nonprofessionals. A pool of 113 items (Schoch, 2014, February 25) was gathered based on art literature, compendia (e.g., Arnheim, 2013; Kandinsky, 1955; Meyer, 2011; Vollmar, 2008) and art therapeutic questionnaires (e.g., Eber et al., 1998; Elbing & Hacking, 2001; Hacking et al., 1996; Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2004). Based on statistical quality criteria it was narrowed down to 26 items. The underlying measurement model was thought of in terms of a formative model. Pictorial expression was – and still is – not seen as a one-dimensional latent variable, but rather a profile of characteristics which complement to the construct. Since there was no quantitative data on formal image analysis by then, *a priori* creating a construct

map was hardly possible. A second study (Schoch & Ostermann, 2021, May 4) validated the 26-item version on a sample of 294 pictorial works by nonprofessionals from the 21st century. . A principal component analysis (PCA) resulted in eight factors (see Table 2). In a third study, the instrument was validated on a sample of 318 works dated to the 21st century by professional artists (Schoch & Ostermann, 2020). A PCA also resulted in eight factors which differed slightly from the study (see Table 2).

Seen across the studies, the theoretical framework of content areas from the first study and the PCA results from the second and the third studies differed substantially. The validation studies included iterative discussion processes on art theory with expert groups. Those came to the intriguing conclusion that the empirical PCA solutions do not appropriately reflect art-theoretical categories.

Goal of this study

Previous studies computed a PCA as an exploratory procedure for data reduction to derive a number of components that account for the variability in measures (DeCoster, 1998). This study makes a further inquiry into an underlying factor structure. With reference to the previous three studies, three different models are hypothesized, specified and empirically tested on another dataset – either based on empirical results or art theory. As a hypothesis-testing procedure, a CFA was conducted to test if there is a sufficient model fit between each hypothesized model and the data (Moosbrugger & Kelava, 2007; Suhr, 2005, 2006). To examine the factors' quality, statistical criteria such as descriptive statistics, normal distribution, internal consistency and intercorrelations were calculated.

Material and methods

Pictorial material

Referring to previous studies and a *ceteris paribus* assumption, the pictorial stimulus material consisted of contemporary pictorial works by professional artists and nonprofessionals. The

required sample size of images was *a priori* calculated based on statistical guidelines. The sample size regarding images is oriented towards Guadagnoli and Velicer (1988) as well as Osborne and Costello (2009), in which a subject to item ratio of at least 10:1 is proposed. As a consequence, a minimum sample size of at least 260 images was calculated to be sufficient for the study.

Artworks by professional artists

The image sample of visual artworks by professional artists was generated using WikiArt (2021) images under a Creative Commons License. For the systematic search and retrieval of images and metadata, the Open Source API for WikiArt (2021) and WikiArt Retriever (Davis, 2018) were used. The data was retrieved in June 2020.

The inclusion criteria for images were determined analogously to the third study as follows: Firstly, as a criterion for being contemporary, a creation date of between 2018 and 2020 had to be specified in the metadata. The WikiArt Retriever (Davis, 2018) code was accordingly modified to retrieve only these works. Secondly, only handmade techniques such as drawings, paintings, collages and mixed techniques were used. Thirdly, the image had to comprise a complete view. Images showing only a detail of an artwork or an entire exhibition space displaying the artwork were excluded. The resulting sample was reduced to one image per artist, choosing the most recent work of that artist. If several works were dated to the same year, the first one, following alphabetical order was selected.

The final sample of professional contemporary artworks consisted of 143 images. Images, in which a background around the actual work was to be seen, were edited using Photos for MacOS (Apple, 2020) and cropped down to show solely the artwork.

Artworks by nonprofessionals

Nonprofessional artworks were collected via a public call, in which nonprofessionals were invited to digitally submit their works. The data was collected during 2020.

Inclusion criteria were determined as follows: Firstly, participants were asked to participate only if they had no professional education in visual arts or previous experience of studying a subject related to visual arts. Secondly, referring to previous studies and *a ceteris paribus* assumption only handmade techniques such as drawings, paintings, collages and mixed techniques were included.

The call was disseminated via a website, email, social media and particularly in specific Facebook groups with potential suitable participants. For finding such groups, the keywords *visual art* were searched in various languages using DeepL (2020) translator. Additionally, a large set of other keywords were used in English and German language, such as *amateur art, hobby art, painting, drawing, international art, Black art/ists, African American art/ists, native American art/ists, Korean art/ists, Armenian art/ists, Vietnamese art/ists, indigenous art/ists, Asian art/ists, Arabic art/ists, Persian art/ists, Islamic art/ists, Indian art/ists, Zambian art/ists, South African art/ists* etc.

Potential participants could anonymously submit their image via an upload form using Wordpress (2020) and the plugin Contact Form 7 (Miyoshi, 2020). The instructions were as follows: First, participants were invited to create a two-dimensional picture. They could also use a picture they had already created. Participants could decide on material and size. It was noted that making a submission was not a painting competition and not about creating a particularly "beautiful" picture, but simply about creating. Second, they were asked to take a photo of the picture using a smartphone or digital camera and were provided with tips and photo examples for taking a high-quality picture. Third, they were invited to upload their photo accompanied with information about the picture's size and artistic material, demographic data and informed consent.

A total of 139 images were gathered this way. Seven of these were excluded due to not fitting the inclusion criteria or lacking image quality (e.g., resolution, sharpness, picture section). The

final sample consisted of 132 images by 132 nonprofessionals (105 female, 25 male, 2 diverse) from 21 to 79 years old ($M = 45.80$, $SD = 15.12$) with a highest educational qualification ranging from secondary school to PhD. Where necessary, images were edited using MacOS (Apple, 2020) and the Open Source image editor Gimp (Neumann, 2020). Those, in which a background around the actual work was visible, were cropped down to solely the artwork. Distorted perspective due to a skewed photography was adjusted. A few were brightened up.

Final image sample

The final sample ($N = 275$) consists of 143 contemporary artworks by professional artists and 132 pictorial works by nonprofessionals. Both subsamples include international image material from different geographic areas.

Study

Study design

An online study design was chosen using SoSci Survey (Leiner, 2018) with the additional use of PHP elements. In this survey, experts with a professional training related to visual art were asked to rate images using RizbA items. Each rater was presented with six images, randomly chosen from the image sample. Raters were recruited via email, websites and social media. Among others, the call was posted in 132 social media groups and sent via email to 123 universities and 47 associations in Germany, Austria and Switzerland. The latter were contacted and their professional staff, students and associates were invited to participate and disseminate the call. No rater training was conducted. As an incentive, vouchers were raffled among participants.

Raters

As a criterion for inclusion and in order to ensure raters were aware of the appropriate terminology, only professionals who had an academic degree related to visual art, or were students who had been studying an art-related subject for at least one year were requested to

participate. Relevant disciplines included art history, art pedagogy, visual art, art therapy, design, graphic design, art sciences, image sciences, restoration and others. Regarding the sample size of raters Walter et al. (1998) recommend two or three observations per subject, given $\alpha = .05$ and a required reliability of at least .40. Based on these parameters the current study aimed at obtaining three raters per picture. Taking into account that each rater had to process six images, this led to an *a priori* calculated sample size of at least 138 raters.

Procedure

All images were reduced to a file size of 21-243 KB using Apple Photos software to adjust them to SoSci Survey specifications. In the online survey, raters were introduced to the scale and asked to rate each picture consecutively presented to them using all 26 items. For each rater, six images were randomly, successively drawn from a pot, without putting them back. When all the images from the entire picture sample had been rated once, the process started again. The order in which the items were presented was randomized between subjects. Raters could not skip items but were obliged to answer all questions in order to proceed. At the end raters were asked if they had completed the questionnaire carefully.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analyzed using R version 4.0.3 and R Studio version 1.3.1093 including the packages psych (Revelle, 2016), readxl (Wickham & Jennifer Bryan, 2013), car (Fox et al., 2019), lavaan (Rosseel, 2020), pbivnorm (Genz & Kenkel, 2015), and semPlot (Epskamp et al., 2019). Only complete datasets were used, in which all six images presented were fully processed. Data from prematurely terminated surveys or from raters who stated that they had not completed the questionnaire carefully were excluded. Because each rater assessed only six images out of the entire collection, the dataset inherently included a large number of empty cells. For analyses regarding the items and factors, subjects were therefore merged to new,

generic combined raters. Descriptive statistics were calculated for the sample of raters in terms of demographic variables, such as self-identified gender, age and art-related qualification.

Three different path models were specified as hypothetical models. Items were accordingly assigned to the factors (see Table 2):

Model A is empirically based on the second study (Schoch & Ostermann, 2021, May 4) (Schoch & Ostermann, 2021, May 4) resembling the factor structure from the PCA at T1. Items with negative factor loadings were reversed in the model.

Model B is empirically based on the third study (Schoch & Ostermann, 2020) resembling the factor structure from the PCA at T1. Items with negative factor loadings were reversed in the model.

Model C is theoretically-based on the initial study (Schoch et al., 2017) and resembles the framework of content areas that was *a priori* used for compiling the initial item pool. In comparison to the content areas (*representation, color, shape, space, motion, composition, expression*) the factor labels were adjusted slightly (see Table 2) to reflect the insights gained by expert group evaluations on the tool. No items were reversed.

For each factor of each model the following analyses were conducted: Descriptive statistics and Shapiro-Wilk normality test and Cronbach's alpha were computed. For the latter interpretation was based on Gliem and Gliem (2003) describing an alpha of .80 as a reasonable goal and George and Mallery (2003) suggesting the following rules of thumb: $\geq .90$ excellent, $\geq .80$ good, $\geq .70$ acceptable, $\geq .60$ questionable, $\geq .50$ poor, and $< .50$ unacceptable. For each model, Pearson product moment correlations between factors were calculated and interpreted based on the usual conventions: .10 small, .30 medium, and .50 large (Cohen, 1992). For inferential statistics the α level was *a priori* defined to be .05.

For each model a CFA was conducted using the model syntax by Rosseel (2021). With the factors being latent variables in the regression formula, they were defined by listing their manifest indicators, the items they are hypothesized to be measured by. For each factor in models A and B the items were ordered from highest to lowest factor loading, based on previous PCA results. As recommended by Li (2016) when the normality assumption is slightly or moderately violated, the robust maximum likelihood estimator (MLR) with robust standard errors and a Satorra-Bentler scaled test statistic (Rosseel, 2021) was used.

For model C an additional CFA was computed on a combined dataset of both the current and the two previous studies, resulting in a total of 894 images rated with RizbA. Models A and B were not tested on the previous data, since this would result in a deceptively optimistic overfitting (Fokkema & Greiff, 2017) and be tautological.

The adequacy of models fit was evaluated using indices as recommended in the corresponding literature (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Lorenzo-Seva & Ten Berge, 2006; Moosbrugger & Kelava, 2007; Parry, 2017; Sen et al., 2014; Suhr, 2006; Tucker & Lewis, 1973): χ^2 statistics in relation to the degrees of freedom (*df*), the comparative fit index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), the root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA), and the standardized root-mean-square residual (SRMR). Due to the normality assumption being slightly violated for some factors, the robust version of these indices was used.

We oriented towards the following recommendations on cutoff values to be interpreted as a fit between the hypothesized model and the observed data: Moosbrugger and Kelava (2007) recommend, that χ^2/df values between .000 - 2.00 suggest a good and those between 2.01 and 3.00 an acceptable fit. CFI values between .970 and 1.00 imply a good and those between .950 and .969 an acceptable fit. RMSEA values between .000 and .050 can be interpreted as a good, values between .510 and .800 as an acceptable fit. Hu and Bentler (1999) recommend for the ML method cutoff values $\geq .95$ for CFI and TLI, $\leq .06$ for RMSEA – according to Shi et al.

(2019) a RSMEA $\geq .10$ is beyond consideration – and close to .08 for SRMR. Concerning TLI Lorenzo-Seva and Ten Berge (2006) suggest, that values in a range of .85 - .94 correspond to a fair similarity, while values $\geq .95$ imply that the two components compared can be considered equal.

Results

Raters

A total of 184 raters finished the survey. Data from one rater was excluded from the analysis after they stated that they had not filled out the survey carefully. Data from four more raters were excluded, because they did not meet the inclusion criteria of expertise. The final sample of valid raters consists of 179 experts (159 female, 16 male, 4 diverse) between 22 and 72 years ($M = 37.59$, $SD = 12.51$). All of them have an academic degree in an art-related subject (75.42 %) or are at least in their second year of study (24.58 %). The disciplines include art therapy (31.84 %), art education (15.64 %), art history (13.41 %), fine arts (8.94 %), art science (5.59 %), graphic design (5.59 %), restoration (5.03 %), design (3.35 %), and others (10.61 %). Each picture is rated by 0 to 7 raters ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 1.39$). One nonprofessional's artwork was unrated and therefore excluded from further analysis.

Factors

The descriptive statistics are reported in Table 3, Table 4, and Table 5. Shapiro-Wilk test yields significant p-values in six of eight factors in model A and B, and in four of seven in model C. Cronbach's alpha ranges between .39 and .91 (see Table 3, Table 4, Table 5). Intercorrelations between the factors are reported in Table 6, Table 7, and Table 8.

Table 2*Models A, B, and C: Assigned items*

Model A		Model B		Model C	
empirically based (Schoch & Ostermann, 2021, May 4)		empirically based Schoch and Ostermann (2020)		theory-based Schoch et al. (2017)	
Factor label	Items	Factor label	Items	Factor label	Items
<i>Picture effect</i>	18, 19, 24, 25 _r , 26 _r	<i>Picture effect</i>	18, 19, 24, 25 _r , 26 _r	<i>Representation</i>	1, 2, 3, 4, 5
<i>Spatiality</i>	15, 16, 17 _r	<i>Spatiality</i>	15, 16, 17 _r	<i>Color</i>	6, 7, 8, 9
<i>Shaping</i>	10, 11 _r , 12, 13 _r	<i>Shaping</i>	10, 11 _r , 12, 13 _r	<i>Shaping</i>	10, 11, 12, 13, 14
<i>Pictorial elements (drawing vs. painting)</i>	1, 2 _r , 5 _r , 14	<i>Pictorial elements (painting)</i>	2, 5, 7 _r , 8	<i>Spatiality</i>	15, 16, 17
		<i>Pictorial elements (drawing)</i>	1, 14, 22	<i>Motion</i>	18, 19
<i>Representation</i>	3 _r , 4, 22, 23	<i>Representation</i>	3 _r , 4, 23	<i>Composition</i>	20, 21, 22, 23
<i>Color intensity</i>	6, 9	<i>Color intensity</i>	6, 9	<i>Picture effect</i>	24, 25, 26
<i>Color mixture</i>	7 _r , 8				
<i>Composition</i>	20, 21 _r	<i>Composition</i>	20, 21 _r		

_r = reversed item with negative factor loading in the previous PCA

Table 3*Model A: Descriptive statistics, Shapiro-Wilk test and Cronbach's alpha*

Factor	Factor label	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	Shapiro-Wilk			Cronbach's α	
						<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	95% <i>CI</i>	
									<i>lower bound</i>	<i>upper bound</i>
1	<i>Picture effect</i>	2.15	0.81	0.40	4.60	0.99	.028	.88	.86	.90
2	<i>Spatiality</i>	2.56	1.06	0.00	4.89	0.99	.030	.91	.89	.91
3	<i>Shaping</i>	3.02	0.94	0.00	4.75	0.94	.000	.88	.86	.91
4	<i>Pictorial elements</i> <i>(drawing vs.</i> <i>painting)</i>	2.30	0.85	0.25	4.85	0.97	.000	.70	.64	.75
5	<i>Representation</i>	1.94	0.91	0.25	4.50	0.96	.000	.73	.69	.78
6	<i>Color intensity</i>	2.47	1.05	0.00	4.50	0.98	.001	.68	.61	.68
7	<i>Color mixture</i>	2.95	0.79	0.50	4.75	0.98	.000	.39	.25	.53
8	<i>Composition</i>	2.74	1.07	0.50	5.00	0.97	.000	.76	.71	.82

M = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, *Min* = minimum, *Max* = maximum, *W* = Shapiro-Wilk test statistic, *p* = p-value Shapiro-Wilk test, *r* = reliability coefficient Cronbach's alpha, *CI* = confidence interval

Table 4*Model B: Descriptive statistics, Shapiro-Wilk test and Cronbach's alpha*

Factor	Factor label	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	Shapiro-Wilk			Cronbach's α	
						<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	95% <i>CI</i>	
									<i>lower bound</i>	<i>upper bound</i>
1	<i>Picture effect</i>	2.15	0.81	0.40	4.60	0.99	.028	.88	.86	.90
2	<i>Spatiality</i>	2.56	1.06	0.00	4.89	0.99	.030	.91	.80	.93
3	<i>Shaping</i>	3.02	0.94	0.00	4.75	0.94	.000	.88	.86	.91
4	<i>Pictorial elements</i> <i>(painting)</i>	2.78	0.70	0.81	4.31	0.98	.000	.61	.54	.68
5	<i>Pictorial elements</i> <i>(drawing)</i>	3.04	0.79	0.17	4.00	1.00	.000	.39	.27	.51
6	<i>Representation</i>	2.01	1.19	0.00	4.67	0.93	.000	.88	.85	.90
7	<i>Color intensity</i>	2.47	1.05	0.00	4.50	0.98	.001	.68	.61	.76
8	<i>Composition</i>	2.74	1.07	0.50	5.00	0.97	.000	.76	.71	.82

M = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, *Min* = minimum, *Max* = maximum, *W* = Shapiro-Wilk test statistic, *p* = p-value Shapiro-Wilk test, *r* = reliability coefficient Cronbach's alpha, *CI* = confidence interval

Table 5*Model C: Descriptive statistics, Shapiro-Wilk test and Cronbach's alpha*

Factor	Factor label	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Min	Max	Shapiro-Wilk			Cronbach's α	
						<i>W</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	95% CI	
									lower bound	upper bound
1	<i>Representation</i>	2.66	0.42	0.42	1.00	0.99	.010	.63	.56	.63
2	<i>Color</i>	2.40	0.76	0.08	4.00	0.95	.000	.62	.55	.62
3	<i>Shaping</i>	2.14	0.40	0.93	3.24	1.00	.754	.77	.72	.77
4	<i>Spatiality</i>	2.33	0.40	0.38	1.33	0.99	.472	.91	.89	.91
5	<i>Motion</i>	2.18	1.02	0.00	5.00	0.99	.009	.92	.90	.92
6	<i>Composition</i>	1.98	0.41	0.25	3.19	0.98	.002	.49	.40	.49
7	<i>Picture effect</i>	2.53	0.38	1.00	3.67	0.99	.010	.75	.70	.75

M = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, Min = minimum, Max = maximum, *W* = Shapiro-Wilk test statistic, *p* = p-value Shapiro-Wilk test, *r* = reliability coefficient Cronbach's alpha, CI = confidence interval

Table 6*Model A: Pearson product moment correlations between factors*

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 <i>Picture effect</i>	–							
2 <i>Spatiality</i>	-.37**	–						
3 <i>Shaping</i>	-.05	.13	–					
4 <i>Pictorial elements (drawing vs. painting)</i>	-.05	-.18*	-.04	–				
5 <i>Representation</i>	.42**	-.46**	-.27**	-.16	–			
6 <i>Color intensity</i>	.09	.05	.03	-.43**	.12	–		
7 <i>Color mixture</i>	.02	.08	-.07	-.33**	.03	.00	–	
8 <i>Composition</i>	-.06	-.10	.06	.02	-.15	-.09	.02	–

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$ **Table 7***Model B: Pearson product moment correlations between factors*

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 <i>Picture effect</i>	–							
2 <i>Spatiality</i>	-.37**	–						
3 <i>Shaping</i>	-.05	.13*	–					
4 <i>Pictorial elements (painting)</i>	.06	.18*	.10	–				
5 <i>Pictorial elements (drawing)</i>	-.05	-.02*	.10	-.36**	–			
6 <i>Representation</i>	.45**	-.53**	-.27**	.02	-.22**	–		
7 <i>Color intensity</i>	.09	.05	.03	.25**	-.29**	.11	–	
8 <i>Composition</i>	-.06	-.10	.06	.02	-.04	-.11	-.09	–

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$ **Table 8***Model C: Pearson product moment correlations between factors*

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1 <i>Representation</i>	–						
2 <i>Color</i>	0.29	–					
3 <i>Shaping</i>	0.00	-0.17	–				
4 <i>Spatiality</i>	0.12	0.12	-0.17	–			
5 <i>Motion</i>	0.10	0.13	-0.02	-0.14	–		
6 <i>Composition</i>	0.01	0.18	-0.05	0.20	0.16	–	
7 <i>Picture effect</i>	-0.03	0.11	0.07	0.33	-0.30*	0.11	–

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$ **CFA**

Models A and B did not converge. Model C (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) revealed the following fit indices: $\chi^2 = 1299.752$, $df = 278$, $p = .000$, RMSEA = .122 (90% CI = .116, .129), CFI = .712, TLI = .679, SRMR = .135 and for the combined dataset of three studies as follows: $\chi^2 = 6860.824$, $df = 278$, $p = .000$, RMSEA = .086 (90% CI = .084, .088), CFI = .740, TLI = .696, SRMR = .084.

Figure 1 CFA Path model C with intercorrelations between factors

Discussion

Previous studies have aimed at exploring the underlying factor structure of RizbA. This paper aims to compare the existing two empirical-based PCA factor models with a theoretical model by means of CFA path models. We were able to show substantial differences between these

approaches. Below, some methodological aspects will be discussed, followed by a broader discussion from a content and art related perspective.

Rater sample size

Preceding validation studies on RizbA used a large number of 10 to 20 raters per image and resulted in sufficiently high inter-rater agreement and test-retest reliability. This study uses a smaller rater sample. This is both more economic and also sufficient. First, because the instrument has been proven to be reliable in terms of inter-rater agreement and test-retest reliability. Second, the current investigation concentrates on artistic stimulus material rather than on intersubjectivity.

Normal distribution

The Shapiro-Wilk test suggests a violation of normal distribution for several factors for each model. However, it is a conservative procedure and there is no theoretical reasoning as to why pictorial expression should not be normally distributed within a larger sample size. For example, model A's factors *shaping*, *pictorial elements (drawing vs. painting)*, *color intensity*, *color mixture*, and *composition* are not distributed normally in this sample. One reason might be that all images were created on purpose, with the knowledge that they would be shown to others. This applies to the professional artworks uploaded to WikiArt, but also for those willingly contributed by nonprofessionals. This might result in a tendency towards more colored or elaborately shaped pictures, while the representation is still balanced between abstract and representational and therefore normally distributed. For testing this rationale, random pictures could be included, e.g., images that are not even considered to be artworks such as scribbles on slips of paper.

Internal consistency

Models A and B provide better internal consistency within factors than model C. For model A Cronbach's alpha can be interpreted as excellent for the factor *spatiality*, good for *picture*

effect and *shaping*, and acceptable for *pictorial elements (drawing vs. painting)*, *representation* and *composition*. However, the reliability is to be seen questionable for *color intensity* and unacceptable for *color mixture*. Analogously, results from model B suggest excellent reliability for the factor *spatiality*. Also, it can be interpreted as good not only for *picture effect* and *shaping*, but also for *representation*. *Composition* yields acceptable, while *pictorial elements (painting)* and *color intensity* only show poor, and *pictorial elements (drawing)* even unacceptable reliability. Regarding model C, the factor *spatiality* again suggests excellent reliability along with *motion*. *Shaping* and *picture effect* are acceptable, *representation* and *color* questionable, while *composition* is unacceptable.

Intercorrelations

The following factors show intercorrelations: Within model A *spatiality* negatively correlates with *picture effect* and *pictorial elements (drawing vs. painting)*. Representation is related to *picture effect* and negatively to *spatiality* and *shaping*. *Color intensity* and *color mixture* both negatively correlate with *pictorial elements (drawing vs. painting)*. Within model B *spatiality* correlates with *shaping*, *pictorial elements (painting)*, and *pictorial elements (drawing)* as well as negatively with *picture effect*. Representation is related with a variety of other factors: with *picture effect* and negatively with *spatiality*, *shaping* and *pictorial elements (drawing)*. Also, *color intensity* is associated with *pictorial elements (painting)* and negatively with *pictorial elements (drawings)*, which correlates to a painting being more likely to be color intensive than a drawing. Within model C factors are less related. Only *picture effect* and *motion* show medium correlations.

Factor structure

Models A and B do not provide model fit indices. For model C all indices yield values beneath the cut-off points associated with an acceptable fit. Only when tested on the combined data of all three studies, does SRMR suggest an acceptable to good model fit. However, none of the

hypothesized models provides a factor model with a thoroughly good or acceptable fit – neither empirically nor theory-based. As an exploratory approach we conducted an *a posteriori* card sorting test with art experts to generate further theory-based models. When tested with a CFA they converged – in comparison to the empirically based models A and B – but still did not provide a good model fit. It can be assumed, that the theory-based models are more likely to fit than the empirically based models, based on PCAs. There are a number of possible reasons, which we will discuss below.

First, a sample of 275 observations (images) – 894 in case of the combined dataset – and 26 variables (items) might still not be large enough to map a factor structure, since CFA is a large sample procedure. According to Shi et al. (2019) a sample of 200 observations only provides a reasonable estimate for CFI and TLI when the number of observed variables is less than 30.

Second, the CFA do not reflect results of preceding PCAs although the sample consisted of a similar sample. This might be due to differences in the calculation of both procedures. Also, the PCA solutions suppressed factor loadings under .40. This is a common practice and if these solutions were stable, a similar structure might be found in the CFA. The fact that these models do not converge, could indicate that the solution is not stable across art. This suggests that measurement of pictorial expression is even more extensive and complicated than anticipated and there might not be a stable global solution.

Third, there is a methodical gap between empirics and theory when it comes to formal image analysis. Pictorial expression in terms of a formal image analysis might be an even more complex construct than assumed. It is possible that there is no underlying factor structure analogous to psychological constructs, such as personality or intelligence. Or possibly the underlying factor is not stable across a larger range of artworks. To gain insight, we have to dive deeper in the various perspectives on image analysis, of which the perspectives addressed below represent only a glimpse of the field.

One established method for image analysis is the *iconographic-iconological method*, which Panofsky (1978, 2006) abstracted to a theoretical model (Eberlein, 2008). It suggests three stages: First, the *pre-iconographic description* determines the primary or natural subject and identifies the objects presented in an image. It requires a rudimentary knowledge of style history as a corrective principle for understanding the image objects as an artistic motive. As an example Eberlein (2008) uses Friedrich Dürer's *Melencolia I*, which today might be interpreted as a grumpy angel in the midst of stuff; however familiarity with the basic art principles from 1514 would anticipate a personification and a symbolic meaning of the objects. Second, the *iconographic analysis*, which uses historical sources and type history to unveil underlying themes and ideas. Third, the *iconological interpretation* examines the actual meaning and content, instrumentalizing the time difference between artwork and interpreter. It refers to Ernst Cassirer's philosophy of symbolic forms, representing the idea that humans no longer live in a merely natural universe, but experience the world via language, myth or religion, and art. If we consider *pre-iconographic* description not only in motives but also in shapes, there is a parallel to RizbA. However, the *iconographic-iconological method* decrypts images based on historical contextualization, implying that an artwork can never be detached from its historical context. RizbA leaves aside all historical aspects of the epochs artworks stem from, which might be one missing piece of the big picture when measuring art.

Another missing piece might be argued from the perspective of a *reception aesthetics* approach (Kemp, 1988), which suggests that every artwork provides a receptive function. The way art encounters the viewer depends on the way the viewer approaches the art: responding and acknowledging the viewer's effort. Reception aesthetics is oriented towards the artwork and is in search of an implicit viewer, a viewer function in an artwork. Each image is addressed to someone, framing its recipient, and discloses two sorts of information: It speaks about its place and impact in society. And it speaks about itself. Consequently, reception aesthetics has (at least) three tasks: Firstly, it has to recognize the means by which the artwork gets in touch with

us and read them with regard to secondly, their social-historical, and thirdly, their actual aesthetic statement. In summary, recipient and artwork are not clinically pure and isolated entities. Although RizbA does not explicitly address internal psychological processes, the items summarized as *picture effect* refer to those. However, the described lack of pure constructs might be another note on a potential non-existence of a stable factor solution.

RizbA is initially based on the framework of *phenomenological image analysis* seeking to overcome judgement, preconception and association (Streb, 1984), while being aware that there is no such thing as absolute objectivity. It is rather a process of reflecting on one's own perceptions. Modern phenomenology goes back to Edmund Husserl and is interested in phenomena (things, objects) and how they present themselves as perceived experiences (Betensky, 1991). Husserl postulates that an artwork possesses an invisible space that belongs to the picture and is opposed to the space, that can be grasped by experience (Uzelac, 1998). The part of an artwork that cannot be grasped might be another missing piece that may not be objectively measurable.

Finally, Bockemühl (1989) argues that analogies of the artwork as sender and the eye as receiver are too simplistic. Art makes the flow of information rather complicated and denies a final statement. It creates a reality of its own, in which only the combination of the creator's hand and the creative power of the eye lead to the artwork, e.g., Mark Rothko's colorfield paintings that slowly arise by looking at them. An image is an open system, that never offers an exhaustive interpretation. We have no choice but to accept certain limits and that analysis only captures a part – even though it is indispensable – of artistic reality. When dealing with art, one seems to be pushed into subjectivism. There might only be one escape: reducing the statement of art to a pure informational level and excluding further questions that might be – how as (Bockemühl, 1989) drastically states it – non-scienceable.

Limitations

The professional art images were retrieved from WikiArt (2021), a shared knowledge database. Unfortunately the accompanying metadata lacks the artists' self-identified gender or other diversity indicators (Pacher-Nishikawa et al., 2021). Thus, it was not possible to compute demographics to ensure heterogeneity and diversity of the image sample. The works by nonprofessionals were gathered via a call using social media. Open Science advocates justifiably criticize commercial platforms' non-transparent algorithms and problematic data protection. Nevertheless, in this study Facebook groups were used since they offer an efficient way to reach specific target groups. The search mechanisms do not provide a systematic search function. Its results are biased toward the user's language and region, hence towards English and German speakers.

In the online survey image sizes were rather small, in order to meet the SoSci Survey's (Leiner, 2018) maximum upload capacity and to make sure images load fast enough. Also, the raters viewed the images on their own devices, which might result in a different display of color and resolution. Using a higher resolution, a different rating experience may be expected, especially when original works instead of digital copies are used. This is particularly true if we are to follow art theories (e.g., Panofsky, 1978; Panofsky, 2006), who claim that an artwork cannot be completely comprehensible if it is detached from its context. Due to the large number of images that needed to be rated, this point was waived.

For one of the nonprofessional artworks, data is missing. This lack of ratings is due to the fact that only complete datasets were used and none of the experts, who rated this particular image finished the survey. However, it can be assumed that these values are missing at random and the sample size is still within sufficient size.

As with other art psychology research, this approach includes features of Eurocentrism and Americanism, in particular in three aspects: underlying art theory, available image material and

raters. First, the underlying theory on image analysis stems from European theorists and a particular way of thinking. Although these paradigms have been dominant in art history, they are by no means the only valid perspectives on art. Second, WikiArt (2021) provides a variety of international professional art, follows a knowledge equity policy and allows not only established institution to contribute, but also the public (Marengo et al., 2017). Nevertheless, with a marginalization of other artists, the overall ratio of images still overrepresents European and Northern American artists. Within the sample of nonprofessional artworks, we aimed for an international sample. But the call in English and German must be seen as a barrier to participation for people who speak neither nor. Third, the current questionnaire and survey were in German. Thus, the majority of experts stemmed from Germany, Austria or Switzerland.

Implications

As the first reliable, validated measurement RizbA allows researchers to not only capture psychological and physiological variables, but also the artwork itself. For example, which formal elements make viewers appreciate art? Is it representation, color mixture, or shaping? Is it easier for an audience distant from art to appreciate Van Gogh's works, rather than connecting to contemporary art by Firelei Báez? Since there are correlations between art preferences, thinking styles and personality (Gridley, 2006, 2013; Silvia & Nusbaum, 2011) these could be investigated in more depth. For example, an attitude of openness to experience positively correlates with a liking for abstract art (Gridley, 2013). But are individuals with higher scores on openness also more likely to create abstract art, when given the opportunity? More examples of how RizbA enhances art psychological methodology is extensively discussed in previous publications (e.g., Schoch et al., 2017; Schoch & Ostermann, 2020, 2021, May 4). However, besides offering a reliable measurement, no stable factor solution for pictorial expression could be found.

Bockemühl (1989) cites a tilt figure as an example for various perspectives on one and the same object, which cannot be perceived simultaneously. He states that aesthetics, if seen as a practical category, cannot be dealt with solely by logic. This might also be an analogy to analyzing art: It is highly ambiguous, refers to various levels and offers numerous perspectives of analysis. Perhaps a model simplification, as used in quantitative research alone is insufficient to capture artworks.

Future research

First of all, the theory-based model C should be tested on an even larger dataset of several thousands of images, in order to discover whether a stable solution can be found. Moreover, further postdisciplinary research is needed to evolve a larger theoretical model of image analysis that does justice to art. Finding substantial differences between theory and empirics would fuel the discourse between arts, humanities and science described by Mersch (2019) and other theorists. Only by bringing those perspectives together, might we one day be able to empirically and globally capture art.

A next step is validating the English translation of the questionnaire to provide a reliable scale. Other language versions could be translated and validated as well. This would lay the foundation to recruit raters and data from other regions and contexts in order to put the Eurocentric view into perspective. Further validation of other image samples should be pursued, such as non-handmade techniques, images created by children and adolescents and in particular by creators from all geographical regions and origins. Further studies could be multi-centered, collaborating with experts from different regions adding a critical view on Eurocentrism (Mosquera, 1992). Other approaches on art should be included in research on image analysis, such as from Africa, Asia, Oceania and Southern America, not in colonial continuities, but as equally valid points of view. Going further, those future research projects should not only

include academic theories on how to analyze art, but also knowledge, that has traditionally been excluded from previous research, such as emic indigenous perspectives of art.

Conclusion

A reliable intersubjective measurement of pictorial expression is possible using RizbA. However, no stable factor structure with an acceptable model fit throughout could be found. Comparing the models, model A and B yield higher internal consistencies than model C. The factors of model C correlate less with each other than those of model A and B. Nevertheless, model C is the only one with a converging model during a CFA that might provide a good model fit within a larger image sample. It may just as well be, that unlike inherent psychological variables, for the construction of pictorial expression there is no stable factor structure that is globally valid over all sorts and levels of art. Art is highly ambiguous, refers to various levels and offers numerous perspectives of analysis. Perhaps a model simplification, as we use it in quantitative empirics alone, is insufficient. Further post-disciplinary research is needed to evolve a larger theoretical model of image analysis that does justice to the subject. Only by this might we one day be able to globally capture art.

Studies show that RizbA is able to reliably measure pictorial expression. Going a step further this study revealed intriguing difference between empirics and art theory. Leder et al. (2012) might be right – at least for today’s perspective – when they stated that art is a mysterious aspect of human experience. In short: It’s complicated and yet a promising starting point for future research on art that should think postdisciplinarily.

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Appendix

Abbreviations

API	Application programming interface
CFA	Confirmatory factor analysis
CFI	Comparative fit index
<i>df</i>	Degrees of freedom
GLAM	Galleries, libraries, archives, museums
MLR	Robust maximum likelihood estimator
PCA	Principal component analysis
PHP	PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor
RizbA	Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works)
RMSEA	Root mean square error of approximation
SRMR	standardized root-mean-square residual
TLI	Tucker-Lewis Index

Additional Material

All material is available under a CC-BY 4.0 license as Open Data (image sample, metadata, ratings) and Open Methodology (SoSci Survey structure including PHP code for randomization and drawing, WordPress plugin Contact Form 7 code, R script) via Open Science Framework: https://osf.io/jnz67/?view_only=cd59189930484270aaa1f83017bee7e0

A paper-pencil-version version of RizbA is available as Open Methodology under a CC-BY 4.0 license:

Schoch, K. (2020, April 24). *Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (RizbA): Fragebogen mit Erläuterungen in deutscher Sprache* [Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA): Questionnaire with explanatory notes in German]. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3765221

Table 9

RizbA original German version

No.	Item
1	Das Bild enthält zeichnerische Elemente
2	Das Bild enthält malerische Elemente
3	Die Darstellungsweise ist gegenständlich
4	Die Darstellungsweise ist abstrakt
5	Der Farbauftrag ist pastos
6	Die vorherrschende Farbgebung ist leuchtend
7	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend reine Farben
8	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend Mischfarben (Sekundärfarben)
9	Im Bild sind Komplementärkontraste vorhanden
10	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend organisch
11	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend geometrisch
12	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend gebogen
13	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend eckig
14	Das Bild enthält unbearbeitete Flächen
15	Das Bild wirkt tief
16	Das Bild ist perspektivisch
17	Das Bild ist frei von Perspektive (aperspektivisch)
18	Das Bild ist unruhig
19	Das Bild ist wild
20	Die Gesamtkomposition ist senkrecht angelegt
21	Die Gesamtkomposition ist waagrecht angelegt
22	Die Gesamtkomposition ist diagonal angelegt
23	Die Gesamtkomposition ist flächendeckend ohne Hauptmotiv (All-Over-Structure)
24	Das Bild wirkt diffus
25	Das Bild wirkt präzise, exakt
26	Das Bild wirkt harmonisch

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE RATERS: NEURAL NETWORKS FOR RATING PICTORIAL EXPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Previous studies on classification of fine art show that features of paintings can be captured and categorized using machine learning approaches. This progress can also benefit art psychology by facilitating data collection on artworks without the need to recruit experts as raters. In this study a machine learning approach is used to predict the ratings of RizbA, a Ratinstrument for two-dimensional pictorial works. Based on a pre-trained model, the algorithm was fine-tuned via transfer learning on 886 pictorial works by contemporary professional artists and non-professionals. As quality criterion, artificial intelligence raters (ART) are compared with generic raters (GR) created from the real human expert raters, using error rate and Mean Squared Error. ART ratings have been found to have the same error range as randomly chosen human ratings. Therefore, they can be seen as equivalent to real human expert raters for almost all items in RizbA. Further training with more data will close the gap to the human raters on all items.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence raters; Machine learning; Neural nets; Pictorial expression; Visual art.

The last decade has been marked by advances in digitization, artificial intelligence, and big data. Progress in these fields stems mainly from the huge amount of computational capacity that is available in big computing clusters. These technologies are now finding their way into new fields. Many online collections of artworks have been created in the past decades with detailed annotations from art experts comprising genre, subject, style, technique, artist etc. They can be used to train machine learning algorithms to automate these categorization tasks and annotate further image catalogues (Cetinic et al., 2018; Santos et al., 2021).

The breakthrough in computer vision happened in 2012 (Krizhevsky et al., 2012). It opened up new possibilities to use the algorithms for a range of classification tasks, thanks to the Open Source availability of the pre-trained deep learning neural nets. They are applicable for comparatively small amounts of annotated training data and require relatively little computational power using the transfer learning approach (Razavian et al., 2014; Rodriguez et al., 2018; Sarkar et al., 2018). To date, this progress has been mainly used for digitization in art history and art science (e.g., Banerji & Sinha, 2016; Cetinic et al., 2018, 2020; Hua et al., 2020; Madhu et al., 2019), but can also benefit and advance art psychological research and documentation (Amirshahi et al., 2014; Castro et al., 2014).

In this work a machine learning approach is used to predict the ratings of the Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA; Schoch, 2020, April 24; Schoch et al., 2017), an art psychological questionnaire measuring pictorial expression. Its goal is to model and train different neural nets for each item of the rating scale. To compare the different artificial intelligence raters (ART), generic raters (GR) are built up from real human expert raters of the original training data stemming from previous validation studies on RizbA (Schoch & Ostermann, 2020, 2021, July 13, 2022). To evaluate the results, we compare the different ARTs with different GRs with respect to error rate and Mean Squared Error (MSE).

The resulting application can be used for image analysis in art-related research and documentation, such as art psychology. It facilitates various possibilities for inquiries related to visual art that involve large amounts of numeric measurements of images. Its application allows a relatively easy rating experience without expert raters having to go through the tedious process of manually rating 26 items per picture. It makes research and documentation more efficient while garnering large sample sizes and retaining statistical power.

PREVIOUS RESEARCH

The Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA)

RizbA is a 26-item questionnaire referring to formal picture analysis (Streb, 1984; Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003). The scale assesses pictorial

expression, which is defined as artistic creation in the form of a picture, whereby aiming for a maximization of objectivity. The instrument focuses on the concept of a formal picture analysis (Bauer, 1996) analyzing formal aspects like representation, color, shaping, spatiality, motion, composition, and expression which can be found across art literature (e.g., Arnheim, 2000; Bauer, 1996; Kandinsky, 1955; Meyer, 2011; Vollmar, 2008). This approach is rooted in the tradition of phenomenological picture analysis (Betensky, 1991; Stuhler-Bauer & Elbing, 2003, 2004), seeking to overcome accidental judgement, preconception, and association (Streb, 1984).

The scale (see Table 1) uses a six-point Likert scale, which is discretely scaled and verbally anchored in shades of agreement (0 = *strongly disagree*, 5 = *strongly agree*). Raters using the questionnaire receive a brief instruction to rate the presented image using the RizbA questionnaire. They are asked to focus on the predominant overall expression of a picture and no single details, while endorsing there is no right or wrong, but only their evaluation.

Table 1

<i>RizbA items: English translation and original German version.</i>		
No.	English translation	Original version
1	The picture includes graphic elements	Das Bild enthält zeichnerische Elemente
2	The picture includes pictorial elements	Das Bild enthält malerische Elemente
3	The manner of representation is concrete	Die Darstellungsweise ist gegenständlich
4	The manner of representation is abstract	Die Darstellungsweise ist abstrakt
5	The color application is pastose	Der Farbauftrag ist pastos
6	The predominant coloring is vibrant	Die vorherrschende Farbgebung ist leuchtend
7	In the picture primary colors are prevalent	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend reine Farben

<i>RizbA items: English translation and original German version.</i>		
8	In the picture mixed colors (secondary colors) are prevalent	Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend Mischfarben (Sekundärfarben)
9	In the picture there are complementary contrasts	Im Bild sind Komplementärkontraste vorhanden
10	In the picture organic shapes are prevalent	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend organisch
11	In the picture geometric shapes are prevalent	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend geometrisch
12	The layout of the line is predominantly curved	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend gebogen
13	The layout of the line is predominantly angled	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend gebogen
14	The picture includes unworked areas	Das Bild enthält unbearbeitete Flächen
15	The picture appears to be deep	Das Bild wirkt tief
16	The picture is perspectival	Das Bild ist perspektivisch
17	The picture is without perspective (aperspectival)	Das Bild ist frei von Perspektive (aperspektivisch)
18	The picture is restless	Das Bild ist unruhig
19	The picture is wild	Das Bild ist wild

<i>RizbA items: English translation and original German version.</i>		
20	The global composition is laid out vertically	Die Gesamtkomposition ist senkrecht angelegt
21	The global composition is laid out horizontally	Die Gesamtkomposition ist waagrecht angelegt
22	The global composition is laid out diagonally	Die Gesamtkomposition ist diagonal angelegt
23	The global composition is laid out area-wide without a main subject (All-Over-Structure)	Die Gesamtkomposition ist flächendeckend ohne Hauptmotiv (All-Over-Structure)
24	The picture appears to be diffuse	Das Bild wirkt diffus
25	The picture appears to be precise, accurate	Das Bild wirkt präzise, exakt
26	The picture appears to be harmonic	Das Bild wirkt harmonisch

RizbA enables a reliable quantitative capture of artworks and is validated for use on two-dimensional pictorial works such as sketches, drawings, paintings, collages, and mixed techniques. It allows a more detailed examination of psychological correlates of art, such as aesthetic appreciation, personality, or clinical diagnoses. As thoroughly discussed in previous literature (Schoch & Ostermann, 2020) it can be used for a variety of art psychological applications related to art reception, aesthetic appreciation, artmaking, and creativity, in both practice and research.

The test was developed in a pilot study (Schoch et al., 2017; Schoch & Ostermann, 2022) and successfully validated in three studies with samples of pictorial works by non-professionals (Schoch & Ostermann, 2022), contemporary artworks by professional artists (Schoch & Ostermann, 2020) and a mixed sample of both (Schoch & Ostermann, 2021, July 13). The data collected in these studies – image material and RizbA ratings for each image – serve as training data for the neural net.

Machine learning algorithms for 2D image recognition

Previous studies on classification of visual art show that certain features of fine art paintings can be captured and categorized (e.g., Banerji & Sinha, 2016; Cetinic et al., 2018, 2020; Hua et al., 2020; Madhu et al., 2019; Tan et al., 2016). These works focus on artist, genre, style, and time period and were trained on publicly available datasets like the WikiArt (2021) dataset. Other studies focus on the difference between art and non-art (Brachmann et al., 2017) and the aesthetics of artworks (Cetinic et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2020). Most approaches use transfer learning (Razavian et al., 2014; Rodriguez et al., 2018; Sarkar et al., 2018) meaning that they take neural nets like VGG16 (Simonyan & Zisserman, 2014) as base network and fine-tune the last layers to learn new object classes.

The pre-trained neural nets that serve as a base are trained on the ImageNet (Deng et al., 2009) dataset with around 1.2 million tagged images. The dataset originates from the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC; ImageNet, 2012, 2016), a yearly competition in which a set of 100,000 test pictures have to be classified into 1,000 categories. This object recognition task for 2D images had its breakthrough with a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) called AlexNet (Krizhevsky et al., 2012). The error rate was enhanced from 25.8% to 16.4% (ImageNet, 2012) and since 2016 it is less than 3% (ImageNet, 2016). These base networks are Open Sourced and available for download and usage.

METHOD**Experimental setup and CNN architecture**

In the current approach the VGG16 (Simonyan & Zisserman, 2014) net is used. The architecture of this model is as follows: The first layer (or input layer) uses the RGB color values of each pixel in the image as input. This is followed by 13 convolutional layers and five pooling layers. These layers comprise the base of the neural network. The header comprises three fully connected layers at the end with dropout layers in between for regularization. For the base network, pre-trained weights are used that result from the training on the ImageNet dataset. Using these, the CNN can be considered as already having some knowledge about images, for instance detecting structures.

DATA SELECTION*Image material*

The neural nets were trained on the image material collected during three previous validation studies on RizbA (Studies A, B, and C; see Table 2; availability of Open Data see Appendix). The image sample involved a total of 886 pictures. Of these, 461 are artworks by contemporary professional artists and 426 are pictorial works by non-professionals.

Non-professional artworks were defined as pictures created by a person without professional education in visual art or related disciplines. This means that contributors never received a professional art training, neither in terms of an academic degree nor having ever studied a subject related to visual arts. Some of these images were collected in an attendance study and digitized. Others were gathered via an online call to submit photographed, digitized pictures.

Professional artworks were defined as pictures created by international contemporary professional artists from different geographic regions, including Europe, Asia, Africa, Northern, and Southern America, dating from 2005 to 2020. The digital images were systematically retrieved from prometheus (prometheus, 2021; Simon & Verstegen, 2004), a distributed digital image archive which connects databases from various institutes, research facilities, museums and from WikiArt (2021), an open visual art encyclopedia, using the WikiArt API (WikiArt, 2020).

Real human expert raters

As an initial dataset, the according image ratings gathered in the three previous studies (Studies A, B, and C; see Table 2) were used, in which real human experts rated the image material using the RizbA scale. Inclusion criterion for raters was to have expertise in visual arts. Thus, only experts with an academic degree related to visual arts, or students who have been studying an art-related subject for at least one year, could participate. Studies A and B were conducted in a test-retest design. Since the retest data only served as a measure for test-retest reliability, only the first ratings were used.

Table 2

Collection of image material and RizbA ratings: Previous studies on RizbA						
		Study A (Schoch & Ostermann, 2022)	Study B (Schoch & Ostermann, 2020)	Study C (Schoch & Ostermann, 2021, July 13)		
Images	<i>N</i>	294	318	131	143	
	created by	non-professionals	professional artists	non-professionals	professional artists	
	gender (coded)	107 female 39 male one diverse	59 female 233 male 1 diverse 25 unknown	104 female 25 male 2 diverse	no metadata available	
	age	17 - 71 years (M = 33.86, SD = 14.02)	no metadata available	21 - 79 years (M = 45.80, SD = 15.12)	no metadata available	
	data collection	attendance study	prometheus	online submission	WikiArt	

Collection of image material and RizbA ratings: Previous studies on RizbA				
Real human expert raters	N	880	506	179
	gender (self-identified)	750 female 122 male 8 diverse	432 female 66 male 8 diverse	159 female 16 male 4 diverse
	age	18 - 74 years (<i>M</i> = 31.59, <i>SD</i> = 10.18)	19 - 77 years (<i>M</i> = 32.92, <i>SD</i> = 11.68)	22 - 72 years (<i>M</i> = 37.59, <i>SD</i> = 12.51).
	expertise	academic degree 65.5 % studying 34.5 %	academic degree 63.6 % studying 36.4 %	academic degree 75.42 % studying 24.58 %
	disciplines	art history 30.6 % art therapy 16.8 % art pedagogy 13.0 % visual art 11.5 % graphic design 5.3 % design 5.3 % art history and aesthetics 4.8 % restoration 1.3 % other 11.4 %	art therapy 24.9% art history 19.2 % visual art 14.6 % art pedagogy 12.8 % graphic design 4.7 % design 4.7 % art sciences 3.4% restoration 2.4 % image sciences 0.4 % other 12.8 %	art therapy 31.84 % art education 15.64 % art history 13.41 % fine arts 8.94 % art science 5.59 % graphic design 5.59 % restoration 5.03 % design 3.35 % other 10.61 %
Ratings per image		16 - 31 (<i>M</i> = 20.35, <i>SD</i> = 5.23)	1 - 19 (<i>M</i> = 9.54, <i>SD</i> = 2.50)	0 - 7 (<i>M</i> = 3.91, <i>SD</i> = 1.39)
<i>M</i> = mean, <i>N</i> = sample size, <i>SD</i> = standard deviation				

Generic raters (GR)

Since no individual human rater had rated all 886 images, different human ratings were combined to have full sets of ratings for all images. Assuming a normal distribution of the ratings, it is canonical to consider the mean value over the different human ratings of each item for each image to be the true value. Consequently, the mean was used to train the CNN.

Additionally, five generic raters were constructed to evaluate the results:

- Random rater (RR): takes a random value between 0 and 5
- Extreme rater (ER): takes always the minimum or maximum of the ratings from previous studies, whichever value is further away from 2.5, the mean of the used Likert scale
 - Over rater (OR): takes either the 25% or 75% percent quartile, whichever is further away from the mean
 - Under rater (UR): takes the 25% or 75% value closer to the mean
 - Mean rater (MR): takes the mean value.

To further evaluate the results to human ratings, four random raters (RR1 to RR4) were created. They were constructed by randomly picking one of the given values from the real human expert ratings for each picture and each item.

TRAINING

For the training of the neural network the data was split up into three sets: a training set with 690 images, a validation set with 173 images, and a test set with 23 images. The training and validation set were used during the training period, while the test set was used for the performance measurement. The test set was randomly chosen prior to the data split. The code is written in Python (2021) using the Keras framework (Chollet, 2018) and is available as Open Source (Gengenbach & Schoch, 2021). Each value on the six-point Likert scale $N = 0, \dots, 5$, was defined as a separate class and the sparse categorical crossentropy (Goodfellow et al., 2016, p. 62f.) was used. Consequently, one neural net per item had to be trained, i.e., a total of 26 different neural nets. For the training a GeForce RTX 2080 Ti (rev a1) with 11019 MiB memory graphics card from NVIDIA was used.

Parameter setup

The parameter setup of the neural net was as follows: For the net architecture a base net *VGG16* with *ImageNet weights* and a dense net with *128 / 32 / 6 with 0.5 dropout layers* (Goodfellow et al., 2016, p. 258–268) in between to reduce overfitting was used. As activation function, *relu* (Goodfellow et al., 2016, p. 193-195); and on the last layer *softmax* (Goodfellow et al., 2016, p. 184-187) to obtain probabilities for each of the classes was used. *Adam* with learning rate 10^{-4} (Goodfellow et al., 2016, p. 303–305) was used as optimizer and *sparse categorical crossentropy* as loss function. The *accuracy* interpreted as *1-error_rate* was used as metric.

Augmentation

Image augmentation is used to achieve a better performance and prevent overfitting of the neural networks when only a small image set is available for training. Augmentation artificially creates more training images by creating randomized transformations of the existing images (Chollet, 2018). The image data was augmented as illustrated in Figure 1 using the following settings: *Rotation* up to 30° , *pixel shift* width and height range up to 0.25 (up to 25% of the image up or down, left or right), *shear range* up to 20° , *zoom range* between 0.8 and 1.2, *channel shift* range up to 0.2, *horizontal* and *vertical flipping*, *brightness range* between 0.8 and 1, *scaling* of the images to 224x224 pixels. *Color values* were normalized by $1/255$ to be in the range $[0,1]$. The *fill in mode* 'nearest' was used for the new pixels that come in, due to the used augmentation.

Figure 1

Augmentation example: top left: original image from the sample next to four augmentations of the same image

Steps

The neural networks, one separate neural network for each of the 26 items, were trained and validated in two steps: The first step with 250 epochs had all VGG16 layers frozen, i.e., the pre-trained weights stay unchanged. The training therefore modified only the head, the dense (fully connected) part of the neural net. Only the best model according to the validation accuracy was stored throughout all epochs. The second step consisted of 350 epochs with the last block of VGG16 unfrozen, i.e., the weights can be adapted, if necessary. As a starting point for the second step, the best model from the first step was chosen. Again here, only the best model according to the validation accuracy was stored throughout all epochs.

Performance values

The test set, comprising 23 randomly chosen images, was used to compare the results of the trained artificial neural network to the GR and real human expert ratings. Their performance was reported using the following key performance indicators:

- Error rate in %: The percentage of errors, i.e., the prediction of the Likert scale value not matching the assumed true value
- MSE: The average squared difference between the predicted Likert scale value and the assumed true value
- Rank: The ranking of the error rates and the MSE, individually, from lowest to highest values
- Combined rank: The mean value of the error rate rank and the MSE rank from lowest to highest value; in case of a tie, the best individual rank was prioritized

RESULTS

On the test set, ART achieved a combined rank of 6 out of 9. The error rate is 56.23%, which is rank 6 out of 9; the MSE is 1.35, which is rank 5 out of 9. The performance in relation to the other raters with exact values is reported in Table 3. A more detailed view on each item's neural network with error rate and MSE is provided in Table 3. The confusion matrices (see Figure 3) show the aggregated number of hits and misses of the ART for each Likert scale value and each item's neural network. Values on the diagonal are hits, values next to the diagonal are misses. The further away from the diagonal, the higher the deviation from the assumed true value. The confusion matrix for all the different rater types over all items can be found in Figure 4.

Table 3

<i>Raters' performance: Error rate, MSE and combined rank</i>			
Rater	Error rate (Rank)	MSE (Rank)	Combined rank
ART	56.23 % (6)	1.35 (5)	6
RR	84.07 % (9)	4.91 (9)	9
ER	83.15 % (8)	2.90 (8)	8
OR	63.19 % (7)	1.21 (3)	4
UR	37.36 % (1)	0.47 (1)	1
RR1	56.04 % (5)	1.49 (7)	7
RR2	50.92 % (3)	1.23 (4)	3
RR3	48.17 % (2)	1.20 (2)	2
RR4	54.58 % (4)	1.48 (6)	5

Figure 2

Figure 3

Confusion matrices of the ART for each item's neural network

Figure 4

Aggregated confusion matrices for all raters

DISCUSSION

Rating with only a pre-trained model could be interpreted as equivalent to non-expert human raters rating pictures. These raters know what a picture is and what it usually looks like but lack knowledge in art history or RizbA. The fine-tuning in the transfer learning approach adds this expert knowledge to the ART.

The results of ART in the middle grey area in Figure 2 can be interpreted as ‘good’ in terms of error rate and MSE, since they reflect the area between the ORs and URs and are therefore in the range of the results of the human raters, i.e., RR1 to RR4. The error rate and MSE of the UR yields by construction the best result, while the OR can be considered as a lower bound for a model to be good. Only item 14 is worse in the MSE value than the ER’s MSE value. Considering the error rate for item 14 being in the expected range, this is probably an artefact in the randomly selected sample of pictures taken for testing. Also, the validation error rate during training was in the same range as the validation error of the other items. Furthermore, the assumption of this artefact in the sample can be confirmed based on the confusion matrix: The assumed true values are located on both ends of the Likert scale with only a few distributed in the center. More data – especially on items with a higher MSE and error value than the average performance – will most likely close the gap to the ratings of real human experts.

In the overall confusion matrix (see Figure 3) for the ART, a tendency towards the middle is apparent, which is stronger than for RR1 to RR4. One explanation for this might be that the training objective prioritized accuracy rather than MSE. Taking only the accuracy as loss function removes the interval scale level property of the Likert scale used. Using the MSE as a term in the loss function as well, would add this property to the ART. Another explanation is the imbalanced number of images per class in the training set. However, since the data is normally distributed, a tendency towards the middle is to be expected.

From a machine learning point of view, the performance could still be considerably improved, (i.e., closer in terms of error rate and MSE to the assumed true value) by using either more data or tuning the neural network parameters. However, the ART is in the range of UR and OR and in between RR1 to RR4 (see Figure 2) and hence indistinguishable from the real human expert raters. Finally, with a critical view on objectivism there is no absolute truth in RizbA ratings, only an assumed true value given by the mean of the real human expert ratings. However, comparing the neural network's performance values, MSE and error rate, the results are promising and allow the conclusion that the ARTs are just as reliable as the real human expert ratings.

LIMITATIONS

Sample size

The major limitations of this work are the size and diversity of the sample. In general, a sample of 886 images is a good start for an art psychological study. For the training of neural networks using the transfer learning approach, samples of 100 images per class are supposed to be sufficient. However, the topic is highly debated and depends on the task at hand (Balki et al., 2019). Since the Likert scale ratings of RizbA are normally distributed for each item and the current sample has a minimum of 70 images per class, about 1200 images would make this neural network approach more reliable.

Image augmentation was used to mitigate the small sample size. However, augmentation itself introduces variations to the images which might in turn affect the ratings. Rotating an image for example influences the horizontal and vertical layout of the image. Not introducing augmentation would however have led to an overfitted neural net. Since the augmentations were applied randomly on images and different in each epoch, we can expect that this effect cancels itself out.

Image material

The non-professional pictorial works in study A were collected in an attendance study in Germany and therefore, by definition, they cannot be globally representative. In study C an online call in German and English language was launched and internationally distributed, which resulted in an international sample. Still, using only two languages is an exclusion criterion for participants speaking only other languages.

The images by professional artists were collected via two digital databases: prometheus and WikiArt (data sets see Appendix: Open Data). Prometheus (Simon & Versteegen, 2004) includes works by international artists, but, being based in Germany, it is still biased towards European art. Also 73.4 % of the artists names are coded male, only 18.4 % female, and 0.3 % diverse. For the remaining 7.9 % coded gender is not assignable, based on the available metadata. WikiArt (2021) is a shared knowledge database, open for use by anyone without GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, museums) serving as gatekeepers.

Theoretically speaking, this should enable more data diversity. Practically speaking, however, the metadata lacks the artists' self-identified gender and other diversity indicators (Nishikawa-Pacher et al., 2021). Unfortunately, the gender and diversity bias in the data reflects the current art world, which is dominated by *white* cis male Eurocentric and Northern American perspectives (Fraiberger, Sinatra, Resch, Riedl, & Barabási, 2018). This bias in the image material is inherent to the ART. Only images from artists with the same background as the training data set can be rated reliably.

Real human rater sample

The majority of raters self-identify as female, some male, and some diverse. All experts needed to be German speakers in order to participate, which resulted in most raters coming from Germany, Austria, and Switzerland. Consequently, the rater sample and as a result also the ARTs are afflicted with a Eurocentric bias.

IMPLICATIONS

The resulting application can be used for a more efficient analysis in art psychology and various other art-related fields of research, documentation, and art databases.

Firstly, it can be used to facilitate a variety of research related to visual art which involves the need for large numbers of numeric measurements of images. The application allows for a relatively easy rating experience without having to conduct the tedious process of rating 26 items per picture by many real human expert raters. Possible fields of research are for example, art psychology, in particular empirical aesthetics, but also art pedagogy, art history, art therapy.

Secondly, there are various possible fields of application. For example, it has potential as an economic tool for documenting and analyzing artworks in different application areas such as artistic processes, art education, and other art-related practices. For example, the application can be used in art therapy to consistently model the progress of therapeutic sessions on a pictorial level. In clinical practice there is little time for extensive documentation. By using ARTs this can be done with relatively little effort, providing a delta analysis for art therapy sessions. As a safety check, the recorded changes can be analyzed against the therapist's impressions. A third field of application is the systematization of art-related digital databases. By rating whole image inventories, the systematic search in databases can be enhanced. Instead of searching artworks only by keywords (e.g., epochs, artist, subject) it could also be browsed by genuinely formal characteristic features such as representation, color, or composition. Other fields of application might be computer vision, marketing, or advertisement.

FURTHER RESEARCH

The current training approach uses *accuracy* as metric with the *sparse categorical crossentropy* as the loss function. A different loss function using the interval scale property of the data might give a lower MSE. Furthermore, hyperparameter-optimization of the model might lead to better validation results in terms of accuracy, i.e., hitting the assumed true value. However, this will not necessarily result in a better model compared to human raters.

Further attention should be paid to the fact that the items' neural networks differ in the quality of their performance. A variance in the statistical quality of items is also reflected in the data of previous studies with human raters only. For example, items such as *The manner of representation is abstract* (item 4) provide more reliable results than items such as *The picture appears to be diffuse* (item 24; Schoch et al., 2017; Schoch & Ostermann, 2020, 2022). This is probably due to some tasks being easier to rate since they refer to more objective criteria than others. Further studies should empirically compare and theoretically discuss possible similarities and differences between human raters and neural networks when it comes to statistical quality criteria.

Since art and several psychological variables differ across geographical regions (Cattaneo, 1994), it can be assumed that there are global differences in creating and perceiving art as well. Future studies should take gender, geographical region, and other relevant diversity variables of the image material more into account with a critical view on Eurocentrism (Mosquera, 1992) and paternalistic structures. Also the real human rater sample needs to be extended to experts from all geographical regions, aiming for a decolonial coding (Ali, 2014). Since the ARTs reflect biases in image material and rater data, they must be trained on diverse samples of both. Only if neural nets are fed with diverse data, their results can be generalized.

Due to colonial continuities, European and Northern American art science still lacks truly diverse and universal perspectives, claiming universality for something that is not universal (Grant & Price, 2020). Thinking this further, not only the samples are biased but also the art theory behind the approach of formal picture analysis. In its way of thinking, RizbA refers to European theorists, such as Husserl (Uzelac, 1998), Panofsky (2006), or Mersch (2019) and is biased towards a *white* male gaze on art, which needs to be mitigated in future research. For this purpose, various global perspectives on art reception (e.g., indigenous art practices) should be considered and, if compatible, implemented in machine learning.

CONCLUSION

Although the image and human rater samples should prospectively become larger and more diverse, the results of the neural networks are

promising. ART ratings can be seen as equivalent to human expert raters for almost all items in RizbA. Future training with more data will probably close the gap to the human expert raters on all items and offers broad implications for art psychological research and practice.

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INDICES

<i>ICC</i>	<i>Intra-Class Correlations</i>
<i>M</i>	Mean
MSE	Mean Squared Error
<i>N</i>	Sample size
η^2	Eta-squared
<i>r</i>	Test-retest reliability
<i>SD</i>	Standard deviation

ABBREVIATIONS

ART	Artificial Intelligence Rater
API	Application programming interface
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
ER	Extreme rater
GR	Generic rater
ILSVRC	ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge
MR	Mean rater
OR	Over rater
RGB	Red, green, blue
RizbA	Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works
RR	Random rater
RR1	Randomly picked generic rater 1
RR2	Randomly picked generic rater 2
RR3	Randomly picked generic rater 3
RR4	Randomly picked generic rater 4
UR	Under rater

ADDITIONAL MATERIAL

This study is conducted under terms of Open Science. The application's source code as Open Source, Open Data, and Open Methodology are freely available under a CC-BY 4.0 license as follows.

Open Source

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Open Data

Study A On request to the according authors for research purposes only

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Appendix A: Itempool

Table 6

Item Pool: Items and statistical quality criteria, Original German version (Study 1)

Item	Content area	Item stem	Item description	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>s_i²</i>	<i>p_i</i>	η_p^2	<i>ICC</i>
1	RE	<i>Das Bild enthält</i>	<i>zeichnerische Elemente</i>	2.68	0.43	0.19	.54	0.57	0.57
2	RE		<i>malerische Elemente</i>	3.28	0.51	0.26	.66	0.48	0.47
3	RE	<i>Die Darstellungsweise ist</i>	<i>gegenständlich</i>	2.14	0.38	0.14	.43	0.71	0.70
4 ²	RE		<i>abstrahiert</i>	2.42	0.47	0.22	.48	0.25	0.20
5	RE		<i>abstrakt</i>	2.55	0.35	0.13	.51	0.62	0.61
6	RE	<i>Der Farbauftrag ist</i>	<i>pastos</i>	2.48	0.58	0.34	.50	0.53	0.52
7 ²	RE		<i>lasierend</i>	2.32	0.51	0.26	.46	0.41	0.39
8 ²	CO	<i>Die vorherrschende</i>	<i>hell</i>	2.65	0.52	0.27	.53	0.20	0.15
9 ²	CO	<i>Farbgebung ist</i>	<i>dunkel</i>	1.88	0.54	0.29	.38	0.43	0.42
10 ¹	CO		<i>kräftig</i>	2.94	0.29	0.08	.59	0.60	0.59
11 ²	CO		<i>zart</i>	1.88	0.46	0.22	.38	0.33	0.30
12	CO		<i>leuchtend</i>	2.62	0.33	0.11	.52	0.59	0.58
13 ¹²	CO		<i>trüb</i>	1.66	0.30	0.09	.33	0.23	0.18
14 ¹	CO	<i>Im Bild befinden sich</i>	<i>bunte Farben</i>	2.21	0.30	0.09	.44	0.55	0.55
15 ²	CO	<i>vorwiegend</i>	<i>unbunte Farben (Unfarben)</i>	2.16	0.46	0.21	.43	0.34	0.31
16	CO		<i>reine Farben</i>	2.39	0.37	0.13	.48	0.53	0.52
17 ²	CO		<i>gedämpfte Farben</i>	1.86	0.33	0.11	.37	0.43	0.41
18 ²	CO		<i>kalte Farben</i>	1.82	0.63	0.40	.36	0.28	0.25
19 ²	CO		<i>warme Farben</i>	2.14	0.41	0.17	.43	0.49	0.48
20 ²	CO		<i>Grundfarben (Primärfarben)</i>	2.32	0.36	0.13	.46	0.49	0.48

Item	Content area	Item stem	Item description	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>s_i²</i>	<i>p_i</i>	η_p^2	<i>ICC</i>
21	CO		<i>Mischfarben (Sekundärfarben)</i>	2.40	0.39	0.15	.48	0.56	0.56
22 ²	CO		<i>Missfarben (Tertiärfarben)</i>	1.72	0.43	0.18	.34	0.38	0.35
23 ²	CO	<i>Im Bild sind folgende Farbkontraste vorhanden</i>	<i>Farbe-an-sich-Kontrast (Primärfarbenkontrast)</i>	2.57	0.62	0.39	.51	0.40	0.38
24 ²	CO		<i>Hell-Dunkel-Kontrast</i>	3.46	0.53	0.28	.69	0.25	0.21
25 ²	CO		<i>Kalt-Warm-Kontrast</i>	2.54	0.57	0.32	.51	0.48	0.46
26	CO		<i>Komplementärkontrast</i>	2.43	0.42	0.18	.49	0.59	0.58
27 ²³	CO		<i>Qualitätskontrast</i>	2.31	0.64	0.40	.46	0.15	0.09
28 ²³	CO		<i>Quantitätskontrast</i>	2.49	0.63	0.40	.50	0.16	0.11
29	SH	<i>Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend</i>	<i>organisch</i>	2.45	0.39	0.15	.49	0.56	0.56
30	SH		<i>geometrisch</i>	2.47	0.36	0.13	.49	0.58	0.57
31 ¹	SH		<i>eckig</i>	2.07	0.30	0.09	.41	0.69	0.69
32 ²	SH		<i>rund</i>	2.36	0.54	0.29	.47	0.41	0.39
33 ²	SH		<i>zart</i>	1.85	0.33	0.11	.37	0.43	0.41
34 ²	SH		<i>dominant</i>	2.70	0.45	0.20	.54	0.46	0.45
35 ²	SH		<i>reduziert</i>	2.85	0.47	0.22	.57	0.33	0.30
36 ¹	SH		<i>zusammenhängend</i>	3.03	0.26	0.07	.61	0.57	0.56
37 ¹²	SH		<i>fragmentiert, unzusammenhängend</i>	2.00	0.31	0.09	.40	0.51	0.49
38 ¹	SH	<i>Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend</i>	<i>gerade</i>	2.14	0.27	0.08	.43	0.61	0.60
39	SH		<i>gebogen</i>	2.31	0.47	0.22	.46	0.58	0.57
40 ²	SH		<i>rund</i>	2.07	0.47	0.22	.41	0.43	0.41
41	SH		<i>eckig</i>	1.78	0.53	0.28	.36	0.58	0.58
42 ²	SH		<i>weich</i>	2.41	0.41	0.17	.48	0.45	0.43
43 ²	SH		<i>hart</i>	2.00	0.66	0.44	.40	0.32	0.30
44 ²	SH		<i>dick</i>	2.28	0.53	0.28	.46	0.37	0.35
45 ²	SH		<i>dünn</i>	2.01	0.46	0.21	.40	0.48	0.47
46 ²	SH		<i>druckvoll</i>	2.36	0.59	0.34	.47	0.34	0.32

Item	Content area	Item stem	Item description	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>s_i²</i>	<i>p_i</i>	η_p^2	<i>ICC</i>
47 ²	SH		<i>stark, kräftig</i>	2.85	0.43	0.19	.57	0.30	0.27
48 ¹²	SH		<i>zart, sachte</i>	2.01	0.29	0.08	.40	0.42	0.40
49 ²	SH		<i>senkrecht</i>	1.95	0.47	0.22	.39	0.39	0.37
50 ²	SH		<i>waagrecht</i>	1.73	0.51	0.26	.35	0.51	0.50
51 ⁴	SH		<i>schräg, diagonal</i>	2.25	0.47	0.22	.45	0.59	0.58
52 ²	SH		<i>überschneidend</i>	2.32	0.60	0.37	.46	0.22	0.19
53 ²	SH		<i>unterbrochen</i>	1.99	0.78	0.61	.40	0.27	0.25
54 ²	SH		<i>schwungvoll</i>	2.82	0.45	0.21	.56	0.40	0.38
55 ²³	SH		<i>stockend</i>	1.48	0.72	0.52	.30	0.06	0.02
56 ²	SH	<i>Die Linienführung</i>	<i>variiert</i>	2.41	0.47	0.22	.48	0.25	0.21
57 ²	SH	<i>Das Bild</i>	<i>wirkt flächig</i>	3.00	0.59	0.35	.60	0.33	0.31
58 ²	SH		<i>enthält Formkontraste</i>	2.94	0.48	0.23	.59	0.35	0.33
59 ²	SH		<i>enthält klare Abgrenzungen zwischen den Flächen</i>	3.22	0.68	0.46	.64	0.27	0.25
60 ²	SH		<i>enthält Flächen, die ineinander übergehen</i>	2.32	0.68	0.46	.46	0.36	0.34
61	SH		<i>enthält unbearbeitete Flächen</i>	2.33	0.34	0.11	.47	0.62	0.62
62 ²	SP	<i>Das Bild wirkt</i>	<i>zweidimensional</i>	2.70	0.52	0.27	.54	0.34	0.31
63 ²	SP		<i>dreidimensional</i>	1.82	0.58	0.33	.36	0.40	0.39
64	SP		<i>tief</i>	2.12	0.35	0.13	.42	0.44	0.42
65 ²	SP		<i>flach</i>	2.31	0.46	0.21	.46	0.33	0.30
66 ²	SP		<i>plastisch, räumlich</i>	2.32	0.44	0.19	.46	0.39	0.37
67 ²	SP		<i>den (Bild-)Raum ausschöpfend, den Raum erfüllend</i>	3.59	0.59	0.34	.72	0.35	0.36
68	SP	<i>Das Bild ist</i>	<i>perspektivisch</i>	2.03	0.44	0.20	.41	0.61	0.61
69 ²³	SP		<i>perspektivisch verzerrt (unperspektivisch)</i>	1.34	0.67	0.45	.27	0.11	0.06
70	SP		<i>frei von Perspektive (aperspektivisch)</i>	2.15	0.40	0.16	.43	0.47	0.46
71 ²	MO	<i>Das Bild ist</i>	<i>ruhig</i>	2.09	0.39	0.15	.42	0.34	0.31
72	MO		<i>unruhig</i>	2.35	0.42	0.17	.47	0.44	0.42

Item	Content area	Item stem	Item description	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>s_i²</i>	<i>p_i</i>	η_p^2	<i>ICC</i>
73	MO		wild	1.86	0.51	0.26	.37	0.44	0.43
74 ²	MO		bewegt	2.71	0.59	0.35	.54	0.27	0.24
75 ²	MO		dynamisch	2.70	0.47	0.22	.54	0.19	0.14
76 ²	MO		starr	1.52	0.45	0.21	.30	0.20	0.15
77 ²	MO		expandierend, sich ausweitend	2.63	0.38	0.15	.53	0.27	0.23
78 ²³	MO	Die Bewegung im Bild ist	klein	2.12	0.56	0.31	.42	0.10	0.04
79 ²³	MO		groß	2.51	0.63	0.40	.50	0.15	0.10
80 ²	MO		geordnet	2.85	0.44	0.19	.57	0.32	0.30
81 ²³	MO		zielgerichtet	2.50	0.48	0.23	.50	0.13	0.07
82 ²	MO		chaotisch	1.75	0.46	0.21	.35	0.41	0.40
83	COM	Die Gesamtkomposition ist	senkrecht angelegt	2.34	0.51	0.26	.47	0.54	0.53
84	COM		waagrecht angelegt	1.60	0.55	0.31	.32	0.46	0.45
85	COM		diagonal angelegt	2.30	0.49	0.24	.46	0.47	0.45
86 ²	COM		einfach	2.80	0.43	0.19	.56	0.25	0.21
87 ²	COM		komplex	2.29	0.49	0.24	.46	0.23	0.20
88 ²	COM		vielseitig	2.37	0.51	0.26	.47	0.19	0.15
89 ²	COM		offen	2.55	0.54	0.29	.51	0.26	0.23
90 ²	COM		geschlossen	2.21	0.53	0.29	.44	0.34	0.32
91 ²³	COM		gegliedert	2.93	0.43	0.18	.59	0.13	0.08
92 ²	COM		im Gleichgewicht	2.93	0.43	0.19	.59	0.36	0.33
93 ²	COM		symmetrisch	1.74	0.42	0.17	.35	0.23	0.19
94 ²³	COM		asymmetrisch	2.74	0.62	0.38	.55	0.19	0.14
95	COM		flächendeckend ohne Hauptmotiv (All-Over-Structure)	1.60	0.53	0.28	.32	0.42	0.41
96 ²	COM	kein Itemstamm	Figur und Grund sind voneinander unterscheidbar	3.27	0.59	0.35	.65	0.27	0.24
97 ²³	COM	kein Itemstamm	Bildobjekte stehen separat	2.81	0.54	0.29	.56	0.19	0.14
98 ²	COM	kein Itemstamm	Bildobjekte verschmelzen	2.00	0.65	0.42	.40	0.28	0.25

Item	Content area	Item stem	Item description	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	s_i^2	p_i	η_p^2	<i>ICC</i>
99 ²	COM	<i>Der Schwerpunkt des Bildes liegt in der</i>	<i>oberen Bildhälfte</i>	2.40	0.53	0.28	.48	0.40	0.39
100 ²	COM		<i>unteren Bildhälfte</i>	2.42	0.59	0.35	.48	0.34	0.32
101 ²³	COM		<i>linken Bildhälfte</i>	2.65	1.01	1.03	.53	0.12	0.09
102 ²	COM		<i>rechten Bildhälfte</i>	2.19	0.67	0.45	.44	0.19	0.15
103 ¹	EX	<i>Das Bild wirkt</i>	<i>leicht</i>	2.24	0.24	0.06	.45	0.47	0.45
104 ²	EX		<i>schwer</i>	1.86	0.46	0.21	.37	0.35	0.33
105 ²	EX		<i>lebendig</i>	3.07	0.41	0.17	.61	0.28	0.25
106 ²	EX		<i>starr</i>	1.73	0.36	0.13	.35	0.24	0.19
107	EX		<i>diffus</i>	1.80	0.37	0.14	.36	0.42	0.40
108 ²	EX		<i>verschwommen</i>	1.42	0.49	0.24	.28	0.22	0.19
109	EX		<i>präzise, exakt</i>	2.40	0.42	0.18	.48	0.45	0.44
110 ²	EX		<i>symbolisch aufgeladen</i>	2.44	0.83	0.69	.49	0.36	0.35
111	EX		<i>harmonisch</i>	2.60	0.49	0.24	.52	0.35	0.37
112 ²	EX		<i>widersprüchlich</i>	1.94	0.53	0.28	.39	0.33	0.31
113 ²	EX	<i>ausdrucksstark</i>	3.07	0.59	0.35	.61	0.21	0.20	

Note. Item selection: Item included based on ¹ = item variance ($s_i^2 < 0.10$), ² = inter-rater reliability (*ICC*; different criteria for each content area), ³ = capacity of differentiation (η_p^2 ; bottom 10% of the distribution), ⁴ = inter-item correlation ($r \geq .80$); Content areas: RE = *representation*, CO = *color*, SH = *shaping*, SP = *spatiality*, MO = *motion*, COM = *composition*, EX = *expression*; Statistical parameters: *M* = mean (0 = *strongly disagree*, 5 = *strongly agree*), *SD* = item standard deviation, s_i^2 = item variance, p_i = item difficulty, η_p^2 = effect size estimator partial eta-squared, *ICC* = intraclass correlation coefficient

Appendix B: RizbA with explanatory notes

Schoch, K. (2020, April 24). Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten (RizbA): Fragebogen mit Erläuterungen in deutscher Sprache [Rating instrument for two-dimensional pictorial works (RizbA): Questionnaire with explanatory notes in German]. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.376522>

Ratinginstrument für zweidimensionale bildnerische Arbeiten

(RizbA; Schoch, 2020)

INSTRUKTIONEN

Im Folgenden werden Ihnen **Bilder** präsentiert. Ihre Aufgabe ist es, jedes Bild **anhand des Fragebogens auf bildnerische Aspekte hin zu beurteilen**. Zu diesen gehören Aspekte wie Darstellungsweise, Farbe, Form, Raum, Bewegung, Komposition und Ausdruck.

Bitte **kreuzen Sie an, inwieweit die folgenden Eigenschaften auf das Werk zutreffen**. Beziehen sie sich dabei auf den **vorherrschenden Gesamteindruck** des Bildes und **nicht auf einzelne Bilddetails**. Dabei gibt es keine richtigen oder falschen Antworten. Es zählt allein **Ihre persönliche Einschätzung**.

Auch falls es Ihnen schwerfallen sollte, **beantworten Sie bitte alle Fragen**. Falls Sie sich nicht sicher sein sollten, wählen Sie bitte das am ehesten zutreffende Feld aus.

Beispiel:

trifft über- haupt nicht zu	trifft nicht zu	trifft eher nicht zu	trifft eher zu	trifft voll- kommen zu
				x

BILD —	trifft überhaupt nicht zu	trifft nicht zu	trifft eher nicht zu	trifft eher zu	trifft zu	trifft voll- kommen zu	Erläuterungen zu Fachbegriffen
1 Das Bild enthält zeichnerische Elemente							zeichnerisch: grafisch ausgeführt, Zeichnungen (z.B. Bleistift, Kohle, Kreide, Tusche)
2 Das Bild enthält malerische Elemente							malerisch: malerisch mit Farben ausgeführt (z.B. Aquarell, Ölmalerei, Mischtechnik)
3 Die Darstellungsweise ist gegenständlich							gegenständlich: der Wirklichkeit entsprechend (z.B. Personen, Landschaften, Objekte)
4 Die Darstellungsweise ist abstrakt							abstrakt: gegenstandslos, gegenstandsfrei, losgelöst von Wirklichkeitsbezug
5 Der Farbauftrag ist pastos							pastos: teigig, dicke Farbschichten
6 Die vorherrschende Farbgebung ist leuchtend							leuchtend: vermittelt aufgrund seiner Farbe den Eindruck von Licht, Helligkeit
7 Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend reine Farben							Primärfarben: Grundfarben: Gelb, Magentarot, Cyanblau
8 Im Bild befinden sich vorwiegend Mischfarben (Sekundärfarben)							Sekundärfarben: Farben, die durch Mischen zweier Primärfarben entstehen: Violett, Grün, Orange

9	Im Bild sind Komplementärkontraste vorhanden									<p>Komplementärkontrast: Farbpaar, das aus jeweils einer Primär- und einer Sekundärfarbe besteht und sich im Farbkreis gegenüberliegt: Gelb - Violett, Magentarot - Grün, Cyanblau - Orange</p>
10	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend organisch									<p>organisch: lebenden Wesen, deren Teilen oder biologischen Produkten nachempfunden</p>
11	Im Bild enthaltene Formen sind vorwiegend geometrisch									<p>geometrisch: weist Formen der Geometrie auf (z.B. Dreiecke, Kreise, Punkte)</p>
12	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend gebogen									
13	Die Linienführung verläuft vorwiegend eckig									
14	Das Bild enthält unbearbeitete Flächen									<p>unbearbeitete Flächen: freie Flächen, die nicht bildnerisch bearbeitet wurden</p>
15	Das Bild wirkt tief									<p>tief: erzeugt Tiefenwirkung</p>
16	Das Bild ist perspektivisch									<p>perspektivisch: vermittelt Dreidimensionalität auf einer ebenen Bildfläche</p>
17	Das Bild ist frei von Perspektive (aperspektivisch)									<p>aperspektivisch: ohne Konstruktion einer dreidimensionalen Perspektive</p>

18 Das Bild ist unruhig									
19 Das Bild ist wild									
20 Die Gesamtkomposition ist senkrecht angelegt									Komposition: Aufbau und Gliederung des Werks
21 Die Gesamtkomposition ist waagrecht angelegt									Komposition: s.o.
22 Die Gesamtkomposition ist diagonal angelegt									Komposition: s.o.
23 Die Gesamtkomposition ist flächendeckend ohne Hauptmotiv (All-Over-Structure)									Komposition: s.o. All-Over-Structure: flächendeckende Struktur ohne Hauptmotiv
24 Das Bild wirkt diffus									diffus: unklar, ungeordnet, konturlos, verschwommen
25 Das Bild wirkt präzise, exakt									
26 Das Bild wirkt harmonisch									harmonisch: ausgewogenes Verhältnis, was Kontraste nicht ausschließt

Curriculum vitae

Education

- 06/2016 – 06/2022 Witten/Herdecke University
Faculty of Health,
Department Psychology and Psychotherapy,
Chair for research methods and statistics in psychology
Dissertation project (Dr. phil.)
- 08/2010 – 03/2014 University of Mannheim
School of Social Sciences
Psychologist (B.Sc.)
- 04/2005 – 06/2005 Hogeschool van Arnhem en Nijmegen (NL)
Creative Arts Therapies (visual art)
Erasmus
- 10/2003 – 02/2008 HKT Nürtingen – University of Applied Sciences and Arts
Art therapist (Dipl.-Kunsttherap. (FH))
- 09/1993 – 06/2002 Zabergäu Gymnasium Brackenheim
Abitur

Work (excerpt)

- since 01/2021 HKS – University of Applied Sciences and Arts Ottersberg
The Pop-up Institute: Reducing stigma by means of Creative
Arts Therapies, funded by the Volkswagen Foundation
Co-founder and research assistant
- 07/2020 – 06/2020 Open Science Fellow Program, Wikimedia Germany, Berlin
Mentoring
- since 03/2020 Sigmund Freud Private University Berlin
Assistant lecturer
- since 09/2019 Nürtingen-Geislingen University
Assistant lecturer

09/2019 – 08/2021	HKS University of Applied Sciences and Arts Ottersberg Equal opportunities representant
09/2016 – 12/2020	HKS – University of Applied Sciences and Arts Ottersberg Institute for art therapy and research, Research focus on artistic interventions in health promotion and prevention, funded by Volkswagen Foundation Research assistant
05/2017	SRH University of Applied Sciences Heidelberg School of Social and Legal Sciences Assistant lecturer
04/2014 – 02/2017	Hochschule Mannheim – University of Applied Sciences Faculty social work Assistant lecturer
09/2014 – 12/2016	Zentralinstitut für Seelische Gesundheit, Mannheim Department of child and adolescent psychiatry and psychotherapy Artistic and art therapeutic project work
07/2009 – 12/2015	Children and youth services Wespinstift, Mannheim Intensive care for children and adolescents at risk of mental disability Therapeutic specialist service, art therapist
04/2009 – 06/2009	County clinic Darmstadt-Dieburg Neurological rehabilitation Art therapist
06/2008 – 12/2010	Autonomous women’s shelter Heidelberg Projects with children who experienced domestic violence Art therapist
since 2008	kunsthochzwei Freelance work art, art therapy, and blogging

Affidavit

I hereby confirm that this dissertation is result of my own work that I have explicitly identified and named all support received from third parties and that I have only used sources or materials listed and specified in the references. I have not submitted this dissertation in this or any similar form to any other university.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'K. Schoch', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Kerstin Schoch

Berlin, May 25, 2022